

Risk assessment of persistent chlorinated and brominated environmental pollutants in food

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Preface

During 2006 and 2007, the Swedish National Food Administration (NFA) has worked with the scientific documentation for a revision of the consumption advisory for fish that contain high levels of methyl mercury (MeHg) and persistent halogenated organic pollutants. This report summarizes the current knowledge on levels of persistent chlorinated and brominated organic pollutants in fish and other foods in Sweden. In addition, the exposure of Swedish consumers and the epidemiological studies which have been conducted on different populations in the world are described. The most important risk assessments are also summarized. Finally, a comparison is made between the exposures the Swedish population faces and exposures at different levels of risk as determined by the risk assessments.

NFA's advice on fish consumption is currently based upon separate nutritional and toxicological assessments. In the revision of the advice regarding contaminated fish, a health-based risk/benefit analysis of fish consumption will be conducted before the revised advice is formulated. Knowledge on the beneficial aspects of fish consumption has been summarized within the project "*Risk/benefit analysis of fish consumption*". The final report of risk/benefit-analysis project is published simultaneously with the present report.

Many experts, within the NFA as well as external experts, have contributed to this report. We would like to particularly thank the participants in the external expert group meeting "*Environmental compounds in fish - a health risk?*", which took place at the end of March, 2006.

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Executive summary

This report documents the scientific basis for the Swedish National Food Administration's (NFA) risk assessment of persistent organic halogenated environmental contaminants in food. The risk assessment is part of the work associated with a revision of NFA's advice to consumers with regard to fish contaminated with polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and polychlorinated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins (PCDDs) and polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDFs).

PCBs are industrial chemicals which have been prohibited in most countries of the world for many years. Levels of PCBs in the environment have dropped since the 1970's. PCDD/Fs (dioxins) are compounds that are produced unintentionally during combustion processes and when certain chemicals are produced. Great emphasis has been placed on minimizing the presence of these contaminants in the environment. NFA's risk assessment focus mainly on PCDD/F (dioxins) and PCBs, even though there are many other organic halogenated environmental contaminants in food.

Current knowledge indicates that PCBs and dioxins are the halogenated compounds that have the largest potential to cause negative health effects among the human population. Exposure to DDT compounds in Sweden is low as compared with the levels that the World Health Organization (WHO) considers to be safe. Extensive international epidemiological research on the potential health risks of DDT compounds suggest that the compounds are not a significant health risk in Sweden. Current knowledge about brominated flame retardant compounds suggest that there is enough of a margin between exposure from food in Sweden and the levels at which there is an increased risk for health effects in animal experiments.

Levels in food

Levels of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and DDT compounds have decreased in the Swedish environment and in food on the Swedish market since the beginning of the 1970's. Studies conducted by researchers at the Swedish Museum of Natural History, however, show that levels of PCDD/Fs in herring from the east and west coasts of Sweden have not decreased since the beginning of the 1990's. NFA's studies show that fish and fish products contain the highest levels of PCDD/Fs and PCBs among all of the tested food products. Other foods of animal origin generally have lower levels than fish. Fruit and vegetables were found to have the lowest levels. The highest levels were found in fatty, wild-caught, fish from the Baltic Sea and

the Bothnian Bay (in the text below referred to as the Baltic Sea) and the lakes Vänern and Vättern. The contaminated fish species in the Baltic Sea are herring, salmon, brown trout and eel, for Lake Vänern the species are salmon and brown trout, and for Lake Vättern the species are salmon, brown trout and arctic char. The levels of PCBs and PCDD/Fs can vary depending on the location where the fish have been caught, the age of the fish, and the season and the year in which the fish have been caught.

Food consumption and intake of PCBs and dioxins

Intake calculations, based upon food consumption surveys among children (study title: Riksmaten – barn 2003) and among adults (study title: Riksmaten 1997-98), show that intake of PCBs and dioxins comes mainly from foods of animal origin. On average, consumption of fish and shell fish accounts for about 30-50% of the intake among children and adults, the rest comes from other types of food. Children have, on average, a slightly higher intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs per kilo body weight than adults. The median intake among children of ages 4-12 years was 1.7 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day, whereas the median intake among adults of ages 18-75 years was 1.1 pg/kg/day. This difference is due to the fact that children eat more food in relation to their body weight. Consumption of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea (herring and wild-caught salmon) was generally very low among participants in the food consumption surveys. Seventy percent of children in the study Riksmaten – barn 2003 never ate this type of fish. For women between the ages of 17 and 40 years, this type of fish contributed to only 2% of the total intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs from fish. Among men and older women the contribution of intake from fatty Baltic Sea fish to the total intake from fish was about 40%. Only 3% of women between the ages of 17 and 40 had a consumption rate of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea that was over NFA's current advisory rate of once per month. Consumption of the other types of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea, Bothnian Bay, Lake Vänern, and Lake Vättern, which are included in NFA's current advisory, is most likely also very low for the general consumer in Sweden.

Intake calculations for individuals with a high consumption of contaminated fish were based upon Swedish studies of adult consumers with long-term high consumption rates (several times a month or more) of fatty Baltic Sea and Lake Vättern fish. Calculations show that high consumers can reach intake levels which lie about 4-7 times greater than the median intake rate from the study Riksmaten 1997-98. In an extreme case, where one consumer indicated a long-term consumption of contaminated fish of more than once a day, the intake was 40 times higher than the median intake in Riksmaten.

Body burdens

Swedish studies of groups with high consumption of fatty PCB- and PCDD/F-contaminated fish reveal that these groups generally have significantly higher levels of environmental pollutants in the body (body burden) than groups which have reported low or no consumption of such fish. Studies of mother's milk collected in the Stockholm region show that the body burdens of PCBs and dioxins have decreased significantly from the early 1970s to the late 1990s among women in child-bearing ages. Studies on primiparous women from the Uppsala region between 1996 and 2004 have shown that PCB and dioxin levels have continued to decrease at a rate of three to nine percent per year, depending on the substance. Furthermore, levels of PCBs were considerably lower among young male conscripts sampled year 2000 than among conscripts sampled 2004. Taken together, these studies show that exposure from food has decreased in Sweden since the 1970s. Studies of PCB and DDT contaminants in blood among older women and in breast milk among younger women from different regions of Sweden show that average levels vary little between different regions (with less than a factor of two).

Risk assessments

Assessments of health risks caused by dioxins and PCBs are based upon animal studies. The extensive epidemiological research on health risks associated with PCB and dioxin exposure, nationally as well as internationally, can not yet be used to estimate a safe intake level of the compounds. This is due to weaknesses in exposure assessment and uncertainties regarding causality of associations between exposure and disease.

The goal of risk assessment is to establish a tolerable intake of the compounds in question, often presented as a tolerable weekly or monthly intake (TVI/TMI). It is the long-term PCB and dioxin intake level which determines the accumulation of contaminants in the body. Short-term variation of intake has less significance. For the sake of simplicity, the tolerable intakes are presented here as a daily tolerable intake (TDI), and they mirror the average intake level which in the long term is considered to be safe from a health perspective.

EU's Scientific Committee on Food has determined a TDI for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs of 2 pg toxicity equivalents (TEQ)/kg body weight/day. This TDI is based on reproduction effects on male offspring after gestational exposure of female rats. This TDI is about ten times lower than the lowest observed adverse exposure level (LOAEL) from the animal studies. From a toxicological perspective, this safety margin may be too small since EU's expert group did not take into account that there can be differences in sensitivities (toxicodynamics) for dioxin-like substances among individuals in the human population. EU's TDI are aimed at the population groups which can become pregnant (girls and women in

childbearing years), because it is based upon the effects which occur in the foetus after an exposure of the mother during a long time period before pregnancy.

Among children from Taiwan and Japan, which were exposed to extremely high PCB and/or dioxin levels during the foetal stage, several negative health effects have been reported, among other, lower birth weight, decreased growth rates during childhood, delayed development of the central nervous system, higher rates of certain infectious diseases and negative effects on tooth development. The relatively low body burdens of dioxins and PCBs, which pregnant women have in Sweden, does not result in such serious health effects. Nevertheless, studies of children from Sweden, Finland, USA, Canada, the Netherlands, Germany and Japan, exposed to low levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs during the foetal stage, have suggested effects that are similar to those observed in highly exposed children, but more subtle and hard to detect. Other studies have not been able to verify some of these effect, which makes it difficult to draw conclusions about if there are risks at low exposure levels. If there are risks, they are most probably so subtle that they are difficult to discover in epidemiological studies.

An expert group from the NFA and the Institute of Environmental Medicine (IMM), at Karolinska Institutet, has conducted a risk assessment of long-term exposure to dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs after birth. This risk assessment is mainly relevant for men and for women after menopause. The expert group concluded that epidemiological as well as animal studies have shown that negative effects occur at higher exposure levels after post-natal exposure than at pre-natal exposure. The negative health effect which occurred at the lowest doses in animal studies during long-term exposure after birth was cancer and disturbances of the immune system.

A TDI-interval of 2-10 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day was suggested, based upon the cancer effects. In contrast to the EU risk assessment of foetal exposure, the Swedish expert group took into consideration that there may be individual differences in sensitivity (toxicodynamics) to dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in the human population. This resulted in a TDI at 10 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. It was also considered that cancer is a serious effect, which resulted in a TDI of 2 pg/TEQ/kg body weight/day. Within this TDI interval (2-10 pg TEQ/kg body weight) the possible cancer risks were considered to be very low or non-existent.

Swedish epidemiological studies of commercial fishing families with high consumption of fish contaminated with PCBs or dioxins have so far not revealed strong associations between exposure and negative health effects. There are however uncertainties which make it impossible to rule out that negative health effects occur among adults with frequent consumption of contaminated fish in Sweden. For instance, several studies from Sweden and USA have shown that diabetes patients have higher levels of PCBs and dioxins, as well as the DDT-

compounds p,p'-DDE, in their blood than groups which do not have diabetes. It is not possible to draw conclusions about whether the compounds are risk factors for diabetes or if the higher blood levels are a result of the disease.

Risk assessment of exposure of boys before puberty is complicated by the fact that there are no animal studies with specific focus on the period of time which corresponds to the childhood period. Epidemiological studies have not yet unambiguously allowed conclusions about causality between back-ground exposure for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs during childhood and health effects such as infectious diseases and asthma/allergies, which have been observed in children from the Netherlands and Germany. Epidemiological studies of health effects in populations from Taiwan and Italy, which were exposed to very high levels of dioxins (and in some cases PCBs), have, however, indicated that groups which were exposed during childhood before puberty have greater risks for negative health effects (chloracne and a skewed sex ratio of offspring) than do groups which were exposed at older age. In addition, the results suggested that boys with high exposure are more sensitive for reproductive disorders (skewed sex ratio of offspring) than are girls.

Comparisons of TDI and intake levels in Sweden

Over 90% of women between the ages of 17 and 40 years, which participated in Riksmaten – 1997-98, had a long-term intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs which is below EU's TDI for foetal effects of 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. About 5% had an intake that was higher than the TDI and many of these women declared a relatively high consumption of fatty fish with high dioxin- and PCB levels (more than once per month). Many of the girls between the ages of 4 -12, participating in the survey Riksmaten – barn 2003, had levels over EU's TDI, especially among the youngest. The somewhat higher intake among girls than among the adult women was not associated with a higher consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish among the girls. It depended rather on a higher food consumption in relation to body weight among children. The higher intake among children may, to some extent, be compensated for by the children's rapid growth rate which dilutes the levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in the body during childhood. This likely reduces the contribution of the early childhood exposure to the body burden of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs during pregnancy many years later.

Most of the men and older women in Sweden have long-term exposure levels which lie under or in the lower range of the TDI interval (2-10 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day) which is considered to be a negligible cancer risk. Men and women with high consumption of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea and the Gulf of Bothnia (up to several times per week) over a long time period can reach intake levels which lie in the higher portion of this TDI interval. At extremely high

consumption levels (daily or more often) over a long time period, it is likely that the intake level reaches over the highest intake in the TDI interval (10 pg TEQ/kg/day). The intake levels which children in Sweden have are so low that they most likely are insignificant for potential cancer risks later in life.

Exposure scenarios and conclusions

Results from the food consumption surveys Riksmaten 1997-98 and Riksmaten – barn 2003 have been used to create different intake scenarios for consumption of fish in general and for contaminated fish in particular. These scenarios were created as a guideline for formulation of consumption advisories from a toxicological point of view.

Fatty fish with a low contamination of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in the scenarios are represented by farmed salmon (average level 2 pg TEQ/g fresh weight), while Baltic Sea herring represents fatty fish with high dioxin and PCBs levels (10 pg TEQ/g). Lean fish are represented in the scenarios by cod and flat fish (0.5 pg TEQ/g).

Women in childbearing years

Avoid herring and eat farmed salmon instead: Women between the ages of 17 and 40 have the same fish consumption as in the food consumption survey, but consumption of fatty contaminated fish is substituted with fatty fish with low contamination level (for example farmed salmon). This does not result in a great change of intake of dioxins and dioxin like PCBs. This is due to the fact that women of these ages in general eat very small amounts of contaminated fish. About 2% exceed EU's TDI (2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day).

Baltic herring once a month: Women in Riksmaten increase their long-term consumption of contaminated fatty fish to once a month, by substituting consumption of fatty fish in general. The median intake increases from 0.9 pg/kg body weight/day to 1.6 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. In this case, 17% of the women would exceed EU's TDI.

Fish 3 times per week: In this scenario the assumption was made that the women follow the general fish consumption advisories, which is three times a week whereof one meal of fatty fish. If this consumption substitutes consumption of fish, meat and chicken, and women consume farmed fatty fish with low contamination levels once a week, then the median intake would be 1.4 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. In this scenario about 4% of women exceed EU's TDI. However, if women exchanged one portion of lean fish for one more portion of farmed salmon per week, the long-term intake increases and 30% of women are

predicted to exceed TDI. If only farmed salmon is consumed three times per week then over 70% of women would exceed TDI.

Fish three times a week including one meal of Baltic herring per month: It was assumed that the women consumed lean fish twice a week and fatty fish once a week, including farmed salmon three times a month and Baltic herring once a month (NFA's current consumption advisory for herring). The resulting median intake is 1.9 pg TEQ/kg/day and 35% of women exceed EU's TDI. A consumption of herring from the Baltic Sea, with a relatively low contamination level (4 pg TEQ/g/fresh weight), once a month, and farmed salmon three times a month results in a median intake of 1.4 pg TEQ/kg/day. Only 7% exceed TDI in this scenario. If herring with a high contamination level (18 pg TEQ/g fresh weight) is consumed once per month, then the median intake would reach 2.4 pg/kg/day and 80% of the women would exceed EU's TDI.

Fish three times a week whereof one meal is Baltic herring: If the women eat Baltic herring once a week and otherwise follow the NFA advisories with regard to fish, then the median intake would reach 3.7 pg/TEQ/kg/day. All young women, in this scenario, have an intake which lies over EU's TDI.

Intake scenario calculations were not made for girls. Nevertheless, intake calculations from Riksmaten barn-2003 showed that most of the girls between the ages of 4 and 12 do not eat contaminated fatty fish at all. A large portion of this group would increase their intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs considerably if they followed the current advisory for fish contaminated with dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs of not more than once per month. Many would, in this case, exceed EU's TDI. The same would be true for women in childbearing age if they increased their consumption of contaminated fish to once per month. From a toxicological perspective it is consequently not desirable for these population groups to increase their consumption of contaminated fatty fish up to the current advisory of once per month.

If women in childbearing years instead only eat fatty fish with low contamination levels once a week and lean fish twice a week, in accordance with NFA's advisories, then only a small increase of the general exposure in relation to the current situation would occur. Few women would exceed EU's TDI. If, however, girls and young women would begin to eat farmed salmon several times per week, then their intake would increase to such levels that many would exceed TDI. Women with very frequent consumption of contaminated fish (several times per month or more) would however clearly decrease their long-term intake if they instead ate fatty fish with a low contamination level.

Currently, most young women in Sweden have long-term exposure levels which are below EU's TDI for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs. These exposure levels will,

most likely, not cause severe health problems among the children that the women give birth to in the future. The consumption surveys which were conducted among young women in Sweden show, however, that about 5% of the participating women had intake levels over the EU's TDI. From a toxicological perspective it is therefore vital that society continue efforts to reduce the general exposure levels to dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs. The most important direct source of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in food is probably contaminated animal feed in the animal production (including fish feed). It is positive that limits for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in animal feed have been established. It is important that the efforts toward a long-term reduction of contaminants in feed are continued.

Men and older women

Fish three times a week whereof one meal of Baltic herring: If men and older women in general would follow NFA's advisories for fish consumption, which is three meals of fish per week whereof one meal of fatty contaminated fish, then the median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs would increase from about 1 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day (Riksmaten 1997-98) for both women and men to 3.6 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day for women and to 2.7 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day for men. In this case men and women with high intake levels lie about four times higher than the median intake in the Riksmaten study.

The studies of intake and body burden of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs which have been done in Sweden show that most men and older women have long-term exposure levels which lie below or are in the lower portion of the TDI interval (2-10 of TEQ/kg body weight/day) which is considered to result in a low or negligible health risk. If all consumers in this group increase their consumption of fish to three times a week, whereof one meal of fatty contaminated fish, then the intake in general would increase significantly. The intake would however still lie in the lower portion of the TDI interval for negligible cancer risks (2-10 pg TEQ/kg body burden/day). Individuals who consume contaminated fish several times per week or more would dramatically lower their long-term exposure if they lowered their consumption of contaminated fish to once per week.

Boys

As in the case of girls, no scenario calculations for intakes of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs were done for boys. A large portion of this group would however dramatically increase their intake of the contaminants if they, during their childhood, followed the current advisories with regard to contaminated fish for girls and women in childbearing years of once per month. One portion of contaminated fish per month with a dioxin and dioxin-like PCB level of 10 pg TEQ/g fresh weight would give an average daily intake of about 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight for a boy who weighs 20 kg. This intake is about twice the median

intake for boys in Riksmaten – barn 2003. If boys followed the current advisories for boys, men and older women of once a week under a long time period, then they would further increase their intake.

The current long-term exposure levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among boys probably do not entail a serious health risk. Nevertheless, results from epidemiological studies of health effects among groups which had very high dioxin exposures during childhood indicate that children can be more sensitive to dioxins than adults. In addition, boys seem to be more sensitive than girls with regards to reproduction effects. Therefore boys should not be given the same advisories as men and older women, but should be given the same advice as girls and women in childbearing years.

General conclusions

The design of future consumption advisories does not only depend on the results of toxicological risk assessments. The health advantages of eating fish must also be taken into consideration in the final judgement. Exposure levels for PCBs and dioxins have decreased within the Swedish human population since the 1970's. Fatty fish from the Baltic Sea, the Gulf of Bothnia, Lake Vänern and Lake Vättern nevertheless still contain high levels of PCBs and dioxins. Moreover, levels of dioxins seem not to decrease anymore in, for example, herring from the east and west coasts of Sweden. Very high consumption of fatty contaminated fish during long time periods can give exposure levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs which lie in the vicinity of those levels which cause negative effects in animal experiments. It is therefore important that society continues its efforts to ensure a continual and long-term decrease of PCBs and dioxins in foods. The Swedish NFA should also continue to follow the development of the Swedish population's exposure from food, and carefully follow the scientific development with regard to persistent organic environmental pollutants in general and PCBs and dioxins in particular. Most consumers in Sweden have infrequent consumption of highly PCB- and dioxin-contaminated fish and among these consumers there are other foods which contribute most to the long-term exposure of PCBs and dioxins. The current state of knowledge suggests that a large proportion of the population who eat small amounts of contaminated fish have exposure levels of PCBs and dioxins which entail very low or negligible health risks.

Introduction

Many halogenated organic compounds have accumulated in the environment because they are lipid soluble and persistent. Examples of these environmental compounds are the industrial chemicals polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), chlorinated pesticides (e. g. DDT, hexachlorobenzene (HCB), chlordanes) and brominated flame retardants, such as polybrominated diphenyls (PBDE). These chemicals have been intentionally produced in order to be used in different ways in society. Other similar compounds such as dioxins (polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins, PCDDs; polychlorinated dibenzofurans, PCDFs) have not been intentionally produced; instead they come about as a result of certain chemical processes at high temperature, for example, during combustion. Many persistent halogenated organic pollutants have long been suspected to cause negative health effects on humans at high levels of exposure. Food is the main source of human exposure to these compounds. The production, use and release of the compounds have in many cases been strongly controlled since the 1970's. Levels of many of these substances, in Sweden and other countries, have also decreased in the environment and in food since the 1970's [1-3]. For other "new" chemicals which are still in use by industry and which are found in consumer products, the time trends can be different. Such is the case with some brominated flame retardants. The levels of polybrominated diphenylethers (PBDEs) in mother's milk increased considerably during the period 1972-1997 [4].

In order to protect the Swedish consumers from high intake levels of PCBs and dioxins in food, the Swedish National Food Administration (NFA) has issued consumption advisories concerning fish which can contain high levels of the pollutants. The main objective of the advisories is to protect consumers during their most sensitive periods of life, specifically during the foetal and newly-born stages. In order to reduce the accumulation of PCBs and dioxins among women that may become pregnant, a specific consumption advisory regarding PCB- and dioxin-contaminated fish for girls and women in child-bearing age has been issued by the Swedish NFA.

The most recent revision of the advisory for fish with high levels of PCB and dioxin was conducted in 1995 [5]. NFA has since that revision adjusted the advisories to identify which fish species and which geographical areas that are affected by the advisory. Several large exposure projects covering people from different Swedish populations have also been conducted. During 2005 NFA initiated a major revision of the food advisories. The Department of Research and Development at the NFA was directed to present a scientific report regarding

levels of persistent halogenated organic environmental pollutants in food, levels of human exposure, and the toxicology of different compound groups. In a final risk characterization, exposure in the Swedish population was to be compared with exposures at different risk levels for health effects. In this way it would be possible to determine if current exposure is at a safe level or if there are groups within the population which have higher risks for negative health effects due to high exposure.

EU has established maximum limits for PCDD/Fs in food in 2002 and for the sum of PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs at the end of 2006. In the Commission regulation setting maximum levels for dioxins in food it is stated that maximum limits are not effective enough to decrease human exposure to dioxins [6]. In order to be effective, the maximum limits must be set so low that a large proportion of all foods would have levels which lie over the maximum limits. Therefore the maximum limits are presently set at levels, which restrict human exposure to very high dioxin levels [6]. For a more general decline in dioxin exposure to occur, it is important to actively reduce the occurrence of dioxins in food through actions against the sources of the pollutants [6].

Sweden and Finland have negotiated a derogation regarding the maximum limits for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in fish, which means that fish caught in Swedish and Finnish waters with levels over the maximum limits may be sold on the domestic market. An important prerequisite for this derogation is that Sweden can show that, from a health-risk perspective, the fish consumption advice system provides satisfactory protection for the Swedish population.

Levels in food

NFA conducts surveys in order to study the levels of persistent organic pollutants, such as dioxins (PCDD/Fs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), chlorinated pesticides and brominated flame retardants, in foods on the Swedish market. Analyses of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in food samples are also conducted in the yearly control system which EU has since 2003 recommended member states to conduct. During 2002 EU initiated maximum limits for dioxins in food and from 4 November 2006 there are maximum limits for the sum of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs. Sweden has as a member country in EU, in addition to the control programs for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, also control programs where chlorinated pesticides and PCBs (mainly the non-dioxin-like PCBs) are analyzed in food. A national maximum limit exists for PCB 153 (most recently revised 1995).

The analytical methods used are well tested and include extractions with different organic solvents, different clean-up steps, and final quantification using gas chromatography coupled to a electron capture detector (GC/ECD) or a mass spectrometer (GC/MS or GC/HRMS). In order to ensure the quality of the analyses, the laboratories participate in proficiency tests and control samples are analyzed regularly. The laboratories are accredited and analyses of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs meet the requirements of the EU directive 2002/69/EC. For more information about these analytical methods see publications, for example, by Atuma, Jensen, Isaac or Danielsson [7-10].

In the following chapter, data from NFA studies and the official control on levels of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and *p,p'*-DDE in fish and shellfish, fish oils and other foods are presented.

Table 1a. Levels found in different fish species (fresh weight basis)*. The table shows number of analyzed pooled samples as well as median values and range (minimum-maximum values) for analytical results. Levels lower than the quantification limits (<LOQ) are, when summarized, set to half LOQ. Number of fish included in the pooled samples depend on the fish species but is usually between 5-100.

Fish species* and site of catchment	No. of pooled samples*	Lipid content (%)	PCDD/F-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB 153 (ng/g)	ΣPCB (ng/g)	p,p'-DDE (ng/g)
Farmed salmon	2	6.7 (2.1-11)	0.7 (0.6-0.7)	2.0 (1.5-2.5)	5.4 (3.5-7.4)	17 (12-21)	10 (7.4-13)
Salmon-wild	6	6.1 (4.7-8.0)	2.4 (1.5-4.0)	3.3 (2.3-5.0)	9.1 (5.8-15)	24 (16-37)	12 (8.1-18)
Lake Vänern	5	4.4 (3.6-10)	2.0 (0.8-3.1)	6.6 (3.7-9.4)	26 (19-43)	65 (42-100)	42 (28-69)
Lake Vättern	27	6.6 (2.5-12)	4.8 (2.3-7.8)	6.7 (4.2-9.6)	20 (10-39)	56 (31-95)	44 (26-72)
Mackerel	1-3	12 (7.2-16)	0.5	1.1	3.2 (1.3-4.7)	8.6 (3.9-13)	3.1 (1.3-4.6)
Turbot	6	0.8 (0.7-1.0)	0.8 (0.5-1.0)	0.8 (0.4-0.9)	2.3 (1.4-3.0)	6.4 (3.7-8.1)	4.8 (2.6-6.7)
Rainbow trout	2-5	4.8 (3.6-9.1)	0.2 (0.2-0.4)	0.7 (0.5-1.0)	2.0 (1.5-2.1)	6.0 (4.9-7.1)	4.3 (3.6-5.1)
Arctic char	4	2.2 (1.0-3.2)	1.4 (0.1-4.8)	3.6 (0.1-14)	12 (0.1-45)	28 (0.4-100)	25 (0.3-91)
Whitefish	6	1.2 (1.0-1.7)	1.1 (0.7-1.9)	1.0 (0.6-1.5)	4.2 (2.9-8.8)	11 (7.9-21)	6.2 (4.3-12)
Herring	2	7.3 (6.7-7.9)	1.0 (1.0-1.0)	1.2 (1.1-1.2)	3.7 (3.7-3.7)	10 (9.7-11)	5.9 (4.9-6.8)
West coast	2	20 (19-21)□	1.7 (1.3-2.1)	1.9 (1.4-2.3)	5.9 (4.1-7.6)	18 (13-23)	Not analyzed
Öresund	40-83	6.4 (1.9-16)	2.6 (0.9-23)	2.5 (0.7-14)	8.0 (1.3-54)	23 (4.0-150)	21 (1.5-110)
Baltic Sea	6	10 (6.6-12)	3.4 (2.8-3.8)	3.4 (3.0-3.7)	7.5 (6.9-8.4)	22 (20-24)	18 (15-20)
Sprat	1	0.6	0.2	0.3	0.7	1.8	1.3
Cod	2-10	21 (14-23)	0.9 (0.8-1.0)	4.1 (3.5-4.8)	23 (4.3-44)	64 (12-130)	23 (10-91)
Inland lakes	1-2	16 (8.8-23)	0.5	2.2	14 (8.4-20)	34 (20-48)	18 (3.6-33)
West Coast	6	18 (14-24)	0.7 (0.6-1.5)	3.6 (2.3-6.1)	15 (9.6-23)	33 (20-57)	14 (8.3-26)
Baltic Sea	1	21	NA	NA	13	30	21
Öresund	12	2.9 (1.3-4.4)	3.4 (0.6-4.8)	4.9 (2.7-12)	19 (11-72)	50 (28-170)	26 (13-150)
Brown trout							

Dioxins (17 congeners) and non-ortho PCBs were analyzed by Umeå University and the National Health Institute in Kuopio, Finland. The other compounds were analyzed by the Swedish National Food Administration. 10-12 dioxin-like PCBs were analyzed (77, 81, 105, 114, 118, 123, 126, 156, 157, 167, 169 and 189). ΣPCB included PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180.

* Sprat samples include fish filets with bones and skin. Herring samples include fish filets with skin. The other samples include fish filets without skin.

If not all compounds have been analyzed in a certain sample, then the range of the smallest to the largest number of analyses are shown for that fish species.

□ The fish included in the pooled samples were large, on average 190-200 g and 27.5-29.6 cm.

Fish and shellfish

Because consumption of fish can be an important source for human exposure to environmental pollutants, NFA has, during several years, surveyed levels of halogenated persistent environmental pollutants in fish from the Baltic Sea and other Swedish waters. Results from NFA's surveys and control program with regards to PCBs, PCDD/Fs and *p,p'*-DDE in fish, shellfish and roe of vendance are shown in table 1a and 1b, where levels of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ, PCB 153, Σ PCB (which is the sum of PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180) and *p,p'*-DDE in different species are shown. Levels are presented on a fresh-weight basis and are shown as a median value with a range from the lowest to the highest measured level for each species. The following species have been investigated: salmon (*Salmo salar*), mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), mussels (*Mytilus edulis*), turbot (*Psetta maxima*), rainbow trout (*Salmo gairdneri*), shrimp (*Pandalus borealis*), Arctic char (*Salvelinus alpinus*), whitefish (*Coregonus lavaretus*), vendace (*Coregonus albula*), herring (*Clupea harengus*), sprat (*Sprattus sprattus*), cod (*Gadus morhua*), eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) and brown trout (*Salmo trutta*).

Table 1b. Levels in roe of vendance and shellfish (fresh weight basis). The table shows the number of pooled samples which were analyzed as well as the median values and ranges (minimum-maximum value) for the analytical results. Levels that are lower than the quantification limits (<LOQ) are when summarized, set to half the LOQ.

Species	No. pooled samples [#]	Lipid content (%)	PCDD/F-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB 153 (ng/g)	Σ PCB (ng/g)	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE (ng/g)
Mussels	1	2.0	1.0	0.2	0.6	1.7	0.4
Shrimp	1	1.5	0.4	0.2	0.5	1.3	0.2
Roe of vendance	4-7	12 (9.7-13)	3.0 (1.9-6.1)	2.2 (1.3-5.9)	3.6 (3.2-16)	11 (9.9-42)	3.1 (2.7-21)

Dioxins (17 congeners) and non-ortho PCBs were analyzed by Umeå University and the National Health Institute in Kuopio, Finland. The other compounds were analyzed by the Swedish National Food Administration. 10-12 dioxin-like PCBs were analyzed (77, 81, 105, 114, 118, (123), 126, 156, 157, 167, 169 and 189). Σ PCB included PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180.

[#] If not all compounds have been analyzed in a certain sample, then the range of the smallest to the largest number of analyses are shown for that sample.

With regard to Tables 1a and 1b, the sampling of fish has not been completely random; there have been some directed selection. This means that fish species expected to have high levels of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and *p,p'*-DDE have been sampled more often and that more fish samples can have been collected in areas known to have high levels of contaminants than if the samples were chosen strictly by random. Therefore some maximum levels which are reported in table 1a and 1b mirror the levels in fish from contaminated areas. The tables show how many pooled samples which have been analyzed for each fish species. The

number of individuals in each pooled sample depended on the fish species but was usually between 5 and 100 fish. Fish in the pooled samples were caught between the years of 2000 and 2006.

Tables 1a and 1b show large differences between the highest and lowest measured levels of contaminants for many species. This can sometimes be explained by the fact that the samples are collected from different geographic areas. How contaminated the site of capture is, determines the levels of compounds in the fish [11-13]. Artic char is an example of this; it shows large differences in levels of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and p,p'-DDE (table 1a). For instance, levels of PCB 153 in the two pooled samples from in the northern part of Sweden (Lake Rebnisjaure, Norrbotten) were much lower (0.1-0.2 ng/g) than those of the pooled samples which were collected in Lake Vättern (24-45 ng/g) in southern Sweden. Samples of roe of vendace from Lake Vänern contained higher levels than the samples from the Bothnian Bay. With regard to brown trout, the samples from the southern part of Lake Vättern had the highest levels (72 ng/g) of PCB 153. Samples of brown trout from the Gulf of Bothnia, the Baltic Sea, Lake Vänern and the northern part of Lake Vättern had significantly lower levels of the same congener (11-25 ng/g). Herring samples also had large differences in levels, depending on the site of sampling. The highest levels of PCB 153 in herring were found in a sample collected close to the Baltic Sea island of Gotland. The highest levels of PCDD/F-TEQ and total-TEQ have, on the other hand, been found in samples taken from the Gulf of Bothnia. Results from Finland also show that levels of dioxins in herring were higher in pooled samples from the Gulf of Bothnia compared with pooled samples from the southern part of the Baltic Sea [14]. An article by Kiviranta from 2003 reports levels of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ, PCB 153 and Σ PCB in herring from the Gulf of Bothnia and the Bay of Finland [15] which are comparable with, or in some cases higher than, the levels shown in Table 1a. The lowest levels of PCBs and PCDD/Fs in herring were found in those caught on the west coast of Sweden (Table 1a).

The measured levels of persistent organic pollutants also depend on the size and age distribution of the fish species in the pooled samples [12, 13, 15, 16]. An example of this is the two pooled samples of herring in the age of 4 to 6 years caught close to Gotland that had an average level of 4.6 pg/g for PCDD/F-TEQ. In pooled samples of 7 to 9 year-old fish from the same area, the average level was 10 pg/g. Average concentrations for total TEQ of 8.2 pg/g were measured for the younger fish while the older fish had about 18 pg/g. Age determination of fish is a time-demanding and costly procedure which is not routinely done for all fish samples. It is therefore not possible to determine associations between age and concentrations for the samples that are shown in Table 1a.

In addition to studies on the variation in contamination levels due to site of capture, the size and age of fish, there are also studies which show that levels of environmental pollutants in fish are dependent upon the season when the samples were collected. Levels of PCBs and dioxins in some fish species caught during the autumn have been shown to be lower than levels for comparable fish caught during the spring. Variation in levels between years must also be taken into account [11] for most of the species in Tables 1a and 1b because the sampling usually was conducted during a limited time period during one particular year. When comparing levels in fish it is also important to consider which part of the fish that is analyzed. Since the persistent organic pollutants accumulate in the fatty tissue (for example in the subcutaneous fat), then the results differ on a fresh-weight basis from samples of fish filets with or without subcutaneous fat [17]. Fat content and levels of environmental pollutants can also depend upon which part of the fish that is analyzed [13, 18]. In Table 1a data are collected on fish filets without skin and subcutaneous fat in all fish species except for sprat and for herring.

The EU maximum limit (see Table 6) for dioxins in muscle meat (fish filets) from fish and fishery products, and products thereof, is 4 pg PCDD/F-TEQ/g. The maximum limit for the sum of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs is, from November 2006, 8 pg total TEQ/g fresh weight. For eel the maximum limits are 4 pg/g for PCDD/F-TEQ/g and 12 pg/g for total-TEQ. When comparing the measured levels of PCB-TEQ and PCDD/F-TEQ in Tables 1a and 1b with EU's maximum limits, it can be noted that the lean fish/shellfish species (mussels, turbot, shrimp, whitefish and cod) contain low levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs. Farmed salmon and rainbow trout also have lower levels as does mackerel, arctic char (fish caught in Lake Rebnisjaure) as well as herring and eel from the west coast of Sweden. High levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are, however, found in the fatty fish from the Baltic Sea and from Lakes Vänern and Vättern, for example, in salmon, herring, sprat, eel and brown trout (Table 1a). In several cases the levels are over the maximum limits. Levels of PCB 153 in all fish and shellfish samples in Tables 1a and 1b are below the Swedish maximum limit for PCB 153 of 100 ng/g. The maximum limit is, however, high and has not been revised since 1995.

The Swedish Museum of Natural History's time-trend studies [1] of herring show that the earlier reduction of dioxins in the Baltic Sea and on the west coast of Sweden has now subsided. During the period 1990-2004 no reduction in the levels is seen. The same study shows, however, that the concentrations of PCBs have gone down 4 to 10% per year during the period 1978/80-2004. The reduction of DDT levels is approximately on the same scale.

Fish oils

Fish oils which are used as food supplements can contain high levels of PCBs and PCDD/Fs [19-22]. In 2003, NFA therefore conducted studies where occurrence of dioxins and PCBs was investigated in 18 fish oils and fish liver oils which were present on the Swedish market in February the same year [23]. Results for levels of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ, PCB 153, Σ PCB och *p,p'*-DDE are shown in table 2.

Table 2. Levels in samples of fish oils bought in Sweden in February 2003. The table shows the number of samples analyzed as well as median and range values for the concentrations of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ, PCB 153, Σ PCB and *p,p'*-DDE on a fresh-weight basis. Levels lower than the quantification limit (<LOQ) are, when summarized, set to half of the LOQ.

	No. samples	PCDD/F-TEQ (pg/g fat)	PCB-TEQ (pg/g fat)	PCB 153 (ng/g fat)	Σ PCB (ng/g fat)	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE (ng/g fat)
Fish oils	18	0.5 (0.2-2.1)	0.3 (0.06-15)	0.4 (<0.05-10)	1.2 (0.2-34)	0.9 (<0.13-38)

Analyses were conducted by Umeå University and the Swedish National Food Administration. For dioxins 17 congeners have been analyzed and for dioxin-like PCBs 12 congeners have been analyzed. Σ PCB are the sum of PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180.

The results show that none of the investigated fish or fish liver oils contained levels of dioxins which with certainty exceeded EU's maximum limit of 2 pg/g fat for PCDD/F TEQ. In cod liver oil levels of 2.1 pg PCDD/F-TEQ/g fat were observed, but with consideration to the measurement uncertainty, this level is not with certainty over the EU maximum limit. For the dioxin-like PCBs there was no EU-determined maximum limit when the study was published. A comparison with maximum limits for dioxin TEQ was therefore made. A large range in PCB TEQ concentrations were observed and that several samples contained levels significantly higher than the dioxin TEQ maximum limit. Large differences in levels were found for *p,p'*-DDE and Σ PCB. An explanation for the high PCB concentrations can be that the cleaning methods which some producers have used have effectively removed dioxins from the fish oils but not PCBs. The maximum limits for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in fish oils is currently 10 pg/g fat, which means that one of the 18 analyzed fish oils would exceed that limit if the same levels were found today.

Other food stuffs

Control programs for chlorinated pesticides and non-dioxin-like PCBs

NFA, has since the beginning of 1970's, controlled organic chlorinated compounds, such as chlorinated pesticides and PCB (mainly non dioxin-like PCBs), in foods of animal origin. Since 1998 the yearly control programs are regulated by the EU in the EU-directive 96/23/EG. The aim of the control is to establish that the current maximum limits are not exceeded. The national control includes samples of beef, pork, lamb, farmed game, chicken, milk, eggs and farmed salmon. Table 3 shows data for milk and eggs.

Table 3. Results from the control of food of animal origin in the years of 2002-2005. The table shows the number of samples as well as the median and range for lipid content and levels of PCB 153, Σ PCB and p,p' -DDE. Levels are presented on a lipid-weight basis. Concentrations lower than the quantification limits (<LOQ) are, when summarized, set to half the LOQ.

	No. of samples	Lipid content (%)	PCB 153 (ng/g fat)	Σ PCB (ng/g fat)	p,p' -DDE (ng/g fat)
Milk*	85	4.1 (3.3-6.8)	0.5 (<0.2-7.4)	1.6 (0.7-22)	1.9 (<0.5-7.4)
Egg yolks*	100	30 (20-34)	0.4 (<0.2-9.7)	1.6 (0.7-40)	1.1 (<0.3-19)

Analyses were conducted by the Swedish National Food Administration. Σ PCB is the sum of PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180.

*Milk samples were collected from milk tanks on the farms. Each egg sample consisted of 12 egg yolks (from the same egg-packaging station).

The national maximum limit for PCB 153 in eggs is 100 ng/g lipid and for milk 20 ng/g lipid. For the sum of DDT (where p,p' -DDE is the largest component) the maximum limit is 500 ng/g fat for eggs and for milk the maximum limit is 40 ng/g milk (fresh weight). The reported levels are significantly below these maximum limits, but the variation in the levels is large.

A compilation of the results from the control of organic chlorinated compounds in fat for bovines and swine show that levels of PCB 153 were reduced by 6.5%/year and 9.9%/year, respectively, during the years 1991-2004 [24]. During the same period levels of p,p' -DDE were reduced by 6.2% per year for bovines and 11.8% per year for swine.

Table 4. Concentration data for milk, chicken, lamb, beef, pork, venison, butter, eggs and vegetable fats 2003-2005. The table shows number of analyzed samples as well as median value and range (minimum – maximum values) for the lipid contents and concentrations of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ, PCB 153 and Σ PCB. Levels are presented on a lipid-weight basis. Levels lower than the quantification limits (<LOQ) are, when summarized, set to half the LOQ.

	No. of samples	Fat (%)	PCDD/F-TEQ (pg/g lipid)	PCB-TEQ (pg/g lipid)	PCB 153 (ng/g lipid)	Σ PCB (ng/g lipid)
Chicken (fat)	6	76 (69-83)	0.33 (0.26-0.55)	0.20 (0.13-0.49)	0.55 (0.39-1.2)	1.4 (1.0-3.1)
Lamb (fat)	4	71 (61-71)	0.73 (0.38-0.87)	0.72 (0.51-1.6)	2.2 (1.3-4.7)	4.1 (2.3-8.0)
Bovine (fat)	6	74 (46-84)	0.41 (0.18-0.71)	0.98 (0.20-2.1)	2.0 (0.52-4.0)	4.9 (1.3-11)
Bovine (liver)	7	3.5 (3.2-4.4)	2.0 (0.68-5.2)	1.4 (0.29-3.4)	4.4 (0.86-6.7)	11 (2.4-18)
Swine (fat)	6	81 (79-85)	0.10 (0.08-0.19)	0.07 (0.02-0.14)	0.51 (0.15-0.92)	1.4 (0.36-2.6)
Venison (fat)	2	78 (78-79)	0.75 (0.39-1.1)	1.4 (0.71-2.0)	2.2 (0.92-3.4)	6.3 (2.5-10)
Milk	12	4.1 (3.2-4.7)	0.31 (0.24-0.99)	0.32 (0.13-0.68)	0.53 (0.23-0.96)	2.0 (1.2-2.6)
Butter	12	82 (81-83)	0.26 (0.19-0.30)	0.31 (0.22-0.56)	0.44 (0.31-0.58)	1.2 (0.92-1.5)
Egg yolks						
-2003 organic	5	28 (27-30)	2.2 (0.32-3.1)	2.4 (0.13-2.7)	5.4 (0.29-6.1)	15 (0.94-16)
- 2003 conventional	3	29 (29-30)	0.27 (0.26-0.30)	0.18 (0.16-0.25)	0.43 (0.30-0.46)	1.3 (1.0-1.6)
- 2004 organic	18	29 (27-31)	0.99 (0.21-3.3)	1.0 (0.09-3.0)	2.4 (0.25-6.7)	5.6 (0.75-16)
- 2004 conventional	10	28 (24-30)	0.33 (0.27-0.71)	0.16 (0.12-0.18)	0.35 (0.22-0.47)	1.1 (0.69-1.3)
- 2005 organic	13	28 (26-29)	0.49 (0.25-1.3)	0.63 (0.16-1.2)	1.6 (0.39-2.3)	4.2 (1.1-5.8)
Vegetable fat	9	100 (70-100)	0.05 (0.03-0.06)	0.01 (0.01-0.07)	0.02 (0.01-0.29)	0.16 (0.03-1.0)

Analyses were conducted by Umeå University. For dioxins 17 congeners were analyzed and for dioxin-like PCBs 12 congeners have been analyzed. Σ PCB are the sum of PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180.

Dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs

NFA also conducts a control program according to EU commission's recommendations where levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCB in different sorts of food such as meat, fish, dairy products, eggs and vegetables are controlled. Table 4 shows results for the samples of chicken, lamb, beef, pork, venison, milk, butter, egg yolks and vegetable fat which were collected between the years 2003 and 2005. Levels usually lie far below EU's maximum limits for these foods (Commission's ordinance 466/2001/EC, most recently revised 199/2006/EG; see table 6). If levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in milk are expressed on a fresh-weight basis (PCDD/F-TEQ 0.013 pg/g and PCB-TEQ 0.013 pg/g) and are compared with levels in herring and salmon from the Baltic Sea (table 1a), then it can be noted that the levels in the fish are as much as 200-500 times higher. Large differences in concentrations can also be observed when herring and salmon are likewise compared with other kinds of foods in table 4.

Table 5. Concentration data for vegetables and fruits. The table shows number of samples analyzed as well as median values and the range (minimum-maximum values) for concentration of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ, PCB 153 and Σ PCB. Levels lower than the quantification limit (<LOQ) were, when summarized, set to half the LOQ.

	Nr. samples	PCDD/F-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB 153 (pg/g)	Σ PCB (pg/g)
Cereals	10	0.010 (0.008-0.023)	0.003 (0.002-0.006)	4.9 (3.6-8.3)	25 (18-59)
Root vegetables	4	0.012 (0.009-0.015)	0.001 (0.0007-0.0015)	1.9 (1.5-2.4)	12 (7.4-14)
Lettuce and spinach	4	0.013 (0.008-0.024)	0.004 (0.0009-0.007)	10 (4.6-15)	43 (19-60)
Cabbage and cauliflower	4	0.009 (0.009-0.009)	0.0006 (0.0005-0.0009)	1.5 (1.3-3.2)	8.8 (7.1-14)
Apples	5	0.009 (0.008-0.015)	0.003 (0.002-0.007)	5.1 (2.7-6.5)	23 (18-34)
Strawberries	2	0.009 (0.009-0.009)	0.0009 (0.0008-0.001)	1.7 (1.5-1.9)	10 (9.7-11)

Analyses were conducted by Umeå Universitet. For dioxins 17 congeners were analyzed and for dioxin-like PCBs 12 congeners were analyzed. Σ PCB are the sum of PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180.

In 2003 elevated levels of PCBs and PCDD/Fs in organically-produced eggs were observed and levels of dioxins where, in some cases, near the maximum limit for which regulations came into effect on 1 January 2005 for organically-produced eggs (Table 4). Levels in the feed were however never found to be over the maximum limits set for animal feeds. Since the sampling in 2003, fish-meal content in feeds for organic production have been reduced and the fish meal currently in use has lower levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs than before. These precautions have resulted in reduced levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in organically-produced eggs. For example, the median value for PCDD/F-TEQ

has gone down from 2.2 pg/g fat in the year 2003 to 0.49 pg PCDD/F-TEQ/g fat in 2005 (Table 4). This shows that levels of PCB and PCDD/F in animal feed are important in determining the levels that later are found in the food-producing animals. It is important that the maximum limits for levels of PCB and PCDD/F in animal feeds are low. Today these maximum limits are high; a reduction of them could result in lower levels of environmental contaminants in food.

Table 6. The highest allowable levels of dioxins and furans (PCDD/F-TEQ) as well as for the sum of dioxins, furans and dioxin-like PCBs (total-TEQ). * Maximum limits are applicable on a lipid-weight basis with the exception of fish and fishery products for which maximum limits are set on a fresh-weight basis.

Food	PCDD/F-TEQ (pg/g lipid)	Total-TEQ (pg/g lipid)
Meat and meat products		
– from ruminants (cows and sheep)	3.0	4.5
– from poultry	2.0	4.0
– from swine	1.0	1.5
Liver and liver-based products from terrestrial animals	6.0	12.0
Fish and fishery products [#]		
– muscle meats from fish and fishery products as well as products of these except eel	4.0	8.0
– muscle meat of eel and eel products	4.0	12.0
Milk and milk products, including butter fat	3.0	6.0
Hens eggs and egg products	3.0	6.0
Oils and fats	3.0	4.5
Animal fats		
– from ruminants	2.0	4.0
– from poultry and farmed game	1.0	1.5
– from swine	2.0	3.0
– mixed animal fats	0.75	1.5
Vegetable oils and fats		
– Oil from sea foods (fish oil, fish liver oil and oil from other marine organisms intended for food).	2.0	10.0

*According to the Commission's directive 466/2001/EG recently changed 199/2006/EG.

Through a derogation from the maximum limits, fish caught in Swedish waters with levels over the limit may be sold in Sweden and Finland.

A number of fish samples have also been analyzed within the control of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs and results for those samples are shown with other fish and shellfish samples in Tables 1a and 1b. Within the control of dioxin and dioxin-like PCBs, a number of vegetable-based foods have been analyzed (see Table 5). There are no maximum limits established for samples of this type. Concentrations are very low and in many cases on the level of the chemical blank samples which were analyzed together with the samples.

Market Basket Study 2005

The NFA conducted in year 2005 a market basket, in order to investigate the *per capita* intake of halogenated persistent organic environmental pollutants (for example PCDD/F and PCB). Results from the study are presented in Table 7. In the study samples were taken from all food products for which a *per capita* consumption of at least 0.5 kg and year have been reported. The food was bought in two food stores in four cities (Uppsala, Sundsvall, Gothenburg and Malmö). When possible, locally produced food was bought. Pooled samples of different food groups were prepared by taking a sample representing the weight of *per capita* consumption of the food in question. Homogenates of fish, meat and dairy products, as well as eggs, and fat/oil, were analyzed for persistent organic environmental pollutants. Table 7 shows the mean values for the different analyzes of the homogenate groups.

Table 7. Fresh weight levels for homogenates of different categories of foodstuffs. The table shows the mean value (N= 8, N=2 for fats /oils) for the lipid content and concentrations of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ, PCB 153, Σ PCB and *p,p'*-DDE in the samples. Levels lower than the quantification limits (<LOQ) were, when summarized, set to half the LOQ.

	Fat content (%)	PCDD/F-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB-TEQ (pg/g)	PCB 153 (ng/g)	Σ PCB (ng/g)	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE (ng/g)
FISH	8.4	0.215	0.326	1.20	3.58	2.21
MEAT	12.8	0.016	0.021	0.076	0.22	0.16
DAIRY	4.4	0.012	0.011	0.025	0.08	0.13
EGGS	8.4	0.023	0.010	0.032	0.10	0.06
FATS/OILS*	73.0	0.137	0.034	<0.11	0.25	0.35

Analyses were conducted by the National Health Institute in Kuopio, Finland Kuopio, Finland and by the Swedish National Food Administration. For dioxins 17 congeners were analyzed and for dioxin-like PCBs 12 congeners were analyzed. Σ PCB are the sum of PCB 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180.

*Purchases were made exclusively in two shops in Uppsala, Sweden.

More detailed data, for example analyzed levels of dioxins, PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE for the various foodstuff homogenates in each of the eight market baskets, are found in a report to the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency [25]. No clear regional differences in the levels of dioxins, PCBs or *p,p'*-DDE were discovered in the food baskets. Quantification levels (LOQ) for dioxins and PCBs in fats/oils were higher than for other foods. This probably led to an over-estimation of PCDD/F-TEQ, PCB-TEQ and Σ PCB levels when levels below LOQ were set to half the LOQ. Intake calculations obtained in the market basket study are presented in the following chapter "Exposure".

Different cooking methods of fish

Preparation and different cooking methods of fish can influence the levels of contaminants and thereby also consumers' exposure. Cleaned and flayed fish, and well as cooked, oven-baked, smoked, fried, poached, salted and deep-frozen fish, can have different levels of contaminants than newly caught fish.

Furthermore, PCBs are not evenly distributed in fish. Fatty tissues such as the fatty lateral line, subcutaneous fat (for example abdominal fat), gills, eyes and brain accumulate more of lipophilic substances, such as PCBs, than muscle tissue, whereas muscle tissue often accumulates compounds which bind to muscle proteins (for example methylmercury). Levels of Σ PCB have been shown to differ depending on from which part of the body the fish muscle have been sampled. Aune et al. have reported a 4.5-fold difference in PCB levels in salmon depending on if the muscle was from the anterior or posterior portion of the fish; the anterior portion had higher levels and higher fat content [13].

Reduction of organic halogenated contaminants, when the fish is cooked, is dependent to factors such as fish species, fat content, and the method of cooking. Several studies have been done, yet it is difficult to give exact numbers for the changes in levels caused by cooking. However, in general, contaminant levels are reduced when fatty fish such as salmon is cooked. There is evidence indicating that contaminant levels are reduced more at higher temperatures and longer cooking times, and this reduction is strongly correlated with the elimination of fat [26].

Most consumers clean (remove organs and head) and filet their fish before cooking, and this procedure results in lower exposures of the consumer to PCBs, PCDD/Fs and DDT compounds. Removal the skin and subcutaneous fat also reduces the levels of these compounds [17, 27]. Smoking of fish also result in a significant reduction of chlorinated pesticides (DDT, DDE, DDD, chlordane, hexachlorobenzene (HCB), dieldrine, toxaphene), PCBs and dioxins. However,

smoking instead leads to higher levels of PAHs, especially in fish with high fat contents [27].

With regard to dioxins, several of the chlorinated pesticides, as well as for PCBs, there is a reduction in levels of contaminants in fish at an increased inner temperature from 60° C to 80° C, an increased surface area when cooked (for example sliced filets), and when the fish is cooked at higher temperatures.

Examples of how great the reduction can be are given here for PCBs [30]:

- Removal of the lateral line and abdominal fat resulted in 19-45% reduction
- Cooking resulted in 20-40% reduction
- Increased surface area (sliced filets) resulted in a 5-10% reduction
- Smoking resulted in >40% reduction
- Canning resulted in a 30% reduction

A study by Bayen et al. [26] showed that cooking of salmon reduced levels of several persistent halogenated organic environmental pollutants. The reduction at cooking was linear and positively correlated with the loss of lipids. The results showed no difference in the reduction of contaminants among the different methods of cooking. However, the study showed a greater reduction of lipids in more fatty tissues (in the anterior portion of the fish), which may show that there is a greater reduction of contaminants in more fatty tissues during cooking. The results from this study are shown in Table 8 [26].

Table 8. Reduction (on a fresh-weight basis) of PCB, DDT and PBDE (in %) in filet of Atlantic salmon using different cooking methods (from [26]).

	Frying pan		Microwave oven		Cooking		Oven baking	
	With skin	Without skin	With skin	Without skin	With skin	Without skin	With skin	Without skin
PCB	36±11	44±11	23±14	30±12	28±16	38±16	28±13	36±13
DDT	31±16	41±14	21±15	29±12	25±5	37±6	19±21	28±19
PBDE	42±15	48±14	25±24	31±22	32±11	40±11	44±20	51±27

The conclusions which can be drawn from these studies are that the levels of PCB and DDT, and most likely levels of PCDD/Fs, decrease by 20-60% when fatty fish are cooked, depending on method of cooking, type of contaminant and fish species. Higher temperatures and longer cooking time seem to reduce the levels of contaminants more since these factors lead to removal of larger amounts of the fat from the fish.

Conclusions – levels in foodstuffs

Based upon the data presented for PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE in food it can be concluded that lean fish and shellfish species (mussels, turbot, shrimp, whitefish and cod) contain relatively low levels of contaminants. The same goes for farmed salmon and rainbow trout, mackerel, arctic char, roe of vendace from the Bothnian Bay, and for herring and eel from the west coast of Sweden. However, higher levels are found in roe of vendace from Lake Vänern and in fatty fish (salmon, herring, sprat, eel and brown trout) from the Baltic Sea and from Lakes Vänern and Vättern. In foodstuffs such as chicken, lamb, beef, pork, venison, butter, eggs and vegetable fats, the levels are generally far under EU's maximum limits. As expected, vegetables and fruits have very low levels of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and *p,p'*-DDE.

Exposure

Food consumption and intake of PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE

Food is an important source of exposure for many persistent halogenated organic compounds, for which production and use have been restricted or completely prohibited. This is also the case for contaminants which are not intentionally produced and for which great efforts have been made to reduce the unintentional production. Some PCBs and brominated flame retardants are still found in products [31, 32], or are still produced and used in society (flame retardants) [33, 34]. In the following chapter the state of knowledge on the PCDD/F, PCB and *p,p'*-DDE intake from foodstuffs in Sweden are described.

The intake calculations are based upon several food consumption surveys. Food habits of children were studied in Riksmaten-barn 2003, among randomly-selected four-year olds, and children in school grades two (8-9 years old) and five (11-12 years old) [35]. Food consumption was quantified with the help of a four-day food diary and a frequency questionnaire regarding fish consumption. In the questionnaire, fish consumption during the most recent year was documented. Food habits of the adult population were studied in Riksmaten 1997-98, where randomly selected individuals between the ages 18 and 74 years registered their food habits during a seven-day period with the help of a food consumption diary [36]. Consumption of fish was also investigated with the help of a frequency questionnaire where participants answered questions on fish consumption the most recent year [36]. A food consumption survey among pregnant primipara women from the Uppsala area have also been conducted, where women answered a questionnaire about their food habits during the year they became pregnant.

The results from the food consumption surveys reflect the more long-term food habits of the study participants. In the intake calculations, the long-term food habits are combined with levels of PCDD/Fs, PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE in the foods. The levels are representative of the average concentrations of contaminants in the various foodstuffs. The intake calculations can therefore be said to represent a long-term exposure for PCDD/Fs, PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE among the different population groups.

Market Basket Study 2005

The aim of the Market Basket Study 2005 was to estimate the *per capita* intake of selected persistent halogenated organic compounds from food and to compare levels and intakes with a previous Market basket study (conducted 1999). The advantages with this type of study are that it is possible to relatively quickly get an idea of the levels of exposure from food and get information about which foodstuff groups are important sources of exposure. The standardized manner in which the samples are collected makes it also possible to conduct time trend studies of exposure from food. This study investigated intake of dioxins (PCDD/Fs), PCBs, PBDEs, chlorinated pesticides, phenolic compounds, as well as methyl mercury from fish/fish products, meat/meat products, dairy products, eggs, fats/oils, cereals, vegetables and fruit. For more detailed information about the study, see the above chapter "Levels in food". For a well-documented report on the Market Basket Study 2005, see the report 215 0506/2006 to the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency [37].

The main contribution (49%) of the *per capita* intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs for the Swedish consumers came from fish. This was the case in the study from 1999 as well; where fish constituted 34% of the intake. Also Kiviranta et al. have shown that fish make the largest contribution to the intake of PCDD/Fs and PCBs in Finland. In the Swedish Market Basket Study 2005, meat contributed with 15%, dairy products 22% and fats/oils 13% of the total intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs. These results coincide well with those of the study from 1999. Fish are also the largest single source of intake of chlorinated pesticides (see table 9 and figure 2). Of the Σ DDT, 52% comes from fish, 26% from dairy products and 17% from meats.

The daily *per capita* intake of total-TEQ was calculated to 0.7 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day (mean body weight from Riksmaten: 73.7 kg). The estimated intake from 2005 indicates a lower intake than that which was calculated in the Market Basket Study 1999 (1.3 pg TEQ/kg body weight and day). It should be noted when making this comparison that some of the reduction in intakes between the studies in 1999 and 2005 could be a result of lower quantification limits in the latter study (rather than an actual reduction in concentrations).

Table 9. Calculated *per capita* intake of persistent halogenated organic pollutants from five individual food groups in the Market Basket Study 1999 and 2005 * (<LOQ= ½ LOQ); number of congeners analyzed are given in parenthesis.

Compound	Intake (TEQ-based intake in pg/day, other compounds in ng/day)											
	Fish		Meat		Dairy prod		Eggs		Fats/oils		Total	
	2005	1999	2005	1999	2005	1999	2005	1999	2005	1999	2005	1999
PCDD/DF TEQ	9.8	12.8	3.3	9.5	5.8	12.8	0.5	2.1	5.3	13.5	24.7	54.4
PCB TEQ	14.9	18.2	4.3	4.8	5.4	5.9	0.2	3.7	1.3	7.1	26.2	41.4
Total TEQ	24.8	31.0	7.6	14.3	11.2	18.7	0.7	5.9	6.6	20.6	50.9	95.8
ΣPCB (23)	236	349	60.8	74.8	49.0	83.6	3.3	33.5	13.7	58.9	362	615
PCB 153	55.0	79.4	15.4	22.2	12.1	23.1	0.7	9.8	2.0	4.1	85.3	139
ΣDDT (4)	151	256	48.2	82.8	74.9	75.2	2.1	18.4	16.2	71.9	292	523
p, p'-DDE	101	164	33.2	51.7	61.4	58.6	1.4	13.9	13.4	14.4	210	306

*The *per capita* consumption was calculated based on analytical data (<LOQ set to ½ LOQ). The amount of each substance in the sample was calculated by multiplying the concentration in the sample with the weight of the sample, which represents the yearly *per capita* consumption of the food group. The daily *per capita* intake was calculated by dividing the yearly intake by 365.

In general, lower levels of PCB, PCDD/F and DDT compounds in food were found in the Market Basket Study 2005 as compared with the Market Basket Study 1999. The levels of the contaminants together with the yearly *per capita* consumption of foods are the basis for the intake calculations in Market Basket studies. The uncertainties associated with consumption statistics and concentration data makes the per capita intake calculations uncertain. Producers and sales statistics regarding different food products probably give an overestimation of consumption which, in turn, adds to the uncertainty in the intake calculations. With regard to the analyzed levels the uncertainties increase when levels are below the limit of quantification (LOQ). In the Market Basket Study 1999 several substances in certain food groups were reported to be below LOQ. In the Market Basket Study 2005 the LOQ for certain analytes were lower, which meant that lower levels of some substances could be detected. Differences in consumption patterns from 1999 to 2005 most likely have less importance for the differences in per capita intake between 1999 and 2005. The consumption of food groups which give the largest contribution to the intake of these substances has, in fact, increased (fish, meat and dairy products).

Figure 1. Contribution of different food groups to intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in the Market Basket Study 2005. Fett=vegetable and animal fat; Fisk=fish and fish products; Kött=meat and meat products; Mejeri= dairy products; Ägg=eggs and egg products.

Figure 2. Contribution of different food groups to intake of Σ DDT in the Market Basket Study 2005. Fetter=vegetable and animal fat; Fisk=fish and fish products; Kött=meat and meat products; Mejeri= dairy products; Ägg=eggs and egg products.

Children; Riksmaten - barn 2003

The Swedish National Food Administration has recently conducted an intake estimation of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in children [38] based on the national food consumption survey among children, Riksmaten – barn 2003 [35]. The food consumption survey included 590 four-year old children, 889 children in second grade (8-9 years old) and 1016 children in fifth grade (11-12 years old). Intakes of

dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs were estimated with the help of a food diary and a food frequency questionnaire, an analytical data for foods, mainly of animal origin. The food stuffs were divided into the categories: dairy products (milk, yogurt, cultured milk, cheese and cream), meat/poultry (meat, ground meat products, sausage, liver paste, black pudding and chicken), eggs, fish (farmed salmon, Baltic Sea salmon, fresh-water fish, flatfish and other lean-marine fish, Baltic Sea herring, smoked Baltic Sea herring, herring/mackerel, tuna fish in cans, shellfish, fish sticks and fish balls), fats (butter, margarine and ice cream) and other fats (the fatty portion of, for example, pizza, quiche, pancakes, crepes and waffles).

The food frequency questionnaire included information on frequency of consumption of specific types of fish during the most recent year, which made it possible to estimate fish consumption in detail. The consumption frequency was recorded according to the following frequency categories: never, 1-4 times/year, 5-8 times/year, 9-12 times/year, 2-3 times/month, once a week, twice a week, or 3-6 times/week. Portion size was estimated with the help of a brochure with illustrations of foods and photos of portion sizes. According to the questionnaire, about 70% of children in all age groups consumed neither Baltic Sea salmon nor Baltic Sea herring/smoked herring during the most recent year. Fish sticks/fish balls and lean marine fish (for example cod, saithe, and haddock) were the most frequently consumed fish types. On average, the daily fish consumption was 9.6 g for four year olds, 11.9 g for 8-9 year olds, and 13.7 g for 11-12 year olds. Fish sticks were reported to be consumed by about 20% of the children once a week and 4.5% of children consumed fish sticks twice a week. Between 11-18% of children were reported to consumed lean-marine fish once a week. After fish sticks and lean-marine fish, farmed salmon was the most frequently consumed fish type, with an average daily consumption of between 1.6 and 2.8 g.

Table 10. Calculated intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCB (total TEQ) from all foodstuffs.

	pg/day		pg/kg body weight/day		pg/kg body weight/week	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
4 year olds						
Mean	46.4	48.2	2.6	2.6	18.2	18.5
SD	23.6	24.3	1.4	1.5	9.5	10.3
25 percentile	33.5	33.5	1.9	1.8	13.1	12.9
Median	41.4	43.6	2.3	2.4	15.9	16.6
75 percentile	52.5	55.1	2.9	3.0	20.5	21.2
95 percentile	91.2	89.1	4.8	4.8	33.5	33.6
Min	12.4	3.3	0.65	0.2	4.6	1.3
Max	255	228	12.8	15.2	89.3	106
N	286	298	260	262	260	262
8-9 year olds						
Mean	62.6	67.0	2.1	2.2	14.7	15.1
SD	49.0	38.6	1.7	1.3	12.0	9.2
25 percentile	39.8	44.0	1.3	1.4	8.8	9.8
Median	53.5	59.1	1.8	1.9	12.4	13.2
75 percentile	68.3	77.1	2.4	2.5	16.6	17.3
95 percentile	130	133	4.2	4.2	29.1	29.6
Min	13.2	19.3	0.5	0.6	3.5	4.5
Max	704	358	23.5	11.9	164	83.1
N	432	440	398	389	398	389
11-12 year olds						
Mean	56.0	64.7	1.4	1.6	9.7	11.0
SD	43.1	60.7	1.1	1.4	7.9	9.6
25 percentile	35.2	41.4	0.8	0.98	5.8	6.9
Median	47.1	54.6	1.2	1.3	8.0	9.4
75 percentile	63.8	71.8	1.6	1.8	11.1	12.7
95 percentile	120	117	3.0	2.9	21.0	20.3
Min	12.0	9.3	0.24	0.19	1.7	1.3
Max	660	856	16.9	22.4	118	157
N	486	506	465	484	465	484

Median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs (total TEQ) in 4 year olds was 2.3 pg/kg body weight/day for girls and 2.4 pg/kg body weight/day for boys. Girls in the ages of 8-9 years old and 11-12 years old had a median intake of 1.8 and 1.2 pg/kg body weight/day, respectively. The corresponding intake for 8-9 year old boys was 1.9 pg/kg body weight/day and for 11-12 year old boys 1.3 pg/kg body weight/day. In other words, there was no difference in intake between girls and boys in the different age groups. The highest total TEQ intake per kg body weight was observed among the 4 year olds, where the 95th percentile intake was at 4.8 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day (Table 10). The highest contribution of different food groups to the median intake dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among children came from fish/shellfish, 32-35% depending on age group, while contribution of meat/poultry and dairy products was 27-32% and 20-26% respectively (Figure 3). The lowest contribution to total exposure in all age groups came from eggs. Among the different types of fish, fatty Baltic Sea fish (salmon and herring)

contributed to 2.9-15% of the total median dioxin intake among children, whereas farmed salmon contributed 7.8-10% and lean marine fish contributed 3.5-4.6%.

The advisory for consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish (salmon and herring) of not more than once a month, issued by The Swedish NFA, is followed by most girls. 2.5% of 4 years old girls (7 of 283), 4.0% of girls in the ages of 8-9 years old (17 of 429), and 4.5% of 11-12 year-old girls (22 of 488) reported that they consumed Baltic Sea salmon more often than once a month (the answer category 2-3 times/month or more often). Consumption of Baltic Sea herring among girls of all age groups was, according to the survey, lower than consumption of Baltic Sea salmon; 2.0-2.8% of the girls were reported to consume Baltic Sea herring. In this group of high consumers of contaminated fish individuals with the highest intake of total TEQ were found. It is possible, however, that consumption of Baltic Sea salmon was overestimated for the population with frequent consumption. It is usually difficult to acquire this type of fish in food stores. In addition, many consumers most likely have difficulty in discerning among different types of salmon in the stores, which can cause some confusion between farmed and Baltic Sea salmon. If children are members of families that fish for Baltic Sea salmon, then it is possible to regularly consume Baltic Sea salmon.

In comparison with the most recent national intake calculations of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs for children which were conducted 2002 [39], with the help of consumer data from 1989 [40] and concentration data from the Market Basket Study 1998/1999, it seems that intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs has been reduced and the food groups which are considered to be the largest exposure sources have changed. The total TEQ intake among children (1-10 years) in the 2002 study was between 2.1 and 3.5 pg TEQ per kg body weight and day, and the dairy products gave the largest contribution to the total TEQ exposure (28-29%), followed by meat/poultry (22-25%) and fish (18-21%) (Figure 4).

Figure 3. The relative contribution of different food groups to the total TEQ exposure among children in different age groups in Riksmaten – barn 2003. The calculations are based on the median intake of total TEQ from respective food group [38]. 4-åringar=4 year old children; 8-9 åringar=8-9 year old children; fisk/skaldjur=fish and shellfish; mejeriprod=dairy products; ägg=eggs; kött/fågel=meat and poultry; matfett=fats and oils; övrigt fett=other fats.

Figure 4. The relative contribution of different food groups to the total TEQ exposure among children (1-14 years) in the 2002 studies [39]. 4-åringar=4 year old children; 8-9 åringar=8-9 year old children; fisk/skaldjur=fish and shellfish; mejeriprod=dairy products; ägg=eggs; kött/fågel=meat and poultry; matfett=fats and oils; övrigt fett=other fats.

Factors which may have contributed to this difference can be changed consumption habits, higher/lower concentrations of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in foodstuffs, different numbers of participants in the study, as well as lack of more detailed information on consumption frequency of different types of fish in the 1989 study. According to the food diary in the children's study 2003 [35] the consumption of dairy products has decreased since 1989 [40] as has the lipid contents of these products. No differences in fish consumption was observed between the years 1989 and 2003 among children between 1 and 14 years (about 20 g/day), while consumption of meat/poultry increased somewhat.

The total TEQ intake per person increases with age (Figure 5) among children, but when calculated per kg body weight it decreases (Figure 6). Median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs calculated per kg body weight for 4 year olds was twice as high as that for adults (17-75 years; [25]) while intake for 11-12 year olds was at the same level as the intake for adults.

Figure 5. Median intake of total TEQ (pg/day) in children and adults. Data are from two studies [38, 41]. Kvinnor=women; Män=men; Ålder=age; år=years.

Figure 6. Median intake of total TEQ (pg/kg body weight/day). Data are from two studies [38, 41]. Kvinnor=women; Män=men; Ålder=age; år=years.

Adults; Riksmaten 1997-98

The intake calculations for adults between the ages of 18-75 years, which was published in the Swedish National Food Administration's report 25, 2005 [41], are based on concentration data for dioxins (PCDD/PCDF) and for dioxin-like PCBs in different foods (fish, shellfish, meat, eggs, dairy products and fats) from different projects during the years 1999-2004. These concentration data were combined with the consumption data from the Riksmaten 1997-98 study [42], in order to get a measure of the intake of dioxins/furans as well as dioxin-like PCBs from food.

The median intake of dioxins and PCBs for participants in the Riksmaten study was 1.1 pg WHO TEQ/kg body weight and day. Fish and shellfish contributed 51%, dairy products 17%, and meat 12% of the total intake [41] (see Table 11). The contribution of fatty Baltic Sea fish to the total intake from fish was on average 42% for men and 44% for women between the ages of 41 and 74. Among women in childbearing years (17-40 years) the median intake was 0.93 pg WHO TEQ/kg body weight and day, where fish and shellfish contributed 45%, dairy products 20%, and meat 12% of the total intake [41] (see Table 12). Consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish among these women contributed on average to only 2 % (median) of the total intake from fish. 5% of women under the age of 41 years had an intake of 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day or higher (Table 12). About 70% of

these women, which had an intake over 2 pg TEQ/kg/day, consumed fatty Baltic Sea fish more than once per month, which is the Swedish National Food Administration's current dietary advisory for this type of fish. The women which followed the dietary advisory but who had an intake over 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight had in general a relatively high consumption of other fish and dairy products.

Table 11. Intake of PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs (total TEQ) as well as the contribution in percent to the total intake among the participants in the Riksmaten study (n=1185).

Intake of total TEQ (pg/day) for all consumers				
	Ave	Med	95th percentile	% of total intake
Fish *	54	35	157	51
Meat and Poultry	9.7	8.5	21	12
Dairy products	14	12	29	17
Vegetable fat	7.9	5.6	23	8.2
Other fats	8.0	7.0	19	10
Egg	0.02	0.5	2.8	0.7
Total intake				
pg/day	94	75	204	
pg/kg body weight/day	1.3	1.1	2.9	
<i>* whereof:</i>				
Fatty Baltic Sea fish	28	11	100	42
Other fatty fish	14	7.8	45	30
Other fish	7.5	6.1	17	24
Shellfish	4.8	1.0	15	3.9
<i>Fish, total</i>				<i>100</i>

Table 12. Intake of PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs (total TEQ) as well as the contribution (in percent) to the total intake among women between the ages 17 and 40 years (n=271).

Intake of total-TEQ (pg/d) among women 17-40 years				
	Ave	Med	95th percentile	% av total intake
Fish*	32	25	87	45
Meat and Poultry	8.0	6.7	19	12
Dairy products	12	11	25	20
Vegetable fat	6.5	5.0	17	9.1
Other fats	7.6	7.0	17	13
Eggs	0.6	0.5	2.4	0.9
Total intake				
pg/day	67	62	127	
pg/bw	1.0	0.93	2.0	
<i>*whereof:</i>				
Fat Baltic Sea fish	11	0.19	34	1.5
Other fat fish	9.4	5.6	33	44
Other fish	7.0	6.0	16	47
Shellfish	4.5	1.0	7.6	7.8
<i>Fish, total</i>				<i>100</i>

Ave= average.

Med = median.

bw = body weight

Pregnant women

During the period 1996-1999, NFA conducted a study on the exposure of PCDD/F, PCB and *p,p'*-DDE in pregnant and nursing women from Uppsala County. Primipara women between the ages of 18 and 41 years, who had participated as controls in a study of risk factors associated with early miscarriages [44], were recruited in late pregnancy. Among these participants, 249 answered a questionnaire about their food habits during the year they became pregnant [43] (Table 13). A comparison of consumption of meat and meat products, as well as fish and fish products, between the primipara women from Uppsala and the women between the ages of 25 and 34 years, who participated in Riksmaten 1997-98, revealed that the consumption (median and the 95th percentile) of the Uppsala women did not deviate from normal [43]. It is, however, difficult to recall which food habits one has. Therefore data from food consumption studies which are based on questionnaires has an element of uncertainty, especially concerning data on the individual level.

Table 13. Food habits (mean (SD)) during the year that the participating primipara women from Uppsala became pregnant (1995-1998).

Foodstuffs	Consumption (g/day)	N
Meat	100 (47)	249
Milk fat	26 (14)	249
Eggs	12 (9)	249
Fish total	24 (20)	249
Fatty Baltic Sea fish	1 (3)	249
Other fatty fish	5 (6)	249
Lean fish	18 (5)	249

With regard to consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish (wild-caught salmon/sea trout and herring from the Baltic Sea and the Gulf of Bothnia) more than half of the women reported that they never ate that type of fish during the year they became pregnant [43]. About 8% reported a consumption that was higher than once per month, which is the present consumption advisory set by the Swedish NFA.

In the Uppsala study, the median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs from food among the primipara women, expressed as total TEQ, was calculated to be 0.9 pg total TEQ/kg body weight/day [43] (Table 14). The intake varied between 0.3 to 5 pg/kg body weight/day. Five percent of women had an intake which was 2 pg/kg body weight/day or higher.

Milk fat and fish accounted for about 60% of total TEQ intake (30% each) [43], while meat on average contributed about 20%, vegetable fat 10% and eggs 5%. Over 50% of the women had no intake from fatty Baltic Sea fish, since they reported that they never ate such fish. For the 5% of women that had high a consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish, this fish contributed over 65% of the total intake [43].

The intake of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE from foodstuffs was also calculated for primipara women from Uppsala (Table 14). The median intake of Σ PCB (23 congeners) was estimated to 5.5 ng/kg body weight/day (range 1.1-28) and for *p,p'*-DDE to 3.1 ng/kg/day (range 0.9-15.4). In these cases fish contributed more to the median intake than was the case for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs (60 % for Σ PCB and 45 % for *p,p'*-DDE) [43].

Table 14. Calculation of daily intake of PCBs, *p,p'*-DDE and total TEQ among Uppsala women the year they became pregnant with their first child.

	Median (range)	5:e/95:e percentile	N
∑PCB (23 congeners)			
Intake (ng/kg/day)	5.5 (1.1-28)	2.2/14	235
Milk fat (%)	15 (1-66)	4/42	249
Meat (%)	11 (0-44)	3/30	249
Veg. fat (%)	6 (0-45)	1/18	249
Eggs (%)	5 (0-46)	1/17	249
Fish total (%)	63 (0-93)	17/87	249
Fat Baltic Sea fish (%)	0 (0-85)	0/48	249
<i>p,p'</i>-DDE			
Intake (ng/kg/day)	3.1 (0.9-15.4)	1.5/6.9	235
Milk fat (%)	18 (2-70)	5/45	249
Meat (%)	11 (0-38)	3/26	249
Veg. fat (%)	10 (0-54)	3/26	249
Eggs (%)	6 (0-44)	2/19	249
Fish total (%)	45 (0-89)	9/77	249
Fat Baltic Sea fish (%)	0 (0-83)	0/45	249
Total TEQ			
Intake (ng/kg/day)	0.9 (0.3-5.1)	0.5/2.0	235
Milk fat (%)	32 (5-78)	11/58	249
Meat (%)	18 (0-65)	5/41	249
Veg. fat (%)	11 (0-44)	3/26	249
Eggs (%)	4 (0-33)	1/13	249
Fish total (%)	26 (0-76)	4/66	249
Fat Baltic Sea fish (%)	0 (0-70)	0/27	249

Consumers with a frequent consumption of fish

Researchers from the University Hospital in Lund, Sweden, have conducted extensive studies of PCDD/F, PCB, and *p,p'*-DDE exposure and health among commercial fishermen and their families. In a report to the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency the associations between consumption of contaminated Baltic Sea fish and body burdens among men were reported. Nine of the 26 men studied had a very high consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish (median: 8 meals per month; range 2-58).

It is difficult to estimate the men's total intake of dioxin-like compounds because the report does not give data on the consumption of other foodstuffs. The following is nevertheless an attempt to estimate the total TEQ intake based upon the intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among men that participated in Riksmaten 1997-98 [41]. Median intake among men between the ages of 17-75 years was in Riksmaten calculated to 83 pg TEQ/day, whereof 18 pg total TEQ/day came from fatty fish. Median intake of TEQ from fatty Baltic Sea fish among frequent consumers in the fisherman study was about 300 pg/day (8 meals per month; portion size 125 g; total TEQ levels of 10 pg/g fish). This example

would give, in total, an intake of 365 pg TEQ/day, if the intake from Baltic Sea fish among fishermen is added to the median intake from the Riksmaten (after exclusion of intake from fatty fish). A body weight of 70 kg results in an intake of about 5 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day, which is five times higher than the median intake for men in Riksmaten [41] (Fig. 8).

If the highest consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish, which was reported in the professional fishermen's study [45], is used (58 portions per month), then the intake contribution from this fish consumption to the total intake would be about 2400 pg TEQ/day. In total that would make an intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs of about 2500 pg TEQ/day or 36 pg/kg/day for a body weight of 70 kg, which is almost 40 times higher than the median intake in Riksmaten [41] (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Intake of PCDD/F and PCB TEQ among different consumer groups in Sweden. **A:** Women from Riksmaten 1997-98 in the age group ≤ 40 years (median +95th percentile) [41]. **B:** Women from Riksmaten in the age group > 40 years (median + 95th percentile) [41]. **C:** Women from commercial fishermen families living on the east coast of Sweden and born before 1930 [46]. Women's intake from fish was added to the median intake (minus that from fish) for women >40 years in Riksmaten. **D:** Women from commercial fishermen families living on the east coast of Sweden and born 1950 or later [46]. Women's intake from fish was added to the median intake (minus that from fish) for women ≤ 40 years in Riksmaten. **E:** Women with frequent consumption of fatty Lake Vättern fish [47]. Mean intake (+ extreme intake) from fatty Lake Vättern fish was added to the median intake (minus that of fatty fish) for women >40 years in Riksmaten. **F:** Men between the ages of 17 and 25 years from Riksmaten (median, 95th percentile) [48]. **G:** Commercial fishermen with frequent consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish (mean intake + extreme intake). The men's intake from fatty Baltic Sea fish was added to the median intake (minus intake from fatty fish) for men in Riksmaten.

A large food consumption survey among commercial fishermen from the east coast of Sweden reported that the men ate on average 208 g of herring and 119 g of Baltic Sea salmon each week [49], which is about twice as much as the consumption among reference persons of the same age from the same geographic area. A consumption of about 300 g fatty Baltic Sea fish per week would result in a daily intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs of about 430 pg TEQ, comparable to 6 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. If this is added to the median intake for Riksmaten men (minus fatty fish) then an intake of 490 pg TEQ/day or 7 pg/kg/day is estimated, which is seven times higher than the total median intake for men in Riksmaten (Fig. 8) [41].

The food consumption habits of the wives of professional fishermen from the Swedish east coast were studied among 100 randomly-selected women [46]. Older women reported that they ate more fatty Baltic Sea fish than did younger women. Women from families living on the east coast of Sweden ate, on average, twice as much of this type of fish than did the women in a reference group who were of the same age and from the same geographic region. The women from fishermen families who were born before 1930 reported that they ate fatty Baltic Sea fish five times per month and lean fish six times per month, on average, whereas women born between 1930-1949 ate these types of fish four and five times per month, respectively. Women born after 1949 ate these two types of fish two and three times per month, respectively [46]. Women in the oldest group that had a consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish five times per month had an intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCB of about 200 pg TEQ/day based upon the assumption that the portion size was 125 g and the total TEQ level in the fish was 10 pg/g fresh weight. The lean fish contributed with an intake of 13 pg TEQ/day (125 g/day, 0.5 pg TEQ/g). If this intake is added to the median intake of dioxins for women between the ages of 41 and 75 years in Riksmaten (35 pg/day excluding intake from fish) [41], then the total intake is 248 pg TEQ/day, or 4 pg TEQ/kg/day based upon a body weight of 60 kg (Fig. 8). This is about four times higher than the median intake for women between 41 and 75 years of age in Riksmaten [41]. For the youngest women in the commercial fishermen families who were born after 1949, the average consumption of fish reported results in a total intake of TEQ which is 2 pg/kg/day if the intake from fish is added to the average intake from foods other than fish.

Lake Vättern is contaminated with PCBs and dioxins [47]. A study of the levels of environmental contaminants in blood of female consumers of Lake Vättern fish (N=37, ages 37-87 years) estimated the median consumption of fatty Lake Vättern fish (Arctic char, trout and salmon) to 3 times per month (range 0-12). If the average content of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in this type of fish is 8 pg TEQ/g fresh weight [47] and if the consumption rate is three times per month, then the intake is estimated to be 100 pg TEQ/day (portion size 125 g). This intake, together with the median intake of total TEQ for women between the ages of 41

and 75 years from Riksmaten (49 pg/day, intake from fatty fish excluded), results in a total intake of 149 pg TEQ/day and 2.5 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day at a body weight of 60 kg (Fig. 8) [41]. The extreme consumption of 12 portions of fatty Lake Vättern fish per month results in a total intake of 7.5 pg TEQ/kg/day, which is about 7 times higher than the median intake for the participating 41-75 year old women in Riksmaten.

Conclusions - food consumption and intake

Foods of animal origin are currently the most important source for consumer exposure to PCBs, *p,p'*-DDE and dioxins. The population-based food consumption surveys Riksmaten 1997-98 (adults) and Riksmaten – barn 2003 (children) show that fish/fish products, dairy products and meat/meat products contribute the most to the intakes of these compounds. Consumption of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea is generally low among children and young women. Among children 70% reported that they never ate this type of fish and among young women this type of fish contributed on average only 2% to the total intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs from fish. Among other adults, on average 40 % of the intake from fish came from fatty fish from the Baltic Sea. The median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs per kilo body weight was highest among the youngest children and decreased with increased age up to 12 years of age. This is because the younger children eat more food per kilo body weight than the older children. The oldest children had an intake on the same level as the adults. Calculations of intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs based on fish consumption data from frequent consumers of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea and Lake Vättern showed that frequent consumption of this type of fish (more than once per week) resulted in an intake which is 2.5 to 7 times higher than the median intake for adults in Riksmaten. In extreme cases, when this type of fish was consumed several times per day, the intake was 40 times higher.

Figure 9. Associations between levels of Σ PCB (10 congeners) and PCB 153 (ng/g fat) in serum from Swedish men and women 1995-96 [50, 51]. The line denotes the regression line for the linear association between levels of Σ PCB and PCB 153.

Body burdens of PCBs, *p,p'*-DDE, PCDD/Fs and PBDEs

These types of compounds are lipid soluble and persistent, and are eliminated slowly from the body. In general, the levels of halogenated compounds in lipids are considered to be about the same in different types of tissues and organs. The body burden of the compounds is often measured in lipids in blood serum or blood plasma, in fat biopsies or in lipids from mother's milk. Levels of the compounds in these different types of samples are often comparable. The levels in body lipids are, in many cases, a result of a long-term exposure before the sampling occasion since this type of compounds bioaccumulate in the body over many years. Analyses of PCBs, *p,p'*-DDE, PCDD/Fs and PBDEs are expensive and therefore an effort has been made to find marker substances which can give a representative estimate of the levels of an entire group of compounds. PCB 153 has proven to work quite well as a representative marker for total levels of PCBs in the body (Fig. 9).

Table 15. Blood concentrations of persistent halogenated organic compounds in children (newly-born – 10 years old).

Country	Germany	Germany	Canada, Inuits	Netherlands	Germany	USA	Germany		Germany
	Age	Age	Age	Age	Age	Age	Age		Age
Year	2002	-	1995-2001	1994	1996-98	1984-5/91-2	1994-95		2002/03 ⁹
Matrice	Serum	Serum	Plasma	Plasma	Serum	Serum	Whole blood		Whole blood
N	20	10/10 ¹	172	100/93 ¹	92	179 (4 yrs) 156 (11 yrs)	44/293 ¹	About 320	about 400
Statistics	Mean (range)	Mean (range)	Mean (range)	Median (range)	Median (5-95 percentile)	Mean ± SD	Mean (95 % conf. int.)	Median (range)	Median (min-max)
Unit	µg/l	µg/l	µg/kg fat	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l
<i>p,p'</i>-DDE	0.18 (0.07-0.54)	1.05 (0.76-3.49) 0.18 (0.07-0.54) ¹	256 (214-307)				0.33 (0.13-1.07) 0.22 (0.13-0.37) ¹		0.17 (0.01-12.1)
HCB		0.13 (0.04-0.52) 0.04 (0.02-0.21) ¹					0.23 (0.11-0.55) 0.16 (0.10-0.25) ¹		0.08 (0.01-0.28)
β-HCH							0.07 (0.03-0.31) 0.04 (0.02-0.07) ¹		0.02 (<0.02-0.62)
PCB 153		0.49 (0.05-0.98) 0.11 (0.05-0.25) ¹	76 (62-93)					0.17 (0.02-1.59)	0.09 (0.03-1.01)
ΣPCB		1.19 (0.16-2.25) 0.29 (0.12-0.63) ^{1,3}	259 (218-307) ⁸	0.75 (0.23-5.9) 0.21 (0.08-0.46) ^{1,5}	1.22 (0.23-3.35) ³ 0.36/0.68/1.77 ^{2,3}	2±3 (4 yrs) ⁴ 1±1 (11 yrs) ⁴	0.54 (0.20-1.63) 0.35 (0.18-0.67) ^{1,6}	0.38 (0.06-3.6) ³ 0.47 (0.10-4.5) ⁷	0.20 (0.04-2.5) ³ 0.23/0.15 ^{1,3}
PCDD/F TEQ									5.5 pg/g lipid ¹⁰
Ref	[54]	[55]	[53]	[56]	[57]	[58]	[59]	[60]	[52]

¹Nursed children/children who were not nursed

²Nursed for a maximum of 2 weeks/ nursed 2 weeks – 4 months/nursed more than 4 months.

³PCB 138+153+180.

⁴"total-PCB".

⁵PCB 118+138+153+180.

⁶PCB 101+118+138+153+170+180+183+187.

⁷PCB 118+138+153+170+180+183+187.

⁸PCB 28+52+99+101+105+118+128+138+153+156+170+180+183+187.

⁹The study was conducted 1996-2003. Only results from 2002/03 are shown.

¹⁰Mean level in 16 pooled samples from 2002-03.

Children

There are no studies which report body burdens of persistent halogenated organic compounds in Swedish children. However, several studies from other countries have been published. Table 16 and the text below give results from some studies from Europe and North America. It is difficult to compare the result in the different studies because of differences in study design, e.g. children's age, sampling year, and analytical methods. Certain studies have also lipid-adjusted blood levels of the compounds while other studies have not done so. Only one study of dioxin levels in blood from children has been found, and in that German study the median level of PCDD/F TEQ was 5.5 pg/g fat [52].

Some patterns in concentration variation between and within studies became visible. In a study of seven-month old Inuit children from northern Quebec (Canada), high levels of PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE were reported [53]. The concentrations were lipid adjusted and if lipid levels in plasma are assumed to be 0.7% and the density is 1 kg/l plasma, then the average levels of Σ PCB, PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE can be estimated to 1.8, 0.5 and 1.8 $\mu\text{g/l}$ respectively. These levels are clearly higher than the levels reported from other studies (Table 15). One reason for these relatively high levels among Inuit children is that fish and marine mammals, with high PCB and *p,p'*-DDE contents, make up a great deal of the diet of this population.

Several studies from Germany, Belgium, the Netherlands, Canada and the USA have shown that nursing affects the body burden of PCB among children during the period of infancy up to 17 years of age [52, 55-57, 59, 61-63] (Table 15). In an epidemiological study of an Inuit population in northern Quebec, the mean level of PCB in plasma lipids of 7 month-old children who were nursed for more than 3 months was 6.6 times higher than in children who were not nursed at all [53, 62]. Similar results have been reported by Patandin et al. (1997) [56], which showed that the median level of PCBs in plasma in 3.5 year-old children was 3.6 times higher in nursed children compared with children who were not nursed. In this study, nursing duration and PCB levels in mother's milk were important indicators for PCB levels in children in the nursed group. On the other hand, in the non-nursed group the PCB levels in children were significantly related to plasma levels in the mother during late pregnancy. In 7-10 year-old children in Germany a positive correlation was found between length of nursing period and levels of DDE, HCB, β -hexachlorocyclohexane (-HCH) and PCB in whole blood [59, 60]. A positive correlation between PCB levels in serum and the length of the nursing period have been shown in children up to 17 years of age [61]. The results indicate that differences in levels between nursed and non-nursed children are decreasing from 7 months to 10 years of age. This depends in part on the dilution of the mother's milk exposure which occurs due to the children's rapid growth. In

addition, some of the PCBs that have accumulated from mother's milk has already disappeared from the body during the childhood growth period through metabolic processes and excretion. Finally, the contribution of the dietary intake to the body burden is increasing after the nursing period.

Patandin et al. (1999) [64] proposed a model for calculating the cumulative intake of PCBs and dioxins from 0 to 25 years of age. The results from these calculations showed that nursing for six months during the infancy contributed with 12-14% to the cumulative intake of total TEQ during the first 25 years of life. Kreuzer et al. (1997) [65] have published a theoretical model which describes the lifetime body burden of dioxins (TCDD). Scenario simulations in this study show that the body burden of TCDD in children who have been nursed quickly reaches a peak during the infancy nursing period. Thereafter the levels decline to reach levels which correspond to those of seven-year olds in the group of children that were not nursed. In the group of non-nursed children the TCDD levels are reduced somewhat during the first year of life, only to slowly increase again and reach a maximum at 16 years of age. From 16 to 60 years of age the model scenario predicts that the body burden of TCDD is reduced slowly [65]. Taken together, experimental and modelled data indicate that the difference in body burden of PCBs and PCDD/Fs between nursed and non-nursed children decreases over the years. It is, however, not clear at what age the differences totally disappear. NFA's studies suggest that the exposure to PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE which a girl get during the nursing period can significantly contribute to her body burden when she becomes pregnant [66,67] (see the chapter "Pregnant and nursing women").

Other life-style and medical factors which have proven to be associated with levels of PCB, *p,p'*-DDE and other similar compounds in children are: sex, body composition, serum levels of triglycerides and cholesterol, as well as intake of animal fats. Boys have higher blood levels of HCB, PCBs and PCDD/Fs than girls [52, 61]. Levels (on a fresh-weight basis) also increase with increased concentrations of triglycerides and cholesterol in serum and with increasing intake of animal fat. Levels decrease with increased body weight, with increased BMI (body mass index) and with increased body fat content [52,59,61]. In a few studies time trends of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and *p,p'*-DDE in children have been investigated. Lackmann (2005) [54] studied the serum levels of *p,p'*-DDE in newborn children in Germany between 1984 and 2002. They found that the average levels were reduced significantly from 1.49 (1984-85) to 0.18 (2002) µg/l during this time period. Another study [52] showed that levels of DDE, HCB, PCBs and PCDDs in ten-year olds decreased by factors of 2-4 during the period 1996 to 2003.

Table 16. Levels of PCBs, chlorinated pesticides, dioxins and brominated flame retardants (median (range)) in the body of pregnant primipara women (weeks 32-34 of pregnancy) in Uppsala county 1996-1999 (serum levels) and in nursing primipara women in Uppsala county 1996-2004, Gothenburg 2001, Lund 2003 and Lycksele 2003-2004 (mother's milk levels). Units are ng/g fat if not otherwise noted.

Compound		Uppsala 1996-1999 Serum, late pregnancy	Uppsala 1996-2004 Mother's milk levels	Gothenburg 2001 Mother's milk levels	Lund 2003 Mother's milk levels	Lycksele 2003-04 Mother's milk levels
PCB 153	Level, N	59 (14-180), 323	55 (11-186), 305	48 (13-188), 37	43 (25-95), 36	31 (14-113), 39
ΣPCB	Level, N	151 (37-618) ¹ , 323	128 (30-402) ¹ , 305	129 (35-456) ² , 37	114 (68-271) ² , 36	83 (38-272) ² , 39
Mono-orto PCB TEQ	Level, N	-	3.2 (0.7-18) pg/g fat ³ , 305	3.5 (1.0-18) pg/g fat ⁴ , 37	3.1 (1.8-8.1) pg/g fat ⁴ , 36	2.4 (1.1-5.7) pg/g fat ⁴ , 39
non-orto PCB TEQ⁵	Level, N	-	4.4 (1-13) pg/g fat, 196	-	-	-
PCDD/F TEQ	Level, N	-	8.0 (3.6-23) pg/g fat, 159	-	-	-
Total-TEQ	Level, N	-	16 (6.4-40) pg/g fat, 158	-	-	-
HCB	Level, N	23 (12-160), 321	14 (4-31), 305	12 (6-26), 37	11 (7-20), 36	9 (4-18), 39
β-HCH	Level, N	9 (3-60), 321	11 (2.7-127), 305	10 (3-104), 37	8 (5-43), 36	5 (2-16), 39
p,p'-DDE	Level, N	88 (21-620), 321	97 (20-894), 305	72 (17-718), 37	64 (19-209), 36	46 (15-149), 39
BDE 47	Level, N	-	1.6 (0.35-16), 186	1.3 (0.55-8.9), 33	1.2 (0.33-9.3), 36	1.8 (0.66-73), 39
BDE 153	Level, N	-	0.59 (0.20-4.6), 186	0.53 (0.24-1.0), 33	0.61 (0.23-1.9), 36	0.62 (0.06-8.0), 39
ΣPBDE	Level, N	-	2.9 (0.91-28) ⁶ , 186	2.5 (1.4-12) ⁷ , 33	2.6 (0.92-13) ⁷ , 36	3.4 (1.3-107) ⁷ , 39
HBCD	Level, N	-	0.32 (0.14-4.4), 70	0.30 (0.15-2.4), 33	0.44 (0.11-5.9), 36	0.39 (0.09-10), 39
Reference		[43]	[67]	[72]	[72]	[72]

¹Sum of 10 congeners. ²Sum of 13 congeners. ³includes PCB 105, 118, 156 and 167 TEQ. ⁴includes PCB 105, 114, 118, 156, 157 and 167 TEQ.

⁵includes PCB 77, 126 and 169 TEQ. ⁶PBDE 47+100+99+153+154. ⁷PBDE 28+47+66+99+100+138+153+154.

Pregnant and nursing women

Since the 1980's NFA has collected mother's milk for analysis of persistent halogenated organic environmental contaminants. Mother's milk was collected from women in various locations in Sweden during 1981 to 1990 [68] as well as from primipara women in the cities of Uppsala and Sundsvall during 1994 [69]. At the most recent update of NFA's food consumption advisory for contaminated fatty fish in 1995 [70] certain shortcomings in the background material were discovered, especially those regarding actual body burden of PCB and PCDD/F in pregnant and nursing women in Sweden. Because of this, a comprehensive project was conducted during the period 1996 to 1999 where the exposures to persistent and halogenated organic compounds in pregnant and nursing women in the Uppsala area were studied [43,67] (Table 16). In total, 395 primipara women were asked to participate in the study, of which 323 donated a blood sample in the late stages of their pregnancy (week 32-34) [43]. After the birth of their child the mothers were contacted again with the request for a sample of mother's milk, of which 211 women obliged [67] (Table 16).

NFA has, with funding from The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency's environmental monitoring program, collected blood, hair and mother's milk from primipara women in Uppsala from the year 2000 to the present. The sampling has been conducted every other year (2000, 2002, and 2004) and in all, 94 women have donated mother's milk (Table 16). All mother's milk samples are collected by the women themselves during the third week after delivery. The median age of the women who donated blood in the late stages of pregnancy (1996-1999) was 28 years, and the median age for the women who donated mother's milk (1996-2004) was 29 years [43,67,71].

Regional differences in levels of PCBs, DDT compounds and PBDEs in mother's milk were investigated by NFA in cooperation with Occupational and Environmental Medicine at the Sahlgrenska University Hospital, the Department of Occupational and Environmental Medicine at the University Hospital in Lund and the Department of Public Health and Clinical Medicine at Umeå University. Mother's milk was collected from primipara women in Gothenburg (2001), Lund (2003) and Lycksele (2003-2004) (Table 16) [72]. The median ages of women who participated were 30, 29 and 27 years, respectively. The method of milk collection was identical to that of the Uppsala study, described above.

In the NFA studies, the substances with the highest recorded levels were *p,p'*-DDE and PCB 153 [72]. The variation in individual levels was remarkably high. The difference between the lowest and highest levels of *p,p'*-DDE and PCB 153 in serum is 30 and 13 times, respectively. In mother's milk the variation was even higher: 45 and 17 times for *p,p'*-DDE and PCB 153, respectively.

The correlations found between levels of most of the PCB compounds and chlorinated pesticides in serum from late pregnancy and mother's milk are strong (Figure 10) [71]. This indicates that levels of these substances in mother's milk as well as in serum give a good estimation of the women's body burden during and after pregnancy, as well as a good estimation of the child's exposure during the foetal and nursing periods.

Figure 10. Linear regression of associations between serum and mother's milk levels of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE. Each point corresponds to the level in one mother's milk sample and in one serum sample (taken in late pregnancy) from the same woman (N=202).

In addition to the studies which have been conducted at NFA, there are several other studies of persistent halogenated organic environmental pollutants in mother's milk from Swedish women. Sampling of mother's milk has been conducted in Stockholm since 1967. Pooled samples from this collection have been analysed and the results from 1967 to 1997 have been reported by Norén et al. (2000) [4]. These pooled samples contain milk from primipara women as well as multipara women, and the average age of these participating women increased during the study period. Results from the most recent sampling year (1997) are shown in Table 17. In yet another Swedish study, which was conducted during 2000-2001, 15 pregnant women were recruited. The women had chosen to give birth with a planned Caesarean section at Karolinska Hospital, Stockholm [73]. These women donated a blood sample at the time of the operation and a sample of mother's milk 2-77 days after the birth. The study included primipara and multipara participants. The average age of the women was 32 years. Table 17 shows the levels of PCBs and PBDEs in plasma and in mother's milk samples from the women.

A comparison between NFA's studies of pregnant and nursing women with results from the other Swedish studies described above (Tables 16 and 17) show that levels of PCBs which were measured in Uppsala [43] are comparable with

those measured in plasma samples from Stockholm in the years 2000-2001 [73]. Mother's milk levels in Uppsala 1996-2004 [67] were, in general, somewhat lower than those in Stockholm 1997 [4], while levels were similar to the levels measured in Stockholm during the years 2000-2001 [73].

Table 17. Levels of PCB, chlorinated pesticides, dioxins and brominated flame retardants in the body of pregnant and nursing women in the Stockholm area during 1997 and during 2000-2001. The units are ng/g fat if not otherwise noted.

		Stockholm 1997, N=1 ¹		Stockholm 2000-2001, N=15	
Compound		Mother's milk levels		Plasma levels	
PCB 153	Median	73	56	61	
	range	-	27-203	24-193	
ΣPCB	Median	324 ²	176 ³	190 ³	
	range	-	104-598	77-547	
non-ortho PCB TEQ⁴	Median	8.0 (pg/g milk fat)	-	-	
	range	-	-	-	
PCDD/F TEQ	Median	15 (pg/g milk fat)	-	-	
	range	-	-	-	
HCB	Median	12	-	-	
	range	-	-	-	
p,p'-DDE	Median	129	-	-	
	range	-	-	-	
BDE 47	Median	2.3	0.83	1.15	
	range	-	0.3-5.1	0.26-4.01	
BDE 153	Median	0.5	0.56	0.32	
	range	-	0.27-1.03	0.03-1.16	
ΣPBDE	Median	4.0 ⁵	2.07 ⁶	2.14 ⁶	
	range	-	0.71-8.39	0.56-7.72	
References		[4] [74]	[73]	[73]	

¹Pooled samples consisting of milk from 20 (PCDD/F) or 40 (other compounds) mothers.

²Sum of 13 congeners.

³Sum of 15 congeners.

⁴Includes PCB 77, 126 and 169 TEQ.

⁵PBDE 28+47+66+100+99+85+154+153.

⁶PBDE 17+28+47+66+100+99+85+154+153+183.

Factors which influence body burdens in pregnant and nursing women

Nursing is an important path of elimination for PCBs, DDT compounds and similar substances in women, and has therefore a significant influence of the body burden [68, 75]. Primipara women therefore generally have a higher body burden of environmental pollutants than do multipara women. For this reason a woman's first child is often exposed to higher levels of these compounds than are her subsequent children. In order to reduce this kind of variation in the dataset, and to make better between-year comparisons of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and p,p'-DDE-levels,

only primipara women have been recruited to NFA's studies since 1996. When comparisons are made with other studies it is important to consider if the participating women are primipara or multipara.

Possible relationships between body burdens of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and chlorinated pesticides (serum and mother's milk levels) in pregnant and nursing women and various lifestyle factors and food consumption habits have been studied within the framework for NFA's investigations [43, 67]. The factor which has been shown to influence the body burden most is the age of the women. Older women have a higher body burden of PCB, chlorinated pesticides and dioxins/furans as compared with younger women (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Mean levels (and standard deviations) of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE in mother's milk from primipara women in Uppsala 1996-2004 (N=295) divided into three different age groups.

Levels of PCB and chlorinated pesticides in serum and mother's milk increased with between 4 % and 13 % for each year of life [43, 71]. This age-related variation can, to some extent, be explained by the fact that older women have had a longer time period to accumulate contaminants in the body than the younger women. Another contributing factor to this age relationship may be that the older women in the study have been exposed to higher levels of the substances through, for example, food consumption than the younger women, since the levels in the environment were higher when the older women grew up. These reduced levels in the environment can also explain that the levels of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and chlorinated pesticides in serum and mother's milk in the primipara women have dropped during the study period (1996-2004) (Figure 12).

Levels of PCB, chlorinated pesticides and dioxins in mother's milk decreased by 3-11 % per year during 1996-2004 [43, 67]. The most rapid reduction occurred in levels of *p,p'*-DDE and β -HCH, whereas levels of some PCB compounds decreased more slowly. The earlier studies from Uppsala [68, 76] have shown that mother's milk levels of PCBs and certain chlorinated pesticides have dropped since the beginning of the 1980's, and studies of pooled samples from the Stockholm's region [4] show that levels have decreased since the 1970's. In the case where data from NFA's mother's milk study and data from the Stockholm

region are plotted together (Figure 13), the negative trend which can be observed for PCB 153 and total TEQ in Stockholm (1972-1997) continues in the Uppsala samples from 1996 to 2004.

Figure 12. Levels of PCB 153 and PCDD/F TEQ in mother's milk from Uppsala women (primipara) during the period 1996-2004. Each point represents the level in a milk sample from one women (raw data; PCB 153:N=305; PCDD/F TEQ:N=159). Regression lines are drawn with the help of multiple regression and are adjusted for important modifying factors (age of the woman, BMI before pregnancy, as well as relative weight change during and after pregnancy).

Figure 13. Levels of PCB 153 and total TEQ in mother's milk from women in the Stockholm and Uppsala regions from 1972 to 2004. One pooled sample, consisting of the milk from 20-431 women from Stockholm, has been analysed each year [4]. The yearly median levels in the samples from Uppsala are shown (in total 305 and 158 samples respectively for PCB 153 and total TEQ) [67].

Besides age and sampling year, several other factors, which to a lesser extent affect serum and mother's milk levels of PCBs, PCDD/Fs and *pp'*-DDE, were identified in NFA's study [43, 67]. One such factor is the weight/height relationship (body mass index, BMI) of the women before pregnancy as well as the change in weight during and after the pregnancy. Levels of certain PCB compounds and chlorinated pesticides in mother's milk as well as in serum were lower in women with high BMI and those with a high relative weight gain during pregnancy. Levels in mother's milk were also lower in women with a low relative weight reduction from the time of the delivery to the time of the mother's milk

sampling [43, 67]. The weight-related associations are most likely due to the fact that short-term and the more long-term weight changes which occur before sampling cause a dilution or a concentration of fat-soluble compounds in blood lipids and in other body fats.

In addition, the women who were not born in the Nordic countries had a significantly lower body burden of certain PCB compounds and higher body burden of β -HCH and *p,p'*-DDE as compared with women born in the Nordic countries [43, 67]. It is difficult to draw general conclusions about the causes to these findings since there were few women born outside the Nordic countries and they represent many different nationalities. Nevertheless, one important factor can be that these women grew up in countries with a lower degree of industrialization (lower use of PCBs) and a higher use of the above-mentioned pesticides.

A positive association was observed between the length of time women in the study themselves were nursed during infancy and levels of certain PCB compounds and chlorinated pesticides found in the serum and mother's milk samples [43, 67]. In other words, exposure during infancy was so high in these women that traces could still be found when they nursed their own first-born child. Of course it can not be excluded that there are other factors that covariate with the length of nursing period that can be of significance for levels of PCBs and chlorinated pesticides in mother's milk.

Even if the association is weak, there was a trend for women who had lived more than five years on the east coast of Sweden during their years of growth to have higher levels of certain PCB compounds in mother's milk compared with the other women [67]. In the food consumption questionnaire, these "east coast" women reported higher consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish during their teenage years than did the other women. This indicates that a higher consumption of Baltic Sea fish during upbringing can result in higher levels of PCBs in mother's milk. No associations between place of upbringing and levels of PCBs and chlorinated pesticides in blood serum in late pregnancy could be demonstrated [43]. In an earlier Swedish study of explanatory factors for plasma levels of PCB 153 among women who were or had been married to commercial fishermen, PCB 153 levels were higher in the women who reported that they grew up in a fishing village [77]. It was suggested that the women who grew up in fishing villages most likely ate more fish during their upbringing than other women.

In NFA's studies, women's food consumption habits were examined by a questionnaire where they answered questions about how often they ate different foods during the year of their pregnancy as well as during their teenage period (when they were 13-14 year of age) [43, 67]. It was mainly the women's consumption of fatty fish, especially from the Baltic Sea, during the year of pregnancy and during their teenage years which showed a positive association

with serum and mother's milk levels of certain PCB compounds and *p,p'*-DDE (Figure 14). These results suggest that fatty fish is an important source of exposure to PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE, and it emphasises the importance of keeping the exposure levels low during early years of life.

Figure 14. Levels of PCB 180 and *p,p'*-DDE in mother's milk from primipara women in Uppsala 1996-2004 (N=160-164) with different reported consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish during the year that they were 13-14 years old. Geometric means (and standard deviations) adjusted for important modifying factors. * $p < 0.05$.

The brominated flame retardants PBDE and hexabromocyclododecane (HBCD) which were studied in mother's milk were dissimilar in several ways as compared with other compounds [67]. Levels of PBDEs and HBCD are in general much lower than the levels of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE (Table 16). Positive associations between PBDE levels in mother's milk and the women's age could, for example, be established only for PBDE 153, and no associations were observed between PBDE levels and country of birth, place of upbringing, length of nursing period or food consumption habits. One reason for the differences in comparison with the chlorinated compounds can be that the exposure to brominated flame retardants, in contrast to PCBs, PCDD/Fs and *p,p'*-DDE, was low when women in our study grew up but have increased during their lifetime [4]. Another possible explanation may be that PBDE congeners are not as persistent as PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE. In addition, PBDEs are still used and is found in many consumer products which indicate that there can be other important sources of exposure than food. Levels of PBDE 47 and PBDE 99 among Uppsala women decreased during the study period (1996-2004), while levels of PBDE 153 increased. Studies of pooled samples from the Stockholm region have also shown that levels of lower brominated PBDE congeners (for example PBDE 47 and PBDE 99) have decreased since the middle of the 1990's, while levels of PBDE 153 have increased [78].

As mentioned above, the NFA investigation showed that PCBs, PCDD/Fs and

chlorinated pesticides in mother's milk have decreased during the period 1996-2004 [67, 71]. The results for the sampling during 1996-99 and 2002-2004 with regard to PCB 153, *p,p'*-DDE and total TEQ are shown in Table 18. As expected, a lower median level of the compounds was observed during the period 2002-2004 than during earlier time period.

Table 18. Levels of PCB 153, *p,p'*-DDE (ng/g fat) and total TEQ (pg/g fat) in mother's milk from primipara women in the county of Uppsala 1996-99 and 2002-2004.

Compound		1996-99	2002-2004
PCB 153	N	203	63
	Median (range)	62 (22-186)	40 (11-97)
	5th-95th percentile	27-117	21-65
<i>p,p'</i> -DDE	N	203	63
	Median (range)	108 (26-649)	61 (20-176)
	5th-95th percentile	41-312	24-146
Total TEQ	N	97	32
	Median (range)	18 (8-39)	13 (6-21)
	5th-95th percentile	9-33	6-19

Men and women

The body burden of halogenated environmental pollutants among Swedish men and women has been studied by measuring levels in blood lipids or body fat (Table 19). Comparisons between studies are difficult since different laboratories have analysed the samples. Comparisons of Σ PCB levels are also made difficult since different numbers of PCB congeners have been analysed. In addition, age of the study participants is of significance for levels of PCDD/Fs, PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE in fat, since average levels increase with increased age of the participant [51, 77] (Fig. 15).

Table 19. Levels of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE in blood lipids or in body fat among men and older women in Sweden (median (min-max)).

Year	Age (years)	N	Group	PCB 153 (ng/g fat)	ΣPCB (ng/g fat)	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE (ng/g fat)	Comments	Ref
Women								
1995	23-62	182	East-coast fishermen's wives	159 (16-780)				[79]
1996	54-75	205	Controls in cancer study	223 (60-607)		497 (32-2542)		[51]
1999?	30-60	20	Janitors	120 (44-363)				[80]
1999?	25-61	20	Administrators	170 (47-470)				[80]
1997-2000	41-75	41-45	Control mothers in cancer study		563 (141-1193)	324 (51-1431)		[81]
1997-2000	42-75	43-44	Case mothers in cancer study		792 (236-2114)	315 (109-3339)		[81]
2000	45-75	184	East-coast fishermen's wives	240 (98-620)		600 (110-2310)	(5-95 perc.)	[82]
2002-2004	37-57	544	East/west-coast fishermen's wives	84 (30-220)		140 (50-530)	(5-95 perc)	[83]
Men								
1991	23-62	18	Never eaten Baltic Sea fish	210 (22-400)		290 (27-1000)		[84]
1991	34-69	12	Average fish consumer	430 (180-1100)		960 (170-6500)		[84]
1991	23-49	9	East-coast fishermen	420 (150-1000)		1100 (330-4500)		[84]
1995?	50-60 ^b	27-29	East-coast fishermen	415-836	1696-306		3 pooled samples	[49]
1995?	53 ^a	29	West-coast fishermen	336	1336		1 pooled sample	[49]
1995?	50-60 ^b	29-32	Controls to professional fishermen	216-345	908-1337		4 pooled samples	[49]
1995	40-75	120	General public	295 (23-630)	700 (150-1550)	590 (25-4030)		[50]
1997-2000	19-47	61	Controls in cancer study		364 (110-1083)	98 (29-601)		[81]
2000	45-80	196	East-coast fishermen	370 (110-1010)		580 (110-2140)	(5-95 perc.)	[82]
2000	18-21	304	Military conscripts	65 (23-248)		88 (<DL-1270)		[85]
2001	33-72	18	Never eaten Baltic Sea fish	120 (38-200)		100 (25-330)		[84]
2001	44-79	12	Average fish consumer	330 (74-1000)		420 (41-2600)		[84]
2001	33-59	9	East-coast fishermen	250 (110-810)		580 (29-2300)		[84]
2001-2002	32-62	189	East/weast-coast fishermen	190 (62-640)		240 (80-890)	(5-95 perc.)	[83]
2002	?	33	Controls to occupationally exposed	85	267		Average value	[86]
2002	?	36	Sanitation workers	127	575		Average value	[86]
2004	18-21	200	Military conscripts	19 (<DL-118)		<DL (<DL-827)		[85]
Kvinnor/män								
1994-99	30-81	83	Controls cancer study		1020 (122-3041)	668 (51-3614)		[87]
1997-1998	46-80	39	Controls cancer study		545 (247-1649)	256 (43-1296)		[88]
1999?	25-60	19	Recycling of electronic devices	270 (69-800)				[80]

DL=detection limit.^aMean age.^b5:th-95:th percentile

Figure 15. Plot of age and serum levels of the PCB congener CB 153 (ng/g fat) and the metabolite of DDT *p,p'*-DDE in men from Uppsala [50] and women from counties along the east and south coasts of Sweden as well as from around Lake Vänern and Lake Vättern [51]. The line denotes the regression line for the linear association between levels and age of study participants.

CB 153 and p,p'-DDE

In most studies from the early 1990's the median levels of *p,p'*-DDE are about twice as high as those of PCB 153 (Table 19). One study of the body burden of PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE in men with varying consumption of fish indicates that the difference between levels of the two compounds increases with increased fish consumption [84]. Total levels of PCBs, in most cases, lie somewhat higher than the levels of *p,p'*-DDE (Table 19). Studies of both men and women in Sweden have shown that levels of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE in the body are significantly

correlated with each other [50, 51]. Strongest correlations are within the groups mono-*ortho* PCBs and di-*ortho* PCBs. The variation in individual levels of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE is substantial (Table 19). The lowest levels of PCB 153, which were measured during the 2000's, were more than 50 times lower among the young military conscripts than the highest levels measured in older men (about 1000 ng/g fat) (Table 19). The variation in levels in *p,p'*-DDE is even greater. The variation is due to factors such as age differences, weight-related traits (BMI, weight increase/reduction, mm), differences in food habits, nursing habits (women) as well as the year the samples were taken (see below). Older women and men have probably also been exposed directly by the use of products that contain PCBs and DDT.

As previously mentioned, levels of PCBs, *p,p'*-DDE and dioxins in mother's milk from mothers in the Stockholm/Uppsala regions have continually decreased since the beginning of the 1970's. No time-trend studies exist for men and older women. One study on military-conscripted men between the ages of 18-21 from southern Sweden does, however, show that the median levels of PCB 153 in the year 2004 was one third of the median level for the year 2000 [85] (Table 19). The reduction of *p,p'*-DDE was even more substantial [85]. This is most likely due to the fact that the men sampled in the year 2000 have been exposed to higher levels of the pollutants in their food during their upbringing than the men which were sampled in the year 2004. The indication that levels of PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE have decreased in food in general is strengthened by the fact that fishermen that were sampled twice with a ten-year interval (1991 and 2001) had a much lower body burden of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE on the latter sampling occasion [84] (Table 19).

Two studies have attempted to discern if there are regional differences in body burden of PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE in Sweden among women. There were no regional differences in levels of PCB 153 among the wives to professional fishermen from the Swedish southern and eastern coasts [77]. A study of older women who were participants as controls in a cancer study found an increase in body burden of PCB 153 in the following four Swedish regions:

Uppsala<Linköping<Umeå<Malmö [51]. Differences in mean levels between Uppsala and the Malmö areas were however not large (about 1.3 times higher in Malmö). No differences were found for *p,p'*-DDE between the regions [51]. In both studies researchers adjusted the results for possible differences in age among the participants and for other factors that could affect the results.

Commercial fishermen from the Swedish eastern coast seem to have a higher average body burden of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE than do professional fishermen from the western coast of Sweden. To some extent this may be due to the fact that eastern-coast fishermen eat more contaminated fish than do western-coast fishermen [49] (Table 19). That the contaminated fish are an important source of

exposure for PCB and *p,p'*-DDE is strengthened by the fact that men who reported that they never ate such fish had average blood lipid levels of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE which was less than half of that in men who reported eating fatty Baltic Sea fish once a month or more (Table 19) [84]. Sources of exposure other than fatty Baltic Sea fish are also important since men which reported that they did not eat fatty Baltic Sea Fish had average levels of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE of about 100 ng/g fat or higher on the 2001 sampling occasion [84]. Among the younger male military conscripts, consumption of dairy fat and fatty fish were significantly associated with serum levels of PCB 153 [85].

Studies of Swedish women have given mixed results with regard to the importance of fatty fish consumption for the body burden of PCBs. Older women who reported never eating fatty fish had a lower mean body burden of several of the PCB congeners, including PCB 153, than women who reported that they ate that type of fish once a week or more, after adjusting for important determining factors [51]. In studies of the wives of professional fishermen, no correlation between fish consumption and body burden of PCB 153 was found [77]. This may be explained by the fact that fish consumption increased significantly with increased age of these women. Possible relationships between fish consumption and body burden of PCB 153 may consequently have been masked when the data were adjusted for age [77].

Eastern-coast wives of fishermen who, as children and teenagers, grew up in fishing villages had on average higher levels of PCB 153 than did eastern-coast wives of fishermen who did not grow up in fishing villages. This was due to the fact that women who grew up in the fishing villages most likely ate more fish during their upbringing than the other women [77]. This suggests that food consumption habits during childhood can influence the life time body burden of PCBs.

Eastern-coast fishermen's wives who had nursed their children for a longer time period (in total >15 months) had on average a lower body burden of PCBs than women who nursed for a shorter period (in total <15 months) [77], which indicates that excretion of PCBs during nursing is of significance for PCB levels in the body many years later. Other factors that can affect body burden of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE are changes in weight before sampling and BMI at the time of sampling [51, 77]. Among older women the average level of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE decreased by 6-7 % per kilo body weight the women had gained during a 3-month period before blood sampling. These women reported that they had increased in weight during the previous 3 months which could cause a dilution effect of the levels in the body [51]. Among men who were sampled in 1991 as well as in 2001, a higher relative increase in BMI between the two sampling occasions resulted in a greater relative reduction in CB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE levels between the sampling occasions [84].

No Swedish study has in a statistically-robust manner attempted to compare levels of PCB and DDT compounds between men and women of the same age. One comparison of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE levels between professional fishermen and their wives show that the men have a higher body burden (Table 19). Older men (sampled in 1995) from Uppsala also had a somewhat higher median level than the older women from different regions in the country (sampled 1996). There was, however, a large overlap in individual levels between the men and women.

Table 20. Levels of dioxins and non-*ortho* PCB in blood lipids/body fat in the Swedish population^a.

Year	Age (years)	N	Group	PCDD/F TEQ (pg/g fat)	non- <i>ortho</i> PCB TEQ (pg/g fat)	Ref
Men						
1987	24-56	9	No Baltic Sea fish	20 (15-38)		[45]
1987	26-49	8	Average consumer	30 (22-54)		[45]
1987	19-47	9	High consumer	71 (20-97)		[45]
1987	19-56	26	All of the above	30 (15-97)		[45]
2002	39-71	9	No Baltic Sea fish	20 (6-58)	5 (4-9)	[45]
2002	41-64	8	Average consumer	22 (14-51)	9 (4-13)	[45]
2002	34-62	9	High consumer	65 (12-170)	17 (4-77)	[45]
2002	34-71	26	All of the above	25 (6-170)	9 (4-77)	[45]
Women/men						
1994-97	?	39	Controls cancer study	27 (11-47)		[89]

^aWHO TEQ [90]. Median (min-max).

Dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs

Knowledge about the levels of PCDD/DF and certain other dioxin-like PCBs (non-*ortho*) among men and older women in Sweden is meagre. Most likely this is due to the high costs of analyses. One study on older men with different consumption patterns of fatty Baltic Sea fish shows that men with high consumption clearly had a higher median level than men who never ate this type of fish (Table 20) [45]. The levels of dioxins and non-*ortho* PCBs have been measured among these men on two occasions at a 15 year interval (1987 and 2002). In contrast to PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE [84] the body burden of PCDD/F did not decrease during this time period, which indicates that PCDD/F exposure from food has not decreased during this 15 year period (Table 20). However, the body burden of dioxin-like non-*ortho* PCBs did decrease as did the other PCBs [45, 84]. Unfortunately, the few published Swedish studies have not reported the results in a manner that allows for easy estimation of the total body burden of PCDD/DF and dioxin-like PCBs. The results nevertheless suggest that there are individuals with levels over 100 pg TEQ/g fat (Table 20).

Brominated flame retardants.

A few Swedish studies have analysed PBDE in blood lipids in men and older women in Sweden (Table 21). The body burden of Σ PBDE is usually much lower than for Σ PCB [80,91,92]. Occupational exposure can result in higher levels of certain PBDE [80,92], up to the levels near those which can be found for PCB 153 among the general population [92]. In contrast to PCB, it seems that the PBDE levels do not increase with increased age [93]. Besides occupational exposure, high consumption of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea can be a source of exposure [93]. Exposure from dust in the living environment is also a probable source of exposure [94].

Table 21. Levels of brominated diphenylethers in blood lipids/body fat in the Swedish population (median (min-max)).

Year	Age (years)	N	Group	PBDE 47 (ng/g fat)	Σ PBDE (ng/g fat)	Comments	Ref
Women							
1997-1998	46-80	39	Controls cancer study		1.2 (0.4-6.3)	10 congener	[88]
1999	30-60	20	Janitors	1.6 (<0.5-17)	3.3 (1.8-24)	5 congener	[80]
1999	25-61	20	Administrators	1.5 (<0.5-4.9)	4.1 (2.4-10)	5 congener	[80]
Män							
1991	23-62	20	Never Baltic Sea fish	0.4 (<0.1-2.5)		(10-90 %)	[93]
1991	34-69	11	Average consumers	1.8 (0.19-4.5)		(10-90 %)	[93]
1991	23-63	12	High consumers	2.2 (1.0-5.7)		(10-90 %)	[93]
2000	?	17	Butchers	1.2 (<0.5-6.3)			[92]
Both sexes							
1994	47-83	5	Accidents	2.3 (1.7-4.0)	5.2 (3.8-7.7)	9 congener	
1994-99	30-81	83	Controls cancer study	0.70 (0.05-28)			[87]
1999	25-60	19	Occupational exposure	2.9 (<0.5-23)	26 (9-46)	5 congener	[80]
2001-2002	20-55	11	Mixed	1.8 (<0.1-14)	4.7 (0.8-43)	7 congener	[95]

Conclusions – body burdens

There is a substantial variation of body burdens of PCB, *p,p'*-DDE, dioxins and PBDE among the Swedish consumers. Factors which contribute to the variation of many of the compounds are age, amount of body fat, and country of birth. People with very high consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish often have higher levels of the compounds in the body than people with low consumption. Levels of PCB, *p,p'*-DDE, and dioxins show a decreasing trend among the consumers, which indicates that exposure from food is slowly decreasing. For PBDE this trend varies depending on which congener is in focus. Data for body burdens of the pollutants among Swedish children is completely lacking.

Hazard characterization

In the following chapter an effort is done to summarize the current knowledge about associations between human exposure to the halogenated compounds and health effects. The text focuses on studies dealing with exposure to PCDD/Fs, PCBs and DDT-compounds, and in some cases with brominated flame retardants. Several international risk assessments have in detail summarized animal studies in the field and the results of these risk assessments are summarized in the next chapter "Risk characterization".

A more detailed summary of the epidemiological studies of human populations with background body burdens of the environmental pollutants is given in Appendix 1. In certain cases the following text is based on evaluations of the epidemiological studies found in documents from international risk assessments and in review articles.

It is important to remember that a single epidemiological study never can conclude that a certain exposure did not cause disease. Small increases in risk caused by the exposure can be very difficult to detect in epidemiological studies. An observed statistically significant association between exposure and disease does however not necessarily mean that the exposure caused the disease. Currently unknown risk factors for the disease, that are associated with the studied exposure and the disease, may still exist (confounders). If a large number of high quality studies have found no statistically significant association between exposure and disease it is reasonable to conclude that the exposure is not a strong risk factor for the disease. When statistically significant associations have been found in many studies of good quality from different parts of the world, it is similarly reasonable to conclude that the associations are causal.

The following text mainly includes studies that have used methods of chemical analysis in PCB, PCDD/F and DDT exposure assessment. In the case of studies of Swedish fishermen families the exposure has sometimes been assessed from the consumption of fat-rich Baltic Sea fish among the participants.

Epidemiology – infants and children

Possible effects of halogenated environmental pollutants on children's health and development have been investigated in a large number of epidemiological studies. The most studied health endpoints are birth weight, body growth during childhood, neurological development during childhood, thyroid hormone levels, markers of immune-system function, infectious diseases, and allergies. Summarized below are the findings of the largest studies. In Appendix 1 the results of the studies of populations with background body burdens are summarized in more detail.

Seveso and Taiwan

The accidental exposures of populations in Seveso, Italy, and on Taiwan (Yucheng) give good information about possible health effects among children with very high pre-natal and post-natal exposures to PCDD/Fs (Seveso and Yucheng) and PCBs (Yucheng). On Taiwan, rice oil was contaminated with very high levels of PCBs and certain PCDD/Fs, resulting in exposure levels that were several hundred-fold higher than background exposure levels. Decreased birth weight, slower body growth during childhood, slower psycho-motor development during childhood, and lower than normal IQ were some of the health effects observed among children with high pre-natal exposure [96]. Some of the exposed children also had hyper-pigmentation of the skin, deformed nails, and swollen eyelids. Among the Yucheng children a higher incidence of bronchitis, upper respiratory infections, and inner ear infections were found [96]. Effects on tooth development were manifested among the Yucheng children as higher frequencies of neonatal teeth, missing teeth, and rooted teeth. Among boys of ages 11 to 14 years born during the first years after the accident a shorter penis length was observed compared to control children in the same age, with low exposure [96]. Some of the effects observed on Taiwan were also found among Japanese children with very high levels of pre-natal exposure to PCBs and PCDD/Fs in the Yusho accident 1968 [97]. In this case as well, the exposure occurred due to contamination of rice oil.

After the accident in Seveso, Italy, when a large amount of TCDD polluted a suburb of Milan after an explosion in a chemical factory, chloracne was most common among exposed children (88 % of the chloracne cases) [98]. In the most polluted area (Zone A) 20 % of the children had chloracne. Among 10 children with chloracne the TCDD concentrations in blood varied between 820 and 56 000 pg/g lipid [98]. Among adults with no chloracne concentrations varied between 1770 and 10 400 pg/g lipid [98]. This indicates that children are more sensitive than adults regarding induction of chloracne. In a follow-up study 20 years after the accident, the patients with chloracne did not have poorer general health than that found within a control population from the Seveso area with low exposure

[99]. In this study a strong association between blood plasma concentrations of TCDD and chloracne was found among individuals with fair hair color, indicating that genetic factors may modify the effects of TCDD [99].

In a study of TCDD effects on tooth development among Seveso victims exposed to TCDD during childhood, 48 individuals from the polluted Zones A and B, and the less polluted Zone R were recruited [100]. The study participants were randomly recruited from the part of the Seveso population that was less than 10 years of age at the time of the accident and that had donated blood samples shortly after the accident. Controls from non-polluted areas around Seveso were frequency matched according to age, sex and education level. The blood serum concentrations of TCDD among the exposed study participants ranged from 23 to 26 000 pg TCDD/g lipid. The prevalence of defected development of tooth enamel was 42 % among the study participants from Zones A, B and R, and 26 % among the controls. Defects were more common among children that were <5 years old at the time of the accident. Among study participants with TCDD concentrations above 237 pg/g lipid, a significantly-increased risk of enamel defects was observed. Lack of a single molar tooth was more common among the participants with the highest exposure. No difference in prevalence of tooth cavities was observed.

Sweden – children born in fishermen families

In a cohort of professional fishermen, wives and ex-wives of the fishermen were identified [46]. In total 1568 wives from the eastern coast and 4027 wives from the western coast who were born in the year 1923 or later were found. From the Swedish Birth Register 1501 children from the eastern coast and 3553 children from the western coast were identified. Of the mothers to these children, 38 from the eastern coast and 31 from the western coast and the same numbers of control women from the general population (matched by age and county of residence) were interviewed about their food habits. It was shown that the mothers from the eastern and western coasts fishermen families consumed locally-caught fish twice as often as the control mothers [101].

Statistical analysis showed that mothers from the eastern-coast fisherman families gave birth to more children with low birth weight (<3000 g) compared with mothers from the general population in the same area, whereas the reverse situation was found for mothers from western-coast fishermen families [102]. The children of the eastern-coast families had a significantly lower birth weight (median 3530 g) than children from the western-coast families (median 3610 g) [102]. The researchers concluded that these data supported an association between high consumption of contaminated fish from the Baltic Sea and an increased risk of giving birth to a child with low birth weight.

During 1995 blood was sampled from mothers from the eastern-coast fishermen families that had given birth to a child between the years 1973 to 1991 [101]. PCB 153 was analyzed in the blood. Cases of low birth weight (N=57, weight 1500-2750 g) were matched to controls (N=135, weight 3250-4500) according to sex of the child, parity and year of birth. With the help of two different models the blood plasma concentrations of PCB 153 were back-calculated to the year the women gave birth. An increased risk of giving birth to a child with low birth weight was observed at PCB 153 concentrations of 300 to 400 ng/g lipid, depending on the kinetic model used for back-calculating the concentrations [101].

The children of the eastern-coast fishermen's wives (N=174 children, whereof 55 with low birth weight and 119 with normal birth weight) and from the western-coast families (N=294, with 88 children having low birth weight and 206 with normal birth weight) were followed up at the ages of 4 and 7 years [103]. No differences in body height and weight were observed between the eastern-coast and western-coast children. Among the children with normal birth weight a significant negative association was found between the back-calculated blood PCB 153 concentrations during pregnancy of the mothers and the weights of the children at ages 4 and 7 years [103].

Studies of background exposure

Over 10 studies of associations between birth weight and/or body growth during childhood and background exposure to PCB, PCDD/F or *p,p'*-DDE have been published (Appendix 1). Studies from the Netherlands, USA (2 Michigan studies, 1 California study), Canada (Inuit population) and Finland have observed negative associations between pre-natal PCB/PCDD/F exposure and birth weight/length, whereas other studies from the USA (Great Lakes region, North Carolina, Oswego cohort, "11 cities", Wisconsin), Spain and Japan did not find statistically significant negative associations. A comparison of the body burdens of PCB 153 among the pregnant women in the studies shows that the body burdens overlap between studies showing significant negative associations with birth weight/length and studies not showing any associations (Appendix 1). The same picture is evident for the studies of *p,p'*-DDE exposure.

The interpretation of results regarding neurological effects is difficult since the infants or children have been tested at different ages and with different tests of psycho-motor development (Appendix 1). Several studies have, however, found statistically significant associations between pre-natal PCB exposure and psycho-motor development of the children. Some other studies did not find significant associations and the body burdens of PCB 153 in these studies sometimes overlap body burdens found in studies showing associations. This makes it difficult to draw conclusions about causal relationships between exposure and outcomes.

Similar problems with varying results are evident for studies of associations between pre-natal exposure to PCB, *p,p'*-DDE and PCDD/F and thyroid hormone levels in the blood of the infants or children (Appendix 1). In studies of levels of markers of immune function in blood from infants and children, significant associations with pre-natal exposure to PCB, *p,p'*-DDE and PCDD/F were found for single markers in most cases. It is, however, difficult to find similarities in patterns of associations between studies, since the infants and children were of different ages and different markers of immune functions were studied. In studies where significant associations were found, the variation in marker levels were within what is regarded as normal from a clinical point of view. It is therefore not possible to draw conclusions about the health consequences of the observed associations (Appendix 1).

Studies with focus on associations between pre-natal and post-natal exposure to PCB and *p,p'*-DDE and risk of infections, asthma and allergies are still too few to allow conclusions about causality between exposure and outcome (Appendix 1).

Negative effects on tooth development that have been described from the Yucheng and Seveso cohorts have also been reported in a study from Finland (Appendix 1). In Finland an increased risk of hypo-mineralization with increased PCDD/F exposure early in life was found. The concentrations in mothers' milk ranged between 4 to 99 pg/ TEQ/g lipid [104].

Reviews and assessments

Several attempts have been made to summarize and assess the results of the epidemiological findings regarding associations between pre- and post-natal PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE exposure and health effects among infants and children. In 1991 Swain [105] reviewed the epidemiological studies published to that date, with focus on studies of PCB exposure among populations living in the areas around the Great Lakes and in North Carolina, USA. Swain used a formalized scheme in the assessment of the studies, called the Susser criteria. Conclusions about causal associations between exposure and health outcomes were based on three criteria: strength of association, consistency upon replication, and statistical coherence in the form of linearity or monotonic dose-response relationships [105].

About studies of birth weight, Swain concluded that exposure data were incomplete in several studies and that the studies showed diverging results. It was therefore not possible to draw firm conclusions about causality of association between pre-natal PCB exposure and birth weight. Swain continued with the assessment of studies dealing with neo-natal health, mainly studies of psychomotor development based on results from mother/child cohorts from

Michigan and North Carolina, USA. The results showed linear or near linear associations between pre-natal exposure to PCBs and effects on neonatal psychomotor development. The results of the various studies were similar and Swain summarized that it could be concluded with enough certainty that the observed associations were causal [105]. The same conclusion was drawn about results regarding psychomotor development in early infancy. Associations between pre-natal PCB exposure and cognitive development and development of child activity, did not fulfil, according to Swain, the three Susser criteria. Therefore it was not possible to reject or confirm that the associations were causal [105].

Kimbrough and Krouskas [106] assessed the results of studies of associations between PCB and PCDD/F exposure and birth weight, and immune and thyroid function published up to the year 2001. The scientific quality of each separate study was assessed. The biological and clinical relevance of the findings were also assessed [106]. Regarding studies of birth weight, Kimbrough and Krouskas concluded that associations between exposure and outcome varied between studies. In studies of the immune system and thyroid hormones the differences in levels of immune system and thyroid biomarkers between groups with different PCB/PCDD/F exposure were within the range regarded as clinically normal. Kimbrough and Krouskas concluded that the variation in marker levels were too small to be biologically relevant [106].

Longnecker and Lynch [107] reviewed the literature dealing with neuro-toxic effect of PCBs and development of the central-nervous system among children. Based on animal data, the authors concluded that it is reasonable to believe that the effects seen in animals exposed to low doses may also occur among humans at background exposure. A meta-analysis of epidemiological studies of psychomotor development and IQ among PCB-exposed children showed that the associations were inconsistent and weak or non-existent [107]. Longnecker and Lynch highlighted the findings of associations between exposure and specific outcomes, such as the Fagan Test of Infant Intelligence and response inhibition, as being more consistent. These two tests are dependent on the working memory of the child, which is dopamine-dependent. Animal studies have shown that PCB can affect the dopaminergic system, making effects on humans plausible. Regarding associations between exposure to dioxin-like PCBs and PCDD/Fs and IQ, it was concluded that the associations were inconsistent. The findings were similar to those reported for non-dioxin-like PCBs and most of the studies reported at least one statistically significant association [107].

Longnecker and Lynch also reviewed the studies dealing with associations between early exposure to DDT compounds and neuro-toxic effects [107]. Associations between *p,p'*-DDE exposure and neurological development were not regarded as conclusive. The few studies of *p,p'*-DDT exposure, however, indicate that negative effects on neurological development are possible. It was concluded

that it is important to continue the research since the use of *p,p'*-DDT in areas affected by malaria continues [107].

In another review of the studies of PCB and neurological development, Schantz *et al.* stated that more and more data suggest that background exposure to PCB negatively affects the cognitive development among children [108]. Schantz *et al.* concluded that several studies have observed negative associations between PCB exposure and cognitive development, in spite of the fact that different types of cognitive tests were used [108].

Effects on tooth development are easy to detect. Based on the current knowledge of dioxin effects on tooth development, a recent Finnish PhD thesis concluded that the margins are low between current exposure levels of PCDD/F and the levels causing negative effects on tooth development in animals and humans [109]. It was nevertheless concluded that intake levels below 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day, which is the currently accepted tolerable intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, appears to be sufficient for protection of the future generations against negative effects on dental health [109].

Epidemiology – men and women

The following text explores the current knowledge about associations between exposure of adults to persistent halogenated organic compounds and health effects. Focus is on studies of cohorts occupationally or accidentally exposed to high levels of the compounds, and on studies of Swedish fishermen and their families living along the Swedish eastern and western coasts. A more detailed summary of studies of cohorts with background exposures is given in Appendix 1.

Cancer

It is difficult to find conclusive evidence that PCB, *p,p'*-DDE and dioxins cause cancer in studies using epidemiological methodology. A large number of participants is needed in studies of populations with background exposure levels in order to attain enough statistical power to detect the small risk increases that are expected if PCB, *p,p'*-DDE and dioxins are cancer-causing agents among humans. A problem with many epidemiological studies is the exposure assessment. At best, the concentrations of the environmental pollutants have been analyzed in blood or adipose tissue from the study participants. In case-control studies and cross-sectional studies it is, however, common that the blood or adipose tissue has been sampled after the manifestation of the disease (retrospective study). This causes uncertainties in the exposure assessment since

the disease may affect the concentrations in the biological sample due to, for example, weight loss which may cause mobilization of the lipid-soluble compounds from the body stores [51]. Prospective studies are preferable, where the concentrations of the compounds are measured before the manifestation of the disease, but these types of studies are uncommon.

The WHO organisation, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has evaluated the knowledge about carcinogenicity of dioxins, PCBs and DDT/DDE. PCBs were evaluated in 1987 [110] and at that time there was enough evidence for classification of PCBs as carcinogens in animals according to IARC. In 1987 it was concluded that the carcinogenicity data for humans were limited, and PCBs were classified as probably carcinogenic to humans (Group 2A) [110]. It is however not possible to determine the contribution of dioxin-like PCBs and dioxins to the carcinogenic effects in animals, since most of the animal studies used technical PCB mixtures containing these types of compounds [111]. DDT/DDE were evaluated by IARC in 1991 and enough evidence was found to classify the compounds as animal carcinogens [112]. Data on humans were insufficient and DDT/DDE were classified as possible carcinogenic to humans (Group 2B).

IARC has classified the most toxic dioxin 2,3,7,8-TCDD as a human carcinogen [113]. It was not possible to classify the other PCDD/F congeners due to lack of animal and human data. The classification of TCDD as a human carcinogen was based on sufficient data on animals and limited data on humans [113]. The IARC expert group included mechanistic data regarding the function of the Ah-receptor in animals and humans in the final classification of TCDD.

It was stated by the IARC that the epidemiological data on the carcinogenicity of TCDD in humans had limitations. The data mainly originate from studies of TCDD-exposed occupational cohorts from the USA, Germany and the Netherlands. In those studies an increased total cancer risk was observed among study participants with the highest TCDD exposure [113]. Less strong associations were found for specific cancer types, such as lung cancer and soft-tissue sarcoma. IARC stated that the studies were of good quality. The relative risk for cancer was, however, not high (relative risk 1.4 for the highest exposed groups) [113]. In the latest risk assessment of JECFA it was concluded that the highest exposed groups in the occupational cohorts had body burdens of TCDD that were 100- to 1000-fold higher than the total body burden of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among humans with background exposure [114].

During the accident in Seveso, Italy, in 1976 a relatively large human population was exposed to high levels of TCDD. In 2001 a 20-year follow-up of the cancer mortality in the Seveso population was published [115]. The risk of mortality in all cancers was not increased among women living in the two most affected

geographical zones (Zones A and B) at the time of the accident in comparison with the reference population. The total cancer mortality, however, was slightly increased among the men from the same areas (relative risk (RR): 1.1 (95 % confidence interval 1.0-1.3)). An increased risk of mortality from lymphatic and hemopoietic cancers was found (RR: 1.8 (1.1-3.2)) among women. Among men the mortality risk was increased for rectum cancer (RR: 2.4 (1.2-4.6)), lung cancer (RR: 1.3 (1.0-1.7)) and lymphatic and hemopoietic cancers (RR: 2.1 (1.1-4.1)). It is not possible to conclude that these excess risks of cancer mortality were due to TCDD exposure since individual data on TCDD exposure was lacking. Analyses of TCDD concentrations in blood among the residents in Zones A and B show that the variation in blood concentrations is very large [116].

A study of associations between TCDD exposure and breast cancer among 981 women from Seveso showed an increased risk of breast cancer with increased TCDD exposure, based on 15 cancer cases [117]. A ten-fold increase in blood TCDD concentration was associated with a doubling of the cancer risk. If the women were categorized into four exposure categories based on blood TCDD concentrations, no significant association between TCDD exposure and cancer risk was found [117].

A study was published in 2004 reporting cancer incidence and cancer mortality among US Vietnam veterans (Ranch Hand veterans) that had handled and sprayed herbicides contaminated with TCDD [118]. The risk of cancer mortality was lower among the veterans than among the general population in the USA. The same situation was evident for the reference population of veterans that had not been exposed to TCDD in the herbicide. The cancer incidence was not increased among the Ranch Hand veterans compared with the general population. Among Caucasian Ranch Hand veterans with the highest estimated TCDD exposure an increased total cancer risk was observed in comparison with the reference veterans. The risk of melanoma was also increased among Ranch Hand veterans with low and high TCDD exposure, and the risk of prostate cancer was increased among Ranch Hand veterans with high exposure [118].

The dioxin and PCB exposure may be high among fishermen living on the eastern coast of Sweden. A study of cancer mortality and cancer incidence among 2896 fishermen from the eastern coast of Sweden showed that the total cancer mortality was somewhat lower in the studied population compared with the general population living in the same regions (standardized mortality ratio (SMR): 0.87 (95 % confidence interval: 0,68-1.03)) [49]. Mortality in specific cancers did not differ from the general population, with the exception that there was a higher mortality in multiple myelomas among the fishermen (SMR: 3.1 (1.2-6.4)). The cancer incidence in general did not differ between the fishermen and the general population (standardized incidence ratio (SIR): 0.95 (0.89-1.01)). Incidence of squamous cell skin cancer was higher among the fishermen (SIR: 2.3 (1.5-3.5)).

SIR for stomach cancer (1.6 (1.0-2.4)) and lip cancer (2.60 (1.05-5.36)) was also increased among the fishermen [49]. The fishermen had a decreased incidence of colon cancer (0.34 (0.12-0.87)) and melanoma (0.00 (0.00-0.72)). Exposure assessment of dioxins and PCBs was lacking in the study and the cancer results were not adjusted for potential confounders. It was concluded that it was not possible to establish if the risk increases in site-specific cancers among the fishermen were due to high exposure to persistent organochlorines. The fishermen may have been exposed to other potentially carcinogenic substances [49].

In a similar study of 1,989 wives of the fishermen, it was found that cancer mortality was not increased among those from the eastern coast of Sweden compared with the mortality among the general population in the same regions [46]. Cancer incidence was slightly higher among the fishermen's wives (SIR: 1.17 (1.00-1.36)). No significant differences in mortality and incidence of specific cancer forms were found between the fishermen's wives and the general population [46].

These two studies of the fishermen and fishermen's wives, that most probably have the highest PCB and dioxin exposure in Sweden, show that the cancer risks among the fishermen and their wives were not markedly different from those of the general population. The lack of individual exposure assessment and lack of adjustment of the results for potential confounders makes it difficult to draw firm conclusions about the involvement of the environmental pollutants in the observed risk increases of the few specific cancer forms.

Studies of cancer risks in populations with background exposures to dioxins, PCB and DDT compounds have not been able to draw firm conclusions about causality of observed associations between exposure and cancer risks (see Appendix 1). In the Nordic countries, studies of good quality have not found consistent associations between exposure and risks of breast cancer, endometrial cancer and soft-tissue sarcoma. Numerous other cancer forms have been studied in many areas of the world and in the few cases, when strong associations between exposure and cancer have been found, problems with confounding and exposure assessment have made it difficult to draw conclusions about the causality of associations. Furthermore, some of these studies have been too small to enable firm conclusions about causality. In a combined analysis of five breast cancer studies from the USA it was concluded that the results did not support a causal positive association between body burdens of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE and breast cancer risk [119]. Two reviews of the literature dealing with breast cancer risks and background exposures to PCBs came to similar conclusions [120, 121]. In a review of epidemiological studies of exposures to DDT compounds and cancer risks, Rogan and Chen [122] concluded that there was no compelling evidence for the carcinogenicity of DDT and its metabolites in humans.

In conclusion, the results of the epidemiological studies do not conclusively show that PCB, dioxins and DDT compounds cause increased cancer risks at the background exposure levels currently found in Sweden. If these compounds are cancer-causing agents in humans at background exposure levels, then the risks are very small and difficult to detect with available epidemiological methods.

Table 22. Comparisons between estimated TCDD levels in groups with the highest TCDD exposure from occupational cohorts and levels of total TEQ measured in Sweden (median or mean values (min-max)).

Cohort	N	Concentrations (pg/g lipid)	Reference
German chemical workers	56	1500 (3-7000)	[123]
Dutch chemical workers	14	1400 (900-2300)	[124]
US chemical workers	344	1600 (6-210000)	[125]
	4		
Young women, Uppsala 2002-2004	32	13 (6-21)	This report
Men, no fatty Baltic Sea (BS) fish	9	25 (10-63) ^a	[85]
Men, moderate BS fish consumption	8	31 (18-67) ^a	[85]
Men, high BS fish consumption	9	82 (16-247) ^a	[85]

^aEstimated concentrations from [85].

For the risk assessment it is helpful to compare the body burdens of TCDD detected in occupationally-exposed cohorts with body burdens of total TEQ detected in different human populations in Sweden (Table 22). The highest exposed subgroups in the occupational cohorts had on average TCDD concentrations of about 1500 pg/g lipid. Among primiparous mothers from Uppsala County, Sweden, the median total TEQ concentration was found to be approximately 100-fold lower and the maximum concentrations about 50-fold lower than the mean TCDD levels in occupationally exposed groups. Among Swedish men with no consumption of contaminated fatty Baltic Sea fish, the average concentrations were 25- to 60-fold lower [45]. The same was true for men reporting an average consumption of these types of fish of 3 times a month. The lowest difference (6 to 20 times lower) was found among men with high consumption of contaminated fish [45] (Table 22).

Diabetes

Associations between body burdens of TCDD and diabetes have been studied in occupationally-exposed cohorts. The Ranch Hand cohort of Vietnam veterans exposed to TCDD during handling of, and spraying, with a TCDD-contaminated herbicide, is the most extensively studied cohort. Higher mean blood-sugar concentrations were found in this cohort than among study participants in a reference group that had not been in contact with the herbicide [126]. Prevalence of diabetes (type not specified) and use of oral diabetes medicine increased with increasing TCDD exposure. The time it took to attain clinically-manifested

diabetes was also decreased with increasing TCDD exposure and the number of individuals with abnormal insulin levels without diabetes diagnosis increased with increased TCDD exposure [126].

In a study of US Air Force veterans with background concentrations of TCDD in the blood (≤ 10 pg/g lipid) an increased risk of diabetes was found in the group of study participants in the highest TCDD-exposure quartile after adjustment for potential confounders [127].

A follow-up study of the Ranch Hand cohort showed significantly decreased insulin sensitivity with increasing TCDD body burdens among veterans that did not have a diabetes diagnosis [128]. It was however concluded that the differences in insulin sensitivity were small and that the biological relevance of the findings were difficult to interpret [128]. An important finding in this study was that the TCDD elimination from the body was not affected by the disease, indicating that the TCDD concentrations in blood are not affected by the disease [129].

In two cohorts of occupationally-exposed industrial workers from the USA increased mean levels of blood sugar were found compared with the level in controls that were not occupationally exposed to TCDD [130,131]. Trichlorophenol workers from the USA however did not have a higher prevalence of diabetes than study participants in a reference group living in the same area as the workers [130]. The diabetes prevalence was not associated with the blood concentrations of TCDD among the workers [130].

The cohort of fishermen and their wives living on the eastern-coast of Sweden were used in a study of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE as risk factors for diabetes (type 2) [132]. Blood analyses of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE were performed on 196 men and 184 women. The study participants were asked questions about diabetes. PCB 153 was used as a marker of body burdens of other PCBs. Diabetes was reported by 12 men and 10 women. Even though the disease was reported by a small number of study participants, a significantly positive association between body burdens of PCB 153 and DDE and diabetes was found among the men after adjustment for potential confounders. The associations among the women were not as strong. The researchers concluded that the blood samples had been taken after diagnosis of the disease making it difficult to interpret the results [132]. Type 2 diabetes is associated with different metabolic alterations that have the potential to affect the blood concentrations of PCBs and DDT compounds [132].

A few more studies have found that diabetes patients have higher blood concentrations of PCBs, dioxins and certain chlorinated pesticides/metabolites (see Appendix 1). These studies also have a cross-sectional design where the blood concentrations have been analyzed after the outbreak of the disease.

Cardio-vascular disease

Some studies have indicated increased cholesterol and triglyceride levels in groups with high TCDD exposure [133, 134], whereas other studies have not found significant associations [131, 135-137]. Among occupationally exposed workers from Germany and the Netherlands there was no increased risk of cardio-vascular mortality, more specifically ischaemic heart disease, than would be expected [115, 124, 138]. However, within the Dutch cohort an increased mortality in ischaemic heart disease was observed with increased TCDD exposure, but this association was not found among the German workers [115, 124, 138]. In another German cohort, a positive association was found between TCDD exposure and mortality in ischaemic heart disease [139]. An increased mortality in ischaemic heart disease was found among occupationally exposed workers from the USA but no association between TCDD exposure and mortality was observed [140]. Within a sub-group from the USA cohort no increased risk of cardio-vascular disease was found [135]. Mixed results were reported in studies of the Seveso and Ranch Hand cohorts [115, 141, 142].

Fishermen with high consumption of PCB/PCDD/F-contaminated fish living on the eastern coast of Sweden had a lower risk of mortality in cardio-vascular disease than expected in comparison with the mortality among the general population from the same area [SMR: 0.88 (0.77-0.99)] [49]. The risk to die in ischaemic heart disease was 12 % lower among the fishermen (not statistically significant). Among wives of the east coast fishermen the mortality risk in cardio-vascular disease was not significantly different from that of the general population [46].

In conclusion, the studies of cohorts with high dioxin exposure have reported mixed results. The studies of Swedish fishermen and their wives indicate that persistent halogenated compounds are not an important risk factor for cardio-vascular disease mortality. The influence of confounding factors can not be disregarded however, since these groups probably had intake of nutrients from fish that have the potential to protect against cardio-vascular disease.

The immune system and infectious diseases

Small alterations in numbers and percentages of certain types of lymphocytes, as well as blood levels of immunoglobulins, interleukins, immune complexes and complement, have been found in cohorts with high exposures to dioxins, PCBs and DDT-compounds from the USA, Germany and Great Britain [131, 143-150]. In follow-up studies of the German cohorts no associations were found between blood concentrations of PCDD/Fs and risk of infections during and after the exposure period [151]. No associations between dioxin exposure and levels of antibodies against tetanus were found 3 weeks after vaccination [151]. An *in vitro*

study of lymphocyte function did not find any associations between dioxin exposure and immune suppression [152].

Shortly after the Seveso accident, subtle and short-term changes in lymphocyte numbers were observed among exposed patients [153]. In a study of 62 randomly selected individuals living in the two most contaminated areas, Zones A and B, and 58 controls from surrounding areas, a negative association between levels of IgG and TCDD in blood plasma was found, after adjustment for potential confounders [154]. No associations were found for IgM, IgA and complement 3 and 4.

Associations between blood levels of markers of immune function and PCB, dioxins and DDT compounds were studied among 23 fishermen with high consumption of contaminated fish from the Baltic Sea and 20 men that did not consume fish at all [155]. The fishermen had a lower proportion of NK-cells than the control men. A negative correlation was observed between consumption of contaminated fish and NK-cells. Among 11 of the study participants a negative correlation between blood levels of NK-cells and PCB 126 and *p,p'*-DDE was found. No associations were found for other lymphocyte types and immunoglobulins [155].

In a study of men from Latvia, with different fish consumption habits, a positive association between fish consumption and number of B-cells and the CD4⁺/CD8⁺ ratio was found [156]. The association between fish consumption and cytotoxic T cells (CD8⁺) was negative.

A few epidemiological studies of associations between background body burdens of dioxins, PCBs and DDT compounds and markers of immune function have been published [157-159]. The results are difficult to interpret due to uncertainties about the clinical consequences of subtle shifts in immune marker levels that were observed in some of the studies. It is also not possible to draw firm conclusions about causality of the observed associations, since there may be unknown life-style or medical factors that could contribute to the observed associations.

Osteoporosis

Among over 17,000 men and women from the Swedish fisherman family cohort (both east and west coast), 586 hospital-treated bone fractures were observed among the women and 524 fractures among the men between 1987 and 1996 [160]. For women 418 fractures were osteoporosis-related, whereas the corresponding number for men was 253. A comparison of fracture risks between study participants living on the eastern and western coasts of Sweden showed that the eastern-coast women had a higher risk of fractures of spinal vertebra after

adjustment for age and year of fracture (incidence rate ratio (IRR): 2.29 (1.23-4.28). No differences in fracture risk were observed among the men [160].

In another study over 6,000 men and 5,000 women from the same cohort were asked questions about fractures, fish consumption and risk factors for osteoporosis [161]. No difference in incidence of osteoporosis-related fractures was found between the study participants living on the eastern and western coasts. Fish consumption was not related to risk of fracture among the eastern-coast men, but a higher risk of fractures was observed among the women reporting a consumption of fatty PCB and dioxin-contaminated fish from the Baltic Sea of more than once per month than among women reporting lower fish consumption [161].

Bone density was measured among 196 men and 184 women from the eastern-coast fishermen cohort and PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE were analyzed in blood lipids [82]. Biochemical markers for bone growth and bone degradation were also analyzed. No statistically significant associations between body burdens of the pollutants and bone density were found after adjustment for age and BMI. The same result was evident for the biochemical markers [82].

Three additional studies have investigated the associations between bone density and body burdens of PCB (1 study) and *p,p'*-DDE (3 studies) among men and women with background body burdens of the pollutants (see Appendix 1). In a study of 115 men from Uppsala County, Sweden, no significant associations between bone density and body burdens of PCBs was found, whereas a weak negative association was found for *p,p'*-DDE. A negative association between bone density and *p,p'*-DDE body burden was also found among older women from Australia, with a sedentary lifestyle, but no associations were found among women from the USA [163, 164].

Taken together the results of the few studies do not suggest that PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE are strong risk factors for osteoporosis. The published studies have however been too small or lacked proper exposure assessment to allow firm conclusions about the possibility of small risk increases caused by the pollutants.

Reproduction

Age at puberty

Among 282 women exposed during the Seveso accident no association was observed between concentrations of TCDD in blood, sampled directly after the accident, and age at puberty [165]. An age-stratified statistical analysis did not indicate associations among women exposed at ages <8 years and <4 years [165, 166].

In the fisherman family cohort from Sweden information about age at puberty was collected from 545 women living both on the east and west coast of Sweden (wives and sisters of the fishermen) [167]. No difference in age at puberty was found between the east and west coast women. Women that had grown up in the fisherman village, which is an indicator for high fish consumption during childhood, did not have a different age at puberty than the other women in the study. No changes in age at puberty were detected between 1944 and 1980 [167].

Several studies from Europe, North America and China have investigated if PCB, dioxin and *p,p'*-DDE exposure and affects the age of puberty, and development of sex organs and body growth (Appendix 1). The results of the studies vary and taken together no consistent associations between exposures and out-come have been found.

Menstrual cycle

No statistically significant associations were observed between blood concentrations of TCDD and menstrual cycle length, number of days with bleeding and bleeding intensity among 301 women from the Seveso cohort [168]. A decreased risk of irregular menstrual cycle was observed with increased TCDD concentrations after adjustment for age at interview and age at puberty.

Studies of cohorts with very high PCB and *p,p'*-DDE exposure are lacking. The few studies of cohorts with background exposure to PCB and *p,p'*-DDE suggest that if these compounds affect the menstrual cycle the effects are so subtle that they are very difficult to detect in epidemiological studies (Appendix 1).

Sex hormones

Associations between blood levels of sex hormones and body burdens of environmental pollutants are usually difficult to study among women, due to the variation in hormone levels during the menstrual cycle. During the third trimester of the pregnancy the hormone levels are more stable. In a small study from Taiwan a significantly negative association was observed between the ratio between two estrogens metabolites (4-OH-E₂/2-OH-E₂) and body burdens of TCDD and 1,2,3,7,8-pentaCDD after adjustment for age and body burdens of other dioxins and PCBs [169] (Appendix 1). No associations with total PCDD/F TEQ were observed. In another study of hormone levels during the menstrual cycle among 50 women, born in Southeast Asia but living in the USA, no associations were observed between blood concentrations of PCB and hormone levels (estrogens and progesterone) during menstruation [170]. The study covered

three menstrual cycles. For *p,p'*-DDE a negative association with progesterone levels at luteal phase was found [170] (Appendix 1).

Blood levels of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), prolactin and free testosterone were analyzed among 110 men from Sweden (N=43) and Latvia (N=67), reporting high consumption of PCB- and dioxin-contaminated fatty Baltic fish [171]. In the blood 18 different PCB congeners, 5 hydroxylated PCB metabolites, *p,p'*-DDT and -DDE, HCB, pentachlorophenol (PCP), and PBDE 47 were analyzed. The only statistically significant association found was a negative association between blood levels of FSH and PCP, after adjustment for age of the men [171].

Among Swedish fishermen (N=196), reporting high consumption of fatty Baltic fish and living on the Swedish east coast, associations between blood concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE and blood levels of gonadotropins and sex hormones were studied [172]. A weak negative association between *p,p'*-DDE and estradiol was observed.

In another study of fishermen from the Swedish east and west coast associations between blood levels of gonadotropins and sex hormones and concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE were studied [173]. After adjustment for age, no statistically significant associations were found.

Among 184 Swedish fishermen, and men from Greenland (N=258), Poland (N=113) and Ukraine (N=194) the blood levels of hormones and concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE were analyzed [174]. A large variation in results was observed between the studied regions. Among the men from the Ukraine a significantly positive association between levels of SHBG and LH and concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE was found. Moreover a negative association was found between *p,p'*-DDE and inhibin B after adjustment for potential confounders. Among the other groups of men no associations between hormone levels and body burdens of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE were found. When all men were included in the statistical analysis only the association between *p,p'*-DDE and FSH was statistically significant after adjustment for potential confounders [174].

The seven different studies of associations between levels of sex hormones in blood and background exposure to PCBs and *p,p'*-DDE among men only observed weak associations or no associations at all (Appendix 1).

Time to pregnancy (TTP)

One way to estimate the fertility of women is to determine the time between the decision of the woman to try to become pregnant and the time of conception. TTP

is influenced by the fertility of the man and it is therefore difficult to determine who contributed most to the TTP. A significant association between exposure of the mother and TTP supports the hypothesis that it is the woman's fertility that has been influenced by the exposure. It may however be possible that the mother and father have been similarly exposed to the studied compounds for a long time, for instance through food.

The women in the Swedish fisherman cohort (N=121) that were living on the east coast of Sweden answered a questionnaire including questions about TTP for their first pregnancy [175]. The concentrations of PCB 153 were analyzed in blood sampled 1995 and the concentrations were back-calculated to the time of pregnancy. The women were divided into tertiles depending on the calculated PCB 153 concentrations at the time of pregnancy (low, medium, high). After adjustment for potential confounders, no significant association was found between TTP and blood PCB 153 concentrations [175]. In an expanded study, including an additional 165 women from the east coast of Sweden, no association between TTP and PCB 153 was found [176]. In the years 2001-2002 blood from 544 women living on the east and west coasts of Sweden, was sampled and analyzed for PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE [177]. The blood concentrations of the compounds were back-calculated to the time of the first pregnancy.

In this study as well, no associations between body burdens of the compounds and TTP were found [177]. In another study of 67 men and women from the eastern and western coasts of Sweden, blood concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE were back-calculated to the time of their first planned pregnancy together [178]. In this small study no associations between TTP and body burdens of the compounds among the men and the women were found.

TTP and body burdens of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE were studied among men and women from Poland, Ukraine, Greenland and Sweden (fishermen's families) [177], and no statistically-significant associations were found. In another study within this EU project a variation in fertility was found among couples from different regions dependent on differences in exposure to *p,p'*-DDE between the regions [179]. The regional differences in fertility could, however, also depend on other factors such as the use of contraceptives and sexual behavior.

These studies of fishermen's families suggest that the body burdens of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE at the time of pregnancy do not markedly affect the TTP, and this conclusion is supported by a study from the USA [180] (Appendix 1). Associations between pre-natal exposure to the compounds and TTP later in life has only been investigated in one study where a negative association between pre-natal *p,p'*-DDE exposure and TTP was found [181] (Appendix 1).

Miscarriage

No increased risk of spontaneous abortion was reported among 555 women from Seveso after exposure to TCDD [182]. Moreover, no association with blood concentrations of TCDD was found.

A cohort of occupationally-exposed male chemical workers from the USA (N=281) were used in a study of TCDD exposure and miscarriage among the partners of the workers [183]. These men had TCDD concentrations in the blood that were more than a 100-fold higher than the total TEQ concentrations found among the general population. No statistically-significant associations between TCDD concentrations among the men and miscarriage among their women were found.

Among Vietnam veterans exposed to TCDD during handling and use of a TCDD-contaminated herbicide, no increased risk of miscarriage or stillborn babies were found in comparison with a group of unexposed veterans that did their service in south-east Asia during the same time period [184].

In a cohort of 2033 male workers, exposed to DDT during a malaria prevention campaign, the concentrations of *p,p'*-DDE in body lipids were modelled, based on analyses of the DDT-metabolite in a small group of the men and the exposure history according to number of years in the campaign, type of work, etc. [185]. Among men with the highest body burdens of *p,p'*-DDE, an increased risk of malformations were observed among babies born after the men had been exposed. No associations were found with risks of miscarriage and sex ratio [185]. A large number of potential confounders were included in the statistical analyses of the results.

The risk of having a full-term, but stillborn baby, was studied among wives of the Swedish fishermen [186]. During the period 1973-1991 3553 children were born in the cohort and the risk of having a stillborn baby was not different from that of the general population during the same time period. A similar result was obtained for sudden infant death and malformations, with the exception of a decreased risk of serious malformations among children born in fishermen families living on the east coast [186]. In a following study 1434 women from the fishermen cohort were asked about the outcome of their first pregnancy [187]. No differences in risks of miscarriage and stillborn babies were observed after adjustment for potential confounders when women from the east coast of Sweden, that reported a consumption of fatty Baltic fish of >14 portions/month, were compared with women from the same area that had not eaten this type of fish [187]. The blood concentrations of PCB 153 did not differ between women reporting a miscarriage/stillborn baby (N=8) and women reporting a normal birth outcome (N=95) [187].

Women in the fishermen cohort (N=165) living on the eastern coast of Sweden answered a questionnaire about reproduction in 1999 [176]. PCB 153 concentrations were analyzed in blood sampled in year 2000 and the concentrations were back-calculated to the time of the first planned pregnancy. Women that reported a miscarriage during their first planned pregnancy (N=16) had significantly lower concentrations of PCB 153 than women with normal pregnancies [176].

In a few studies from Australia, Germany and Japan the body burdens of DDT compounds have been determined among women that at the same time were asked about miscarriages in earlier pregnancies (Appendix 1). In a study from Australia no associations between body burdens of DDT compounds and miscarriages were found [188], and this was also the case in two studies from Germany and Japan [189, 190]. Women with markedly higher body burdens of DDT compounds than normally found in Swedish women today had an increased risk of miscarriages when they had a high body burden of *p,p'*-DDE [191], and an increased risk of early miscarriages when they had a high body burdens of total DDT [192] (Appendix 1).

Sex ratio

Directly after the Seveso accident more girls than boys were born by TCDD-exposed women [193]. The concentrations of TCDD in blood serum collected right after the accident were analyzed among 239 men and 296 women. Between 1977 and 1986 346 girls and 328 boys were born. The blood concentrations of TCDD among the mothers were not associated with the chance of having a girl. A strong positive association was, however, found between the serum concentrations of TCDD among the fathers and the chance of giving birth to a girl. Men that were exposed to TCDD at an age of less than 19 years fathered more girls than men that were exposed at older ages [193].

In concordance with the Seveso study, men in the Yucheng accident on Taiwan, who were exposed to high dioxin and PCB levels in rice oil before the age of 20 years, had a higher chance of fathering a girl than non-exposed men in the same age [194]. Among women exposed in the same accident no change in sex ratio was observed among their children.

In a small study of male workers exposed to high levels of TCDD it was also observed that men exposed before the age of 20 years fathered fewer boys than expected [195].

Men from Russia with a high exposure to TCDD (N=150) fathered more girls than expected [196]. Women with the same type of TCDD exposure did not give birth to more girls than expected.

Among male chemical workers exposed to high levels of TCDD no alteration in sex ratio was observed among children born by their wives, in comparison with the sex ratio among children born in an unexposed reference population [183]. The participating men had been exposed to TCDD as adults.

Fishermen living on the Swedish eastern and western coasts (N=149) were studied regarding associations between blood concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE and the proportions of sperm sex chromosomes [197]. The proportion of Y-chromosomes was positively associated with the blood concentrations of the compounds after adjustment for potential confounders.

In an extended study, which included Swedish fishermen and men from Greenland (N=157), Poland (N=121), and Ukraine (N=120), a positive association between the proportion of sperms with Y chromosomes and blood concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE was found among the Swedish fishermen [198]. Among men from Poland the association with PCB 153 was negative. For the other two cohorts no associations were observed. It was concluded that the result among the Swedish fishermen was not confirmed by the results in the other cohorts. The differences in results could be due to differences in exposures caused by life style or food habit differences, or could be due to chance [198].

In Australia the association between sex ratio and body burdens of *p,p'*-DDT and DDE was studied among 815 primiparous women [188] (Appendix 1). After adjustment for potential confounders, no significant association between body burdens of the DDT compounds and sex ratio was found.

Taken together, the results suggest that men with high dioxin exposure father fewer boys than girls if the men have been exposed at a young age. If background-level exposure to dioxins also causes such an effect is not known. Women appear not to be sensitive to this effect of TCDD. It is not possible to draw conclusions about associations between body burdens of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE and proportions of sperms with Y chromosomes in male populations with background-level exposure. The results vary considerably between cohorts.

Endometriosis

Among 601 women exposed to TCDD during the Seveso accident, 296 women were recruited in a study of endometriosis. Among the recruited women, 19 of the examined women had the diagnosis of endometriosis and 277 examined women

did not have the disease [199]. No statistically significant association between TCDD exposure and endometriosis was found.

Only a few endometriosis studies among women with background exposure to PCB and dioxins have been reported (Appendix 1). In some studies positive associations between exposure and outcome have been reported [200, 201], whereas other studies did not find significant associations [202-204].

Menopause

Two studies from the USA did not find statistically-significant associations between blood PCB concentrations and age at menopause [205, 206] (Appendix 1), whereas two other studies reported varied associations between age at menopause and body burdens of DDT compounds [206, 207] (Appendix 1). In one study the women with the highest body burdens of *p,p'*-DDT were younger than women with low body burdens, whereas no association with body burdens of *p,p'*-DDE was observed. In another study a positive association was found between age at menopause and body burdens of *p,p'*-DDE [206]. In both studies the researchers were careful in their conclusions since the body burdens of the environmental pollutants had been analyzed years after the women had reached menopause (Appendix 1).

Function of sex glands and sperm quality

Among 176 fishermen from the east and west coast of Sweden, associations between body burdens of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE and sperm-chromatin integrity were studied [208]. A negative association between body burdens of PCB 153 and sperm-chromatin integrity was found, also after adjustment for potential confounders, when the body burdens of PCB 153 were treated as a categorical variable. In this case the men in the category with the highest body burdens had lower chromatin integrity than men in the reference category with the lowest body burdens. If the body burdens of PCB were included as a continuous variable in the statistical analysis no significant association was observed after age adjustment. No associations were observed for *p,p'*-DDE [208].

An enlarged study included, apart from the Swedish fishermen, men from Greenland (N=193), Poland (N=141) and Ukraine (N=195) [209]. A first analysis of the results suggested that the men from Greenland differed from the other men in the study regarding associations between blood concentrations of PCB 153 and DNA-damage in the sperm chromatin (DFI). Because of this the men from Greenland were treated separately in the statistical analysis. After adjustment for potential confounders a positive association between PCB 153 and percent DFI were found among the men from Sweden, Poland and Ukraine, but not among the

men from Greenland. No associations between exposure and chromatin condensation were found in any of the study groups. The compound *p,p'*-DDE was associated with neither DNA damage nor condensation.

Associations between exposure to PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE and sperm quality (semen volume, sperm concentration, sperm count and sperm motility) were studied among 99 fishermen from the Swedish west coast and 96 fishermen from the east coast [173]. No significant associations were observed after adjustment for age.

The fishermen cohort (N=157) was also used in a study of markers for sex gland function in semen and associations with PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE [210]. The following markers were studied: activity of the enzyme neutral alfa-glucosidase (marker for the function of the epididymis), and levels of PSA (prostate-specific antigen), zinc (marker of prostate function), and fructose in semen. No significant associations between markers and exposure were found after adjustment for confounders.

Associations between blood concentrations of PCB 153 and *p,p'*-DDE and markers of sex-gland function in semen were studied in four cohorts of men from Sweden (fishermen, N=135), Greenland (N=163), Poland (N=167) and Ukraine (N=158) [211]. Among men from Poland and Greenland a negative association between PCB 153 and total activity of neutral alfa-glucosidase after adjustment for confounders was found whereas a positive association was found for men from Ukraine. A positive association between PSA and zinc levels and PCB 153 was observed among men from Ukraine, whereas a negative association between PCB 153 and fructose levels was found among the Swedish fishermen. No associations were found between markers and *p,p'*-DDE [211]. In another study of these four cohorts, it was concluded that there were no differences in sperm quality between the cohorts that could be explained by differences in PCB and DDE exposure between the cohorts, with the exception of higher sperm motility among the Polish men with the lowest PCB exposure [179].

Associations between background exposure to PCB and *p,p'*-DDE and sex-gland function and sperm quality have been reported (Appendix 1). Among the many outcomes studied only a few weak associations have been found, [212-214]. The only exception is a study of Mexican men exposed to DDT during a malaria prevention campaign [215]. Several statistically-significant, negative associations between *p,p'*-DDE concentrations in blood and different sperm quality measurements, such as percent motile sperms, percent sperms with tail damage, and percent sperms with incomplete chromatin condensation, were observed (Appendix 1).

Thyroid hormones

Studies of occupational cohorts have, in some cases, found weak associations between dioxin exposure and levels of thyroid hormones in blood. The results vary and the exposure assessment has sometimes been uncertain [130, 131, 216]. Within the German cohorts of dioxin-exposed individuals, a higher frequency of thyroid disease was observed compared with the frequency found in a reference population [217]. The risk was highest within the most exposed group but the risk was not higher among those with chloracne [217]. In the Ranch Hand cohort the risk of thyroid disease was not increased, and this was also the case for a cohort of US chemical workers [130, 218]. Among dioxin-exposed German chemical workers higher levels of certain blood markers of thyroid function, such as T4 and TBG (thyroid-hormone-binding-globuline) were found, but no such associations were found among chemical workers from the USA [130, 131].

No associations were found between thyroid hormone levels and blood levels of PCDD/DF among 76 workers in a metal recycling plant [219]. Similar findings were reported in a small study of Yusho patients (N=16), who were poisoned by PCDD/DF/PCB through consumption of contaminated rice oil [220]. No differences in thyroid-hormone levels between patients and controls were found [220]. Among 37 workers with background exposure to TCDD, a weak negative association between body burdens of TCDD and T3 and TSH levels in blood was found [221]. No adjustment of the results for potential confounders was conducted.

Hagmar et al. [79] studied associations between blood concentrations of PCB 153 and levels of thyroid hormones among 182 women from the fishermen cohort living on the eastern coast of Sweden. Total levels of T3 decreased significantly with increased body burdens of PCB 153, even after age adjustment. It was however concluded that the association was weak, since only 6 % of the variation in hormone levels could be explained by the variation in PCB levels and age in the regression analysis. No significant associations were found for TSH, free T4 or total T4 [79]. In a similar study of 196 fishermen living on the eastern coast of Sweden a negative association between body burdens of *p,p'*-DDE and TSH levels was observed, here also after age adjustment [172]. In this case the regression model explained 7 % of the variation in TSH levels. No associations were observed for PCB 153 [172].

The levels of thyroid hormones, PCB (89 congeners) and *p,p'*-DDE were analyzed in blood from 178 men and 51 women from the USA, with different levels of consumption of Great Lakes fish [222]. Among the women the levels of thyroxine and total and free T4 were negatively associated with the body burden of total PCB after adjustment for age, BMI and medication. Further adjustment for potential confounders did not alter the associations. TSH levels were positively associated with the body burdens of PCB after exclusion of an outlier in the

statistical analysis. Among the men, the blood levels of T4 were negatively associated with the body burdens of PCB after adjustment for potential confounders [222].

In 2002 Hagmar [223] reviewed the knowledge of PCB exposure and thyroid function, and concluded that the published studies did not show in a convincing way that PCB exposure influences the homeostasis of thyroid hormones. It was, however, not possible to completely dismiss the hypothesis that PCB influences thyroid-hormone homeostasis [223].

Epidemiology-brominated flame retardants (BFR)

Little information is available about human effects of BFRs, with the exception of polybrominated biphenyls (PBB). Two epidemiological studies were initiated after an incident in Michigan when a technical mixture of PBB was mistakenly mixed into animal feed causing contamination of the local food production. The epidemiological studies, which were published in 1994 [224], showed few effects related with PBB exposure. In one case subtle effects were detected in a neurological test, but this result has been questioned. One of the cohorts was followed up regarding cancer risks between 1973 and 1993 [225]. A positive association between risks of cancer in the gastro-intestinal tract and PBB levels in blood was observed, as well as for lymphomas. No associations between PBB and total cancer risk were observed [225].

Studies of decaPBDE and skin sensitisation in humans did not show any significant effects [224]. Among workers exposed to PBB and PBDE, a higher prevalence of hypothyroidism and certain effects on nerve signal transduction was found [226]. No associations between outcomes and decaPBDE were observed. A case-control study of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (NHL) reported a positive association between risk of NHL and body burdens of BDE 47 [87]. The study was small and treatment of confounders in the statistical analysis was limited. Among 110 men with high fish consumption [171] an association between PBDE and TSH levels in blood was observed, but it was concluded that this association probably was due to chance [171]. Taken together the results of the few studies are not coherent enough to enable firm conclusion about causal associations between BFR exposure and the studied health effects.

Conclusions-epidemiology

The studies of children exposed to very high levels of mainly PCDD/F *in utero* or early after birth have shown negative effects on, for example, tooth development, the skin, the central nervous system (CNS), and reproduction. Studies of skin effects (chloracne) and reproduction (skewed sex ratio) suggest that the childhood phase of development is a more sensitive period for dioxin exposure than the period after puberty. The reproduction effects (skewed sex ratio, more girls than boys born) occurred only when the fathers had been exposed to high levels of dioxins during early life, whereas no effects were observed if the mothers were exposed. This suggests that boys are more sensitive than girls regarding skewed sex ratio of future offspring.

Comparative studies of sensitivity of children and adults to background exposures to persistent organic halogenated environmental pollutants are lacking. A number of studies have found significant negative effects of *in utero* exposure on birth weight and the CNS. Other studies have, however, not found any significant effects. The scientific evaluations of the studies of children have arrived at different conclusions about the causality of associations between *in utero* PCB and PCDD/F exposure and birth weight/CNS effects. Taken together, the results of the many studies do not allow firm conclusions about causality of associations between negative health effects and exposure to persistent halogenated organic pollutants early in life.

In recent years a few studies have investigated if background pre-natal exposure and exposure soon after birth to PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE affect the function of the immune system and if the exposures are risk factors for infectious diseases and allergies/asthma. Most of the studies have found statistically-significant associations between exposure and shifts in immune markers, mainly numbers and percentages of white blood cells (WBC). The results are, however, difficult to interpret since different markers of immune function have been studied and the age of the children varied between studies. Moreover, the shifts in immune markers have been within the limits regarded as normal for healthy children. It is therefore currently not possible to draw conclusions about health consequences of these subtle changes. Studies of PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE exposure early in life and infectious diseases and allergies/asthma are too few to enable firm conclusions about causal relationships between exposures and health outcomes.

In conclusion, there are currently many uncertainties regarding the causality of associations between exposure to background levels of PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE early in life and health development during childhood. It can, however, be concluded that if background exposures of children in Sweden really cause negative health effects they will be very subtle and hard to detect in epidemiological studies. There are so many factors in life that influence the health

development of children that very large studies with good control of all these potential confounding factors are needed in order to allow detection of the subtle health effects that may occur at background exposures.

TCDD is the only persistent halogenated organic substance that has been classified as a human carcinogen by the WHO research center for cancer, IARC. Studies of occupationally-exposed cohorts have shown that groups of workers with high TCDD exposure had an overall increased risk of cancer. The risk increases were however small and the mean TCDD exposure levels among the exposed workers were approximately 100-fold higher than the mean background exposure of the general Swedish population to PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs. Studies from the Nordic countries, as well as from other parts of the world, have not found that background PCB/DDE exposures are important risk factors for endometrial cancer or breast cancer among women, and STS among women and men. Among fishermen and their wives, with high consumption of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea contaminated with persistent halogenated organic compounds, no increases in overall cancer risks were detected. Risk increases for certain specific cancer forms were observed, but it was not possible to draw conclusions about the involvement of PCB/DDE/PCDD/F in the risk increases of these cancer forms. Many specific cancer forms have been studied in cohorts with background exposures to PCB/DDE/PCDD/F. In the cases where positive associations between exposures and outcomes have been observed, problems with confounders and exposure assessment have made it impossible to draw conclusions about causality between exposures and outcomes. In some cases the studies have also been too small to allow firm conclusions. Taken together, the cancer studies published so far suggest that the current levels of exposure of the general population in Sweden to persistent halogenated organic compounds constitute a very small cancer risk or no cancer risk at all.

The results of epidemiological studies of the function of the immune system among adults do not suggest that the current exposure levels of PCB, PCDD/DF and *p,p'*-DDE exposures in Sweden cause severe negative effects on immune function. It is not likely that the exposures cause serious negative effects on thyroid function and bone development. However, as in the case of cancer, it is not possible to exclude that the exposures cause subtle negative effects that are very difficult to detect in epidemiological studies.

Several studies have investigated if PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE exposures are risk factors for diabetes. The majority of the studies have found statistically significant positive associations between body burdens of the compounds and risks of diabetes. All the studies have however been cross-sectional in design, which means that the blood levels of the halogenated compounds have been determined when the disease already has manifested itself. Diabetes is a metabolic disease and it can therefore not be excluded that the disease is the cause of the

observed enhanced blood levels of the halogenated compounds among diabetic subjects. Patients with diabetes are given the advice to loose weight, and weight loss before blood sampling may cause increased levels of the environmental pollutants in blood lipids and body fat.

Effects of persistent halogenated organic pollutants on reproduction have been studied among women and men from the Swedish fishermen cohort. Outcomes are reported in terms of age at puberty, time to pregnancy, miscarriages and malformations, sex hormone levels, and several markers of sex-gland function and sperm quality. No consistent findings of negative effects associated with exposures were reported. A study of young military conscripts found a positive association between blood levels of PCB 153 and levels of steroid-hormone-binding-globuline (SHBG) and a negative association with the ratio between testosterone and SHBG. It was, however, concluded by the researchers that no such association was found among Swedish fishermen, which may suggest that the findings among the conscripts were due to chance. The results from similar studies around the world vary and it is difficult to find coherent associations between exposures and outcomes. Body burdens of the studied compounds have often been assessed at the same time as the outcomes, and in some cases several years after the outcomes. An interesting finding is the shift in sex ratio that was found among newly-born children in the Seveso cohort, i.e. more girls than boys were born shortly after the accident. This shift in sex ratio was associated with high TCDD exposures among the fathers of the children. Similar findings have been reported from Taiwan, Austria and Russia. The few studies of cohorts with background exposure have not reported such findings.

In conclusion, it is probable that the current background exposures to PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE among the Swedish population do not cause severe negative health effects. If negative health effects are induced by the pollutants then they are very difficult to detect in epidemiological studies. In these cases it is probable that other life style and medical factors are more important risk factors. There are, however, still knowledge gaps that make it difficult to draw firm conclusions about if the environmental pollutants cause negative health effects among the general population in Sweden. Data regarding body burdens of PCBs, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE among infants and children are completely lacking. Knowledge about body burdens of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among adults (except for women in child-bearing age) is meager. Animal studies suggest that the reproduction system is one of the most sensitive organ systems to *in utero* dioxin exposure. Epidemiological studies of these outcomes are almost completely lacking. In general, studies of associations between exposures early in life and health outcomes later in life are scarce. Many epidemiological studies have assessed exposure at the same time as the health outcomes, which makes it difficult to draw conclusions about the exposures that the study subjects encountered before the disease manifested itself. There is therefore a great need of

prospective epidemiological studies where the exposures are determined several years before the outbreak of the diseases.

Risk characterization

Animal studies have been used to determine which health effects possibly occur as a result of exposure to PCBs or PCDD/F and at which exposure levels the effects are induced. The following text presents the risk assessments which are the basis for risk characterization of PCBs and PCDD/F. The risk levels used in the risk assessments are: No Observed Adverse Effect Level (NOAEL) which is the highest long-term exposure level giving no negative effects on the most critical health parameter in the most sensitive test animal; Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level (LOAEL), which is the lowest exposure level causing negative effects on the most critical health parameter in the most sensitive test animal; Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI), which is the exposure level which is deemed to be safe for humans, after consideration is taken for uncertainties. Uncertainties are often handled by dividing NOAEL/LOAEL with the uncertainty factors of various sizes, depending on how much is known about the differences between the test animal and humans, and between humans, regarding the kinetics of the compound in question and sensitivity to the compound. If the effect is judged to be very serious, then an additional factor can be added. The larger the uncertainty, the greater the margins are between NOAEL/LOAEL and TDI.

For PCDD/DF, PCB and DDT compounds no thorough review of the animal studies has been conducted in this report. Instead the risk assessments performed by international and national expert groups are summarized. A more detailed review of the studies on PBDE is made since there are no internationally accepted risk assessment.

Two different measures of exposure are used in the comparisons between the Swedish population's exposure levels and NOAEL/LOAEL and TDI, that is, the long-term intake of PCB and PCDD/F from food and levels of compound in body fat (body burden). The exposure data can be found in the chapter entitled "Exposure".

Risk assessments

Dioxins and dioxin-like PCB

Several international expert groups have conducted risk assessments of PCDD/DF and dioxin-like PCBs. These risk assessments show that the foetus is the most sensitive life stage. The tolerable intake determined in the risk assessments are therefore based on animal studies of effects after *in utero* exposure. This TDI can be used for the development of food consumption advisories for girls and women in childbearing years with the aim of limiting the long-term accumulation of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs before pregnancy. There are no international risk assessments of health risks due to exposure after birth, and NFA has therefore, in cooperation with the Institute of Environmental Medicine (IMM) at Karolinska Institutet, conducted such a risk assessment (see below).

Exposure during the foetal stage

WHO's expert group for food additives and contaminants (JECFA) and EU's expert group Scientific Committee on Food (SCF) have conducted a risk assessment of dioxin in food, where exposure during the foetal stage has been identified as the most sensitive period [227-229]. Both expert groups reached the same tolerable intake and SCF's risk assessment is summarized below. In year 2000, SCF determined a provisional tolerable weekly intake (p-TWI) of 7 pg/kg body weight for 2,3,7,8-TCDD. The p-TWI could be applied on all 2,3,7,8-substituted PCDD/DFs and dioxin-like PCBs because WHO's toxicity equivalent system was used [90]. The risk assessment was based in part on a WHO document from 1998 [230], and in part on data which was published after the WHO evaluation. The most sensitive effects which were identified were the effects on the immune system and reproductive development in rats, and effects on CNS functions in Rhesus monkeys, after *in utero* exposure for TCDD [227]. Development of endometriosis in adult Rhesus monkeys was also weighed into the risk assessment results.

In the development of the p-TWI, differences in toxicokinetics between animals and humans were dealt with by calculating the TCDD dose given to the animal and adjusting it to the corresponding body burden of TCDD (amount TCDD per kilo body weight) in the animal. An uncertainty factor of 3x was used in the extrapolation of the body burdens from the animal studies to the human situation, since NOAEL for the most sensitive effects were lacking. An additional uncertainty factor of 3.2x was used to account for possible differences in toxicokinetics within the human population.

With regard to the potential differences in the toxicodynamics between animal and humans, SCF referred to studies of the Ah-receptor which suggests that humans are less sensitive to TCDD than the most sensitive experimental animal strains. Studies of certain biochemical and cellular effects suggest that animals and humans have about the same sensitivity for TCDD. From this, SCF concluded that it could not be excluded that the most sensitive humans are as sensitive for TCDD as the most sensitive experimental animals. Therefore no uncertainty factors were used for extrapolation of potential differences in toxicodynamics between animals and of toxicodynamic differences within the human population [227].

A revision of the risk assessment was made in 2001 and as a result, SCF raised p-TWI to 14 pg/kg body weight/week and took away the prefix "provisional" [228]. Studies of developmental effects after exposure to TCDD during the foetal stage used single doses of TCDD. In the revision of p-TWI the body burden of TCDD that female rats attained after a single dose during pregnancy was extrapolated to match a long-term exposure before and during pregnancy. The studies of the effects of TCDD on CNS development and endometriosis in Rhesus monkeys were not used as a basis for TWI. A new study had shown that the TCDD-exposed animals had higher levels of 1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDF, PCB 77 and PCB 126 than the control animals [228]. In addition, higher levels of TCDD in blood were not associated with an increase risk of endometriosis among the monkeys [228]. The expert group took away the label 'preliminary' since they considered themselves more sure of the new TWI after the toxicokinetics recalculations. The new TWI was based upon effects of TCDD on sperm production and sexual behavior in male rats after exposure during the foetal stage [228]. The same uncertainty factors which were used in previous risk assessment was also used in the revision.

Exposure after birth

The Swedish National Food Administration (NFA) and the Institute for Environmental Medicine (IMM) have conducted a risk assessment of exposure to PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs after birth [231].

The risk assessment was based mainly on the toxicological studies of animals that were exposed to the most toxic dioxin 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-*p*-dioxin (TCDD). In previous risk assessments of TCDD, the exposure has been estimated as a body burden of TCDD (ng TCDD per kilo body weight). By the use of the body burden concept no uncertainty factors for differences in toxicokinetics between animals and humans is needed. NFA's and IMM's risk assessment was based on body burdens of TCDD in fatty tissue (ng TCDD/kg lipid), since it was assumed that the dioxins at low exposure levels are evenly distributed in the lipids of the body's various tissues and organs. Levels in body lipids give a good estimate of the exposure that target organs encounter. In the calculations of TCDD

levels in the body, the amount of body fat was assumed to be 10% in rats and mice and 20% in humans. In addition, the absorption factor for TCDD was assumed to be 80 %, rather than 50 %, which was previously used in the international risk assessments. The assumption of higher absorption and the different amounts of fat in animals and humans is supported by published data [231].

Animal studies of TCDD exposure have clearly shown that the foetal stage is the most sensitive period of development and that the reproductive system is the most sensitive target system at foetal exposure. The most sensitive negative health effects during exposure after birth seems to be the development of cancer. After rats of both sexes were exposed during two years (life-time exposure) the highest TCDD levels in the body which did not cause cancer development was estimated to range between 540-2000 ng/kg fat. TCDD is not genotoxic and it can therefore be expected that there is no cancer risk at exposure below a certain threshold [231].

Benchmarking models were used to estimate the exposure level which causes an increase in incidence of cancer by 5 % in relationship to the background incidences in animal experiments (Benchmark dose, BMD). The lower 95% confidence interval limit was calculated on BMD (BMDL) and BMDL was then utilized in the development of a tolerable intake. From the cancer studies in rats the BMDL05 was estimated to 1500 ng TCDD/kg fat which is comparable to an average daily intake of TCDD of 95 pg/kg body weight in humans [231].

Since the risk assessment was based on animal studies, it was necessary to extrapolate the results to a safe exposure level in humans. Normally, uncertainty factors are used to compensate for potential differences in dioxin kinetics and dynamics (sensitivity) between animals and humans, as well as between different human individuals. NFA's and IMM's expert group presented three different TDI scenarios using these uncertainty factors. In the first scenario (scenario 1) the extrapolation model used was that which EU's and WHO's expert groups have used. These two expert groups came to the conclusion that humans are not more sensitive for dioxins than experimental animals are and therefore used no uncertainty factors for toxicodynamic differences between animal species and humans, or for individual differences between humans. In scenario 1 the NFA and IMM expert group used only the uncertainty factor (3.2x) for differences in toxicokinetics between different humans, similarly as EU's and WHO's expert groups. The uncertainty factor was used because the half-life for TCDD in the body varies between different human individuals. Scenario 1 resulted in a tolerable body burden of TCDD in humans of 500 ng/kg fat, which is comparable with a daily intake of 30 pg/kg body weight/day [231].

It was however regarded necessary to use an additional uncertainty factor in order to take consideration to possible differences in toxicodynamics in the human population (3.2x). Both mechanistic and epidemiological studies have suggested there are great variations in sensitivity within the human population. In the epidemiological studies it is difficult to discern differences in sensitivity due to the variation in toxicokinetics or toxicodynamics. Extrapolation in scenario 2, including uncertainty factors which accounted for differences in toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics among humans, resulted in a tolerable body burden level of 150 ng TCDD/kg body weight, which is comparable to a daily intake of 10 pg/kg body weight and day [231].

In scenario 3 an additional uncertainty factor (5x) was used since cancer is a serious and often life-threatening effect. An extra safety margin for the BMDL05 was also motivated because BMDL05 is an exposure level which entails a significant 5% increase of cancer above background in animals, which can be regarded as unacceptable from a health perspective. Scenario 3 gave a tolerable level in fat of 30 ng TCDD/kg fat, which corresponds to a daily intake of 2 pg/kg body weight.

The expert group from NFA and IMM concluded that the TCDD risk assessment can also be used for other PCDD/DF and dioxin-like PCBs if WHO's system for toxic equivalents factors (TEF) for these compounds is used when calculating the total exposure of toxic equivalents (TEQ). Furthermore, it was concluded that the current knowledge about dioxin-induced cancer among humans shows that the risk for cancer in humans is probably very small or non-existent at long-term exposure levels comparable to those calculated in scenario 2 (10 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day) and scenario 3 (2 pg TEQ/kg body weight and day).

Non-dioxin-like PCBs

PCBs are complex mixtures of chlorinated biphenyls with different toxic traits. A group of PCBs has the ability to bind to Ah receptors in the cell and thereby cause dioxin-like effects; they are therefore called dioxin-like PCBs. Another group of PCBs is toxic by way of other mechanisms and are called non-dioxin-like PCBs. The most common indicator congeners for non-dioxin-like PCBs are PCB 28, PCB 52, PCB 101, PCB 138, PCB 153 and PCB 180. These congeners represent about 50 % of the total levels of dioxin-like and non-dioxin-like PCBs in food.

The European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) conducted a risk assessment of non-dioxin-like PCBs in the year 2005 [111]. This risk assessment was difficult in that there is no toxicity equivalent system for non-dioxin-like PCBs, like the one that exists for PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs. In addition, the PCB congener patterns differ between foodstuffs [111]. Another problem with the risk assessment is that many animal experiments have been conducted on technical PCB mixtures that

contain dioxin-like and non-dioxin-like PCBs. In the epidemiological studies of occupationally-exposed groups and groups with background exposure it is also difficult to discern between exposure for dioxin-like and non-dioxin-like PCBs [111]. EFSA's scientific panel for contaminants (CONTAM) concluded that the risk assessment must be based on animal experiments where rodents have been exposed to non-dioxin-like PCBs.

Liver and thyroid toxicity were the most sensitive effects of the non-dioxin-like PCBs in animal experiments [111]. In 90-day studies of PCB 28, PCB 128 and PCB 153 in rats, it was estimated that the highest doses which did not give negative effects in the most sensitive animal species (NOAEL) were 30-40 µg/kg body weight/day. These NOAELs were estimated to be comparable to a body burden of non-dioxin-like PCB congeners PCB 28, PCB 128 and PCB 153 of 400, 800 and 1200 µg/kg body weight, respectively [111]. In order to be able to compare these NOAEL body burdens with those which has been measured in the European population, the CONTAM panel made the assumption that the effects of PCB 28, PCB 128 and PCB 153 also were representative for the mixtures of non-dioxin-like PCBs found in humans. Since the lowest doses which caused negative effects on the liver and thyroid (LOAELs) are about ten times higher than the NOAELs, an assumption was made that a body burden of non-dioxin-like PCBs of 500 µg/kg was a conservative estimation of a NOAEL body burden [111].

Based on the median level of non-dioxin-like PCBs in European mother's milk of about 240 µg/kg fat, the CONTAM panel calculated a median body burden of 50 µg/kg (based on a fat content of 20% in the body). This body burden is only ten times lower than the NOAEL body burden [111]. The CONTAM panel pointed out the problem that even the single PCB congeners, which was used in the animal experiments, could have been contaminated with dioxin-like compounds. This makes it difficult to draw conclusions about how much of the observed effects were caused by non-dioxin-like PCBs [111].

The CONTAM panel concluded that it was not possible to determine a health-based tolerable intake of non-dioxin-like PCBs for humans since it was not possible to discern between the effects of non-dioxin-like PCBs from possible effects of dioxin-like PCBs [111]. The data regarding the effects of single non-dioxin-like PCBs was judged to be limited. The panel closed by remarking that there are indication of small but measurable effects on children's development caused by non-dioxin-like PCBs and PCDD/F/dioxin-like PCBs, either separately or together, after exposure during the foetal stage. These exposures are only slightly higher than the exposures which are expected to occur at the average intake of PCB, within human populations in Europe [111]. Certain population groups and individuals have intake levels which are clearly higher and it is therefore important to continue the efforts to lower the levels of non-dioxin-like PCBs in food [111].

DDT

FAO/WHO's expert group for pesticide residuals in food (JMPR) revised the provisional tolerable daily intake for DDT compounds in the year 2000 to 10 µg/kg body weight/day [232]. This pTDI was based on a NOAEL from studies of reproduction on rats and an uncertainty factor of 100 was used.

HCB

JMPR has not reached a conclusion on a TDI for HCB due to lack of data.

Brominated flame retardants (BFR)

PBDE

There are a few review articles on PBDE, of which some contain sections on toxicity and human exposure [34, 233-237]. Effects which have been observed at the lowest doses of PBDE are changes in liver morphology, foetal toxicity/teratogenicity in the offspring, disruptions in the thyroid hormone balance as well as behavioral toxicity after neonatal exposure [34]. Of these effects, neurotoxicity was observed at the lowest given dose (0.6-0.8 mg BDE 99/kg body weight) [238 and 239]. The lower brominated PBDE mixtures generally give a greater biological activity than the higher brominated, which leads to the following order of toxic potency: PentaBDE>OctaBDE>DecaBDE.

Recent studies have increased our knowledge on the toxicity of PBDEs. In a number of articles by Kuriyama, Chahoud and colleagues, new effects have been attributed to PBDE. Reproduction parameters (for example sperm production) in offspring to rats, which were exposed during pregnancy to the PBDE congener BDE-99 (60 or 300 µg), were influenced in male offspring at low doses [240]. Effects were also seen on motor activity [241] and on thyroid hormone levels [242]. In the female offspring, the same low dose (single dose of 60 µg/kg body weight to mothers during pregnancy) affected ovarian morphology when determined on post-natal day 90 (PND 90) [243]. The indications of negative effects on male fertility and on neurotoxicity were strengthened later in peer-reviewed articles [244, 245]. Effects on experimental animals were also observed after exposure to BDE-47. Effects on behavior and on thyroid hormone levels could be seen in offspring to rats which were exposed to single doses of BDE-47 during pregnancy (0.7 mg/kg body weight; gestational day 6) [246, 247]; this exposure also gave effects on the thyroid hormone levels in the mother (post-natal day 1 and 22) [248].

In studies by Lilienthal and colleagues, pregnant rats were exposed to BDE-99 during GD 10-18 (1 or 10 mg/kg body weight/day) and thereafter certain

parameters which mirror sexual development (sex hormones, development of reproductive organs) were investigated in the offspring [249]. In general, effects were observed at higher doses (10 mg/kg) but in some cases even at doses as low as 1 mg/kg. The same research group also studied neurotoxic parameters in the offspring after gestational exposure and observed certain effects at a dose of 10 mg/kg body weight.

In conclusion, the new PBDE studies show effects on markers of the development of sex functions. The findings in these studies support previously observed effects, for example neurotoxicity and thyroid hormone changes. In addition, the new studies show that the effects can be observed at lower doses than those which were previously reported. It should however be noted that certain of the above-mentioned references have not been published as complete articles and therefore have not gone through the peer-review process.

HBCD

Hexabromocyclododecane (HBCD) is used commercially in different areas where flame retardant materials are necessary. HBCD consists of several different congeners, of which the alfa, beta and gamma forms are the most common. Currently no differences in toxicity between the different forms have been shown. HBCD has been found in environmental samples and also in animals in the food production. Newer intake calculations have suggested an intake of 10 ng HBCD/day) [37].

In a study on rats (28 and 90 day toxicity studies) the liver was identified as a target organ and the effects included increased liver weight and morphological changes [251-254]. In the 90-day study these effects became apparent at 100 mg/kg body weight, and at the same dose the effects were also seen on the thyroid. In a 28-day reproduction study on rats, effects were seen on the mother at 750 mg/kg body weight (reduced food intake) whereas no foetal toxicity or teratogenicity could be seen at this dose [253].

The carcinogenic potential of HBCD was examined in mice (18-month study) [255] exposed to 13, 130 and 1300 mg HBCD/kg body weight. Certain effects were observed in the liver (liver nodules, necrosis, fat infiltration, foci and hepatocellular tumors), most clearly observed in the group that was exposed to 130 mg/kg body weight. Lack of a dose-effect relationship, lack of effects in female mice, and use of the mouse strain B6C3F1 (a strain that is sensitive for the development of neoplastic liver changes) make this study questionable. If carcinogenic effects exist at all, the lack of mutagenic effects shows that epigenetic factors more likely lie behind HBCD's increase in tumor incidences.

In studies of the neuromotor development, HBCD gave certain effects on the spontaneous behavior at 0.9 mg/kg body weight (neonatal exposure, effects observed 3 months after birth) [256]. This effect was more pronounced at a higher HBCD dose (13.5 mg/kg body weight). HBCD also has an influence on the thyroid function of rats, which was studied by van den Ven and colleagues [257]. The lowest dose which, with statistical significance, could be coupled to the effects on thyroid weight was 1.6 mg/kg body weight, based on a 10 % increase in organ weight. HBCD also affected the auditory functions in the brain stem (brain stem auditory evoked potentials, BAEP) in male rats. The benchmark dose for BAEP was 0.2-0.9 mg/kg body weight in the most sensitive cases [258]. The same authors also investigated the HBCD effects on the movement patterns in rats. In the female rats, the cataleptic effects (rigid and slow movements) could be seen at a dose under 1 mg/kg body weight, whereas male rats were affected at a somewhat higher dose (3 mg/kg body weight).

TBBPA

Tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA) is globally used in large volumes as a flame retardant. Because of its low persistence in biological systems, TBBPA is regarded to have low toxic potential. In a few studies TBBPA has been found in measurable concentrations in wild animals, although at lower levels than HBCD [259, 260]. To our knowledge there are no intake calculations conducted on TBBPA intake in humans.

According to an earlier review by Darnerud [34], the toxicity of TBBPA in experimental animals is assumed to be low. Besides some slight kidney changes in rats (at 250 mg/kg) [261], the effects were seen only at doses higher than 1 g/kg. Recently, however, studies report kidney toxicity when TBBPA was given to newly born rats (200 and 600 mg/kg body weight), while no kidney toxicity could be observed when older rats were exposed (up to 6000 mg/kg body weight) [262]. In this study there were also references to other studies in which no effects could be observed when young rats, as well as offspring to pregnant rats, were exposed to TBBPA (up to 3 000 mg/kg body weight) [262]. Other studies report estrogenic effects of TBBPA on the uterus/body weight ratio in ovary-ectomized mice (dose 20 mg/kg body weight for three days) [263]. *In vitro* studies of TBBPA's estrogenic potential suggest that this substance is an agonist to estrogen and estrogen receptors [264], which also strengthens the previously mentioned *in vivo* findings. Studies of neurotoxic effects on auditory functions report that the offspring to Wistar rats, exposed pre-natally and post-natally to TBBPA, showed changes of the BAEP threshold value (BMDL 0.9 mg/kg body weight) and also the BAEP latency times at somewhat higher doses (7-8 mg/kg body weight) [265].

Conclusions - BFR

Knowledge about levels and effects of BFR is continually improving, and harmful effects have now been observed in experimental animals at doses that are significantly lower than previously reported. LOAEL, NOEL or BMDL at doses under 1 mg/kg body weight have currently been described for each of the four BFR groups named above. Effects for the higher brominated PBDE mixtures (octaBDE and decaBDE) or comparable congeners are, however, first seen at higher doses. With regard to the newly conducted studies of PBDE, HBCD and TBBPA, the critical effects were observed during early development and consist of effects on neuro-motor functions, hormone levels, as well as reproductive-organ morphology and function. These effects can partly be integrated since disruptions in hormone levels can affect development within many areas, for example neuro-motor functions. A limitation of our assessment of the data is that a number of the documents considered to be critical for the conclusions are abstracts and other short presentations which have not yet gone through the peer-review process.

The critical toxicity studies on BFR in experimental animals mentioned above, are summarized in Tabell 23.

Table 23. Critical effects of brominated flame retardants in experimental animal models.

Substance	Critical dose	Species	Effect	Reference
BDE-99 (PBDE)	60 µg/kg pregnant females (LOAEL)	Rat	Male reproduction, motor activity	[245]
BDE-99 (PBDE)	0.6-0.8 mg/kg neonates (LOAEL)	Mouse	Neurotoxicity	[238, 239]
BDE-47 (PBDE)	0.7 mg/kg pregnant females (LOAEL)	Rat	Neurotoxicity	[246]
HBCD	0.9 mg/kg neonates (LOAEL)	Mouse	Neurotoxicity	[256]
HBCD	0.2-0.9 mg/kg – BMDL	Rat	Auditory nerve function (BAEP)	[258]
HBCD	1.6 mg/kg – BMDL	Rat	Thyroid weight	[257]
TBBPA	0.9 mg/kg – BMDL	Rat	Auditory nerve function (BAEP)	[265]

Interaction effects between PCB and MeHg

A number of studies have shown different effects of organic environmental pollutants and methyl mercury in both humans and animals. A simultaneous exposure of halogenated environmental pollutants and MeHg is very likely since these compounds often exist together, especially in fish. Many persistent halogenated organic pollutants, as well as MeHg, can cause neurotoxic effects in

humans and animals at high exposure. Both organic pollutants and MeHg can easily pass the placenta and blood-brain barrier and many of the organic compounds can also be found in mother's milk. Humans and animals have proven to be sensitive for exposure to persistent halogenated environmental compounds and MeHg during foetal development and in early infancy.

Some epidemiological studies of co-exposure have been conducted, but it is very difficult to reach unambiguous conclusions. Several studies have been conducted on children from the Faroe Islands. The population on the Faroe Islands consumes whale meat and whale fat which contain high levels of methyl mercury and PCBs. Among children to mothers on the Faroe Islands, which were exposed during pregnancy, behavioural changes have been observed in the form of memory disorders, concentration disorders, as well as problems with motor functions and visual-spatial function [266, 267]. A study from 2001 concluded that the effects are most likely related to MeHg exposure, but the simultaneous PCB exposure could have increased the effect of MeHg [266, 267].

A study by Stewart *et al.* also suggests that there is an interaction effect between PCB and MeHg. In the study, children which were participants in the Oswego-study in the USA [108, 268] were examined. Although the results are difficult to interpret, they indicate that high exposure to PCB enhance the behavioural effects caused by MeHg at 38 months of age [269].

PCB and MeHg have shown to cause behavioural disruptions in several animal studies (for review see [270]). A number of animal studies have been conducted to study potential interactions effects between PCB and MeHg. In a study by Tanimura *et al* [271], female mice were exposed to Kanechlor 500 (commercial mixture of PCB) as well as to MeHg (0.4 or 4 mg/kg) during gestation and the postnatal period. The offspring were then tested in several behaviour tests. The results were somewhat ambiguous. Behavioural disruptions were sometimes associated with PCB and sometimes with MeHg, but in a few of the tests the combination of PCB and MeHg exposure caused behavioural changes (hind-limb dysfunction and visual placement task) [271].

Roegge *et al.* studied the interaction effects between PCB and MeHg in female rats. Female rats were exposed to Aroclor 1254 (6 mg/kg and day) and to MeHg (0.5 ppm in drinking water) starting four weeks before mating until postnatal day 16 (PND 16). Offspring were tested PND 60 using three tests which involve cerebellar functions. In one of these tests (rotating rod) an additive effect on behaviour was discovered even though the substances separately had no effect. [272].

Fischer *et al.* reported behavioural changes in adult male mice which were neonatally exposed to PCB 126 or PCB 153 and MeHg during the sensitive period

of brain development. Combination exposure to PCB 153 (0.5 mg/kg body weight) and MeHg (0.4 mg/kg body weight) proved to have a ten-fold greater effect on behaviour than exposure for a high dose of MeHg (4.0 mg/kg body weight), which is known to cause behavioural disruptions. Exposure to PCB 153 (0.5 mg/kg body weight) or to MeHg (0.4 mg/kg body weight) alone had no effect on behaviour. Exposure to PCB 126 (0.46 mg/kg body weight) and MeHg (4.0 mg/kg body weight) also caused a significantly greater effect on behaviour than the compounds separately [273]. In the same study, interactive effects between PBDE 99 and MeHg were investigated. Neonatal male mice were exposed to PBDE 99 (0.8 mg/kg body weight) as well as to MeHg (0.4 mg/kg body weight) during the sensitive period of brain development. Tests on adult animals that were simultaneously exposed showed strong behavioural disruptions whereas animals exposed to a single compound showed no disruptions [273].

In vitro studies have shown that PCB and MeHg can have additive or synergistic effects on the nervous system. Bemis and Seegal [274] exposed striatum cells to PCB (Aroclor 1254 and 1260), to MeHg or to a combination of these. They found that PCB reduced dopamine secretion, which did not occur at exposure to MeHg alone. At simultaneous exposures to PCB and MeHg, the secretion of dopamine was reduced more than at exposure to PCB alone, indicating a synergistic effect [274]. In another study, Bemis and Seegal found that low concentrations of PCB and MeHg synergistically increased intra-cellular calcium levels. Higher concentrations and/or a lower exposure time, however, resulted in a reduction of intra-cellular calcium. Both of these effects are thought to depend upon the interactions between PCB and MeHg with the ryanodine receptor [275].

Other research groups have also seen *in vitro* effects at simultaneous PCB and MeHg exposure. Johansson *et al.* exposed an AtT20 pituitary gland cell line for PCB 126, PCB153 and MeHg. The study showed that the cells went through necrotic and apoptotic cell death after exposure to PCB and MeHg. Effects were additive for the combination of PCB 153 and MeHg and were weakly synergistic for the combination of PCB 126 and MeHg [276].

In conclusion, simultaneous human exposure for persistent halogenated organic environmental contaminants and MeHg occur via fish consumption. Various epidemiological studies have revealed behavioural changes in children which were exposed to these compounds during the foetal stage and emphasize the possibility of interactive effects of PCB and MeHg. In the same manner, a number of animal studies and *in vitro* tests show interactive effects between different halogenated environmental pollutants and MeHg.

Conclusions- risk assessments

Swedish consumers are exposed to a highly complex mixture of persistent halogenated organic pollutants in food. The currently available risk assessments have not determined the risks of health effects caused by the complex mixture as a whole, but have assessed single substance groups separately.

Risk assessments of PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs have shown that reproduction effects are the most sensitive negative health effect in animal exposed during the foetal stage. Studies of young and adult animals showed that cancer effects are the most sensitive end-points after exposure during these life stages. Other identified sensitive effects are immunotoxicity after exposure during the pre- and post-natal stages, as well as in adult animals, and neurotoxic effects after pre-natal exposure.

Epidemiological studies suggest neurotoxicity may occur in children after background exposure to PCDD/DF and PCB during the foetal stage. In addition PCB, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE are suspected to influence the development of immune-system related diseases (for example asthma and allergies), based on a few epidemiological studies conducted on children.

Risk assessments of toxic compounds use uncertainty factors in order to account for uncertainties when extrapolating safe exposure levels from animals to humans. These factors may also be used to account for differences in sensitivity within the human population. In the risk assessment of non-developmental exposure to dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, uncertainty factors for differences in toxicokinetics (3.2x) and toxicodynamics (3.2x) among humans were used when results from cancer studies in animals were used to determine a TDI. This was based upon epidemiological studies that indicate large differences in sensitivity for TCDD among humans. Moreover, it is not possible to discern if these differences are due to variation in toxicokinetics and/or toxicodynamics. With the use of these uncertainty factors TDI was estimated to 10 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. An additional uncertainty factor of 5x was added because cancer is a serious health effect, resulting in a TDI of 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. In the TDI interval of 2-10 pg TEQ/kg/day, cancer risks were regarded as very low or non-existing.

When extrapolating results from animal studies, EU's and WHO's risk assessment of foetal exposure to dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs only used an uncertainty factor for differences in toxicokinetics between humans (3.2x), together with a factor of 3x for the use of a LOAEL [114, 228]. The margin between the estimated intake at LOAEL and the estimated TDI was therefore only 9.6-fold, resulting in a TDI of 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day.

There are great uncertainties with regard to the safe levels of human exposure to non-dioxin-like PCBs. No internationally accepted risk assessment has been able

to determined tolerable intake levels for these types of compounds due to the lack of high-quality data. Many of the non-dioxin-like PCBs used in animal studies are suspected to be contaminated with dioxin-like compounds. The epidemiological studies which have investigated the associations between PCB exposure and health effects have problems in that there may be strong correlations between body burdens of non-dioxin-like PCBs, dioxin-like PCBs and PCDD/Fs in human populations with background levels of exposure.

Intakes of PCDD/F/PCB TEQs in Sweden and TDI

Girls and women in child-bearing age – exposure of the foetus

Riksmaten - barn 2003: girls

The body burden of PCDD/Fs and PCBs during pregnancy depends on the exposure during a long time period before pregnancy. This is due to the long half-life of the compounds in the body. Therefore, the exposure of women during their childhood gives a contribution to the body burden of the compounds at pregnancy. The most recent intake estimation of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among children was performed in 2006 [38] and a population-based food consumption survey was the source of data for the food consumption habits among the children (Riksmaten – barn 2003) [35]. The intake calculations included children from three age groups (4, 8-9 and 11-12 years). As described in the chapter "Exposure", Swedish children have somewhat higher PCB and PCDD/F intakes than adults. This is mainly due to the higher food consumption per kilo body weight among children. Younger children also have higher food consumption per kilo body weight than older children.

The tolerable intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, established by the EU-SCF in 2001, is an estimation of the safe average life-long intake level before pregnancy. This intake will result in a body burden among pregnant women that is regarded as safe for the foetus. A comparison between the tolerable daily intake (TDI, 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day) and the estimated intakes among Swedish girls shows that 65 % of the girls in the youngest age group (4 years old) had higher intakes than the TDI, 39 % among the 8-9 year olds, and 13 % among the 11-12 year olds. Five percent of the girls in the whole study group had intakes over 4 pg TEQ/kg body weight/ day.

Women less than 41 years old -Riksmaten 1997-98

The population-based food consumption survey for adults in Sweden, Riksmaten - 1997-98, was used in the intake calculations for women of child-bearing age (<41 years old). The intakes were compared with the EU-SCF TDI which results in safe body burdens among pregnant women. The intake calculations from 2005 [41] resulted in a median intake level of 0.93 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day, which is less than half of the TDI of 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. The intake at the 95th percentile was determined to 2.0 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day, which means that 5 % of the women of child-bearing age had intakes equal to or higher than the TDI (Table 24). Of these women 69 % did not follow the current consumption advice regarding dioxin- and PCB-contaminated fatty fish from the Baltic Sea region (Table 24). The women that followed the fish consumption advisory but nonetheless had a higher intake than the TDI, had a relatively high consumption of fish in general and of dairy products [41].

Table 24. Total TEQ intake among Swedish women in comparison with the tolerable intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, and in relation to the fish consumption advisory regarding dioxin and PCB-contaminated fish (not more than once per month).

	Women ≤ 40 years
All consumers (N)	271
Total TEQ intake > TDI	4.8 % (13/271)
Consumption > advisory	3.3 % (9/271)
>TDI and > advisory	69 % (9/13)
> TDI and < advisory	31 % (4/13)

Pregnant women

The median intake of PCDD/F and dioxin-like PCBs among primiparous pregnant women from Uppsala, who were recruited between 1996 and 1999, was estimated to 0.9 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day [43]. This is less than half of the EU-SCF TDI (2 pg TEQ/kg/day) [228]. Among the Uppsala women the intake for the 95th percentile was at the same level as the TDI, i.e. 5% of the women had intakes equal to or higher than the TDI (Fig. 16) [43].

Figure 16. Daily intake of PCDD/DF/PCB TEQ among primiparous women from Uppsala County 1996-99 (N=235).

Among the primiparous women from Uppsala that had higher intakes than the TDI 60 % reported that they consumed fatty fish from the Baltic Sea region more than once a month [43]. This shows that women who consume more contaminated fish than advised have a high risk of exceeding the TDI. Other women that exceeded the TDI often reported a high consumption of fatty fish from areas other than the Baltic region (10-29 g/day) [43]. Only two of the 235 study participants had intakes over TDI when the contribution of the fatty fish was excluded from the intake calculations. None of the participants had intakes over the TDI when only intakes from foods other than fish were included in the calculations [43].

The median intake of *p,p'*-DDE (3,1 ng/kg/day) among the primiparous women from Uppsala [43] was at the same level as the median intake among women in the age group 17-40 years in Riksmaten [250]. WHO has determined a provisional TDI (pTDI) for DDT compounds to 10 µg/kg body weight/day, based on developmental effects on male rats exposed *in utero* [277]. A comparison between the estimated intakes of *p,p'*-DDE among women of child-bearing age in Sweden and the pTDI shows that all women had intakes well below the pTDI [43].

Conclusions-exposure of the foetus

Among girls in the ages 4-8 years, intakes of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are somewhat higher than among older girls and women, and these young girls exceed the TDI to a higher degree. The consequences of this slightly higher intake during early childhood for the long-term accumulation of dioxins and dioxin-like

PCBs among the girls is unknown. Knowledge about the body burdens of the compounds among children and adolescents in Sweden is completely lacking. It is, however, likely that the higher intake among young girls to some extent is compensated by the rapid increase in body weight and length that occurs during childhood. This will result in a dilution of the higher intakes during early childhood.

A long-term intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs at or below the TDI among girls and women in child-bearing age results in a body burden of the compounds during pregnancy that is regarded as safe for the foetus. The majority of the population of adolescents and women of child-bearing age in Sweden have intake levels that are below the SCF-EU TDI for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs. A few percent of the population have an estimated intake that is above the TDI. In the food consumption survey Riksmaten 1997-98, women in childbearing age with intakes above the TDI in many cases reported a consumption of contaminated fatty fish from the Baltic Sea region over the advised maximum consumption issued by the Swedish NFA (once a month).

Children and adults - exposure after birth

The risk assessment of the exposure to PCDD/F and dioxin-like PCBs after birth showed that cancer is the negative health effect that occurs at the lowest exposure levels in animal studies (rat) [231]. A TDI interval of 2-10 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day was established as an intake interval that results in very small or no cancer risks [231].

Children: Riksmaten - 2003 barn

The median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs was estimated to 1.7 pg/kg body weight/day among children in ages 4-12 years, which is lower than the intake levels in the TDI interval (2-10 pg/kg/day) [231] (Fig. 17). Children on the higher end of the intake distribution (95th percentile) had intakes that were twice as high as the median, but the intakes were nevertheless in the lower range of the TDI-interval.

Figure 17. Intake of PCDD/DF/PCB TEQ in different populations in Sweden in comparison with TDI for cancer effects obtained by using two different extrapolation methods from results in animal studies. BMDL05 represents the estimated lowest intake that causes an increase in cancer risk of 5% above a background cancer risk among rats [231]. BMDL05/10 is a tolerable daily intake extrapolated from the BMDL05 by the use of an uncertainty factor of 10x. The uncertainty factor takes into account uncertainties about differences in sensitivity (toxicokinetics and -dynamics) among humans. BMDL05/50 represents the TDI after further addition of a uncertainty factor taking into account that cancer is a very serious health effect (50-fold margin to the BMDL05) [231]. **A:** Children of ages 4-12 years from Riksmaten - barn 2003 (median and 95th percentile). **B:** Women from Riksmaten 1997-98 in the ages ≤ 40 years (median and 95th percentile). **C:** Women from Riksmaten of ages >40 years (median and 95th percentile). **D:** Women from fishermen families living on the east coast of Sweden and born before 1930 (mean intake). **E:** Women from fishermen families living on the east coast of Sweden and born 1950 and later (mean intake). **F:** Women with high consumption of fatty fish from Lake Vättern (mean and maximum intake). **G:** Men of the ages 17 to 75 years from Riksmaten (median and 95th percentile). **H:** Commercial fishermen with high consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish (mean and maximum intake).

Men - Riksmaten 1997-98

The median intake of PCDD/F and dioxin-like PCB among men of ages 17-75 years in Riksmaten was estimated to 1 pg/kg body weight/day [41] which is half of the lowest intake level in the TDI range 2-10 pg/kg body weight/day for cancer [231] (Fig. 17). Men in Riksmaten with an intake at the higher end of the distribution (95th percentile, 2.7 pg TEQ/kg/day) had intake levels only slightly above the lowest intake in the TDI interval. Only nine men of 347 had intakes over 2 pg TEQ/kg/day if the intakes of PCDD/F and dioxin-like PCBs from fatty fish from the Baltic Sea region were excluded in the intake calculation. No man exceeded an intake of 2 pg TEQ/kg/day if intake from fish were excluded from

the intake calculation. If the individual consumption of dairy products, meat and meat products, fats and oils, and eggs and egg products was doubled (intake from fish still excluded), the intake of 2 pg TEQ/kg/day was only exceeded by seven men. This shows that high intakes of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are unlikely among extreme consumer of dairy products, meat and meat products, fats and oils and eggs and egg products (if they do not eat fish).

Women – Riksmaten 1997-98

Women of ages less than 41 years had a median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs that was half of the lowest intake in the TDI range for cancer (2-10 pg/kg/day) [231] (Fig. 17). Women with a high intake (95th percentile) had intakes at the lower end of the TDI range. Among women over 40 years of age the median intake (1.2 pg/kg/day) was lower than the intakes in the TDI range (Fig. 17). At the 95th percentile the intake was in the lower end of TDI range (3.5 pg/kg/day).

High consumers

Fishermen from the Swedish east coast were estimated to have a mean intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs of 7 pg/kg/day, which is seven-fold higher than the median intake among men in Riksmaten 1997-98 [41]. The mean intake among the fishermen was in the higher range of the TDI interval for cancer (2-10 pg/kg/day) [231] (Fig. 17).

If the highest reported consumption of fatty Baltic Sea fish (58 portions per month) is used in the intake calculation for fishermen [45], the total intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs would be approximately 36 pg/kg/day (Fig. 17). This is about 4-fold higher than the highest intake level of the TDI range for cancer, and this extreme intake is close to the lowest intake estimated to increase the cancer risk with 5 % above background in rats (Fig. 17) [231].

In a study of wives of the Swedish fishermen living on the Swedish east coast the fish consumption was studied among 100 randomly recruited study participants [46]. The oldest women born before 1930 reported that they ate fatty Baltic Sea fish on average five times per month and lean fish six times per month. In total this consumption results in an intake of approximately 4 pg/kg/day which is in the lower range of the TDI interval for cancer (Fig.17) [231]. The youngest women born after 1949 ate fatty Baltic Sea fish on average twice per month and lean fish three times per month [46], resulting in an intake of 2 pg/kg/day (Fig. 17).

A median consumption of fatty fish from Lake Vättern (Arctic charr, brown trout and salmon) of three times per month (min-max 0-12 times per month) was reported by female Lake Vättern fish consumers [47]. This consumption rate

resulted in an estimated total intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs of 2.5 pg TEQ/kg/day, which is on the lower end of the TDI range for cancer of 2-10 pg TEQ/kg/day (Fig. 17) [231]. A consumption of 12 portions of fatty Lake Vättern fish per month would result in an estimated total intake in the upper range of the TDI interval (7.5 pg TEQ/kg/day) [231].

Conclusions – exposure after birth

It is currently not possible to draw firm conclusions about possible cancer risks caused by dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among high consumers of fatty fish from the Baltic Sea region. In the risk assessment of exposure to the compound groups after birth it was concluded that a long-term intake of 2-10 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day most probably causes very small or non-existing cancer risks [231].

The current state of knowledge strongly suggests that the intake levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among the general Swedish population in most cases are on the safe side in comparison with estimated intake levels causing increased cancer risks. Individuals with extremely high consumption (daily) of fatty fish with high concentrations of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs may reach intake levels that are above the intakes that can be regarded as safe. In these cases the intake levels are close to those estimated to cause increased cancer risks in animals.

Intakes of BFRs in Sweden and TDI

The health risks caused by BFRs have been investigated in animal studies using one substance or substance group at a time. Currently there is little knowledge about interactions between different BFRs, and no study has tried to reach a conclusion about the total toxicity of the BFRs present in food. In order to get a better picture of the health risks caused by BFRs, the mechanisms behind BFR toxicity need to be elucidated.

The estimated mean intake of PBDEs in Sweden today is approximately 50 ng/day [37, 278], which corresponds to an intake of about 0.7 ng/kg body weight/day. If this intake level is compared with the lowest intake connected with negative health effects in animals (LOAEL, BMDL) a difference of approximately 100 000 is apparent for PBDE. For HBCD, the difference between current mean intake in Sweden and risk intakes is even larger (approximately 1 000 000), based on preliminary data. The difference for TBBPA can not be estimated at all since there is a lack of intake data. If instead, the body burden is used in the comparison between the current Swedish situation and risk levels, then

the suggested differences will be significantly reduced. It is probable that the body burdens of BFR observed in Sweden is a result of exposure from several sources other than food. This leads to smaller differences than if food is the only source of exposure. It is likely that new toxicological data in the future will further reduce these differences between exposure levels in Sweden and levels at which toxic effects are observed in animals.

Intakes of PCDD/F/PCB TEQs and TDI - consumption scenarios

In order to estimate how exposure to dioxins and PCBs change with various food consumptions patterns, theoretical intake calculations were made. Results from food surveys in Riksmaten 1997-98 were used to produce different consumption scenarios. In Riksmaten 1997-98, girls and women between the ages of 17-40 years had a median intake of 0.9 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day and an extreme intake of 2.0 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day (95th percentile). Approximately 5 % of the young women had an intake which exceeded EU's TDI (2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day).

In the scenarios different fish consumption patterns were assumed (Table 25). If the Riksmaten participant's own fish consumption was too small to completely match the assumed consumption, then the residual assumed fish consumption was added to the individual's food consumption at the expense of meat and poultry consumption.

The PCDD/F and dioxin-like PCB TEQ concentrations in fish were assumed to be 0.5 pg TEQ/g fresh weight for lean freshwater and marine fish, 2 pg TEQ/g fresh weight for fatty fish with low contamination level, for instance farmed salmon, and 10 pg TEQ/g fresh weight for fatty fish with a high contamination level.

Scenario 1: Avoid contaminated fatty fish and eat other types of fatty fish with low contamination levels instead: If women between the ages of 17 and 40 have the same fish consumption as in the food consumption survey but exchange the consumption of fatty contaminated fish with the same amount of fatty fish with a low contamination level (for example farmed salmon) then the median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs declines slightly. This is due to the fact that the women generally eat very small amounts of contaminated fish. About 2% exceed the TDI for women in childbearing age of 2 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day (Table 25).

Scenario 2: Avoid contaminated fish and eat meat (beef and poultry) instead: If the young women exchange all of their consumption of contaminated Baltic Sea fish with consumption of meat, then no great change in the intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs would occur. This is due to the above-mentioned fact that the younger women consume such small amounts of contaminated Baltic Sea fish. Only 0.7 % of all women will exceed the TDI (Table 25).

Scenario 3: Contaminated fish once a month: If the women instead increase their consumption of contaminated fatty fish to once a month at the expense of consumption of lean fish and fatty fish with low contamination levels, then the median intake is increased to 1.6 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. In this case 17 % of the women will exceed TDI.

Scenario 4: Fish 3 times a week whereof one meal of farmed salmon: The assumption is that the women follow the NFA's general fish consumption advisory with regard to fish; that is to say they eat fish three times a week whereof one is a portion of fatty fish. If this consumption occurs at the expense of consumption of contaminated fatty fish and meat and poultry, and the fatty fish consumption consists of fish with a relatively low contaminations level, then the median intake will be 1.4 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day. Approximately 4 % of women in this case will be above EU's TDI (Table 25).

Scenario 5a 5b and 5c: Fish 3 times a week whereof one meal is fatty fish, consisting of contaminated fish once a month and farmed salmon three times per month: Scenario 5a is the same as Scenario 4, with the exception that a portion of farmed salmon a month is exchanged for a portion of contaminated fish. The resulting median intake will be 1.9 pg TEQ/kg/day and 35 % of women will exceed EU's TDI. Herring caught in the Baltic Sea proper has lower levels of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs than does herring from the other waters along the east coast of Sweden and different salmonid species caught in the Baltic Sea, Gulf of Bothnia, Lake Vänern and Lake Vättern. In Scenario 5b an average level of 4 pg TEQ/g fresh weight is assumed for the herring from the Baltic Sea proper. A consumption of herring from the Baltic Sea proper once a month and farmed salmon three times a month will result in a median intake of 1.4 pg TEQ/kg/day. Only 7 % exceed TDI in this scenario. If, on the other hand, herring from the Bothnian Bay is consumed once per month (Scenario 5c) (average level 18 pg TEQ/g fresh weight) then the median intake of will reach 2.4 pg/kg/day and 80 % of the women will exceed TDI (Table 25).

Scenario 6: Fish 3 times a week including one meal of contaminated fish: If women eat contaminated fatty fish instead of farmed salmon once a week, and otherwise follow scenario 3, then the median intake will be 3.7 pg TEQ/kg/day. All young women in this case have an intake clearly over EU's TDI (Table 25).

Table 25. Intake scenarios for women in childbearing years calculated from the food consumption survey Riksmaten 1997-98.

	Riksmaten survey	1	2	3	4	5a	5b	5c	6
Average (pg/kg body weight/day)	1.0	0.93	0.87	1.57	1.36	1.87	1.46	2.39	3.68
Median (pg/kg body weight/day)	0.93	0.85	0.80	1.50	1.34	1.86	1.44	2.39	3.67
95th percentile (pg/kg body weight/day)	2.0	1.62	1.56	2.36	1.97	2.55	2.08	3.16	4.76
% over TDI	4.8	1.8	0.7	17	3.7	35	7	80	100

These scenarios show that if women eat only fatty fish with low levels of dioxin and dioxin-like PCB contamination, but increase their fish consumption to the level that is recommended by the NFA (three times a week including one meal of fatty fish, Scenario 4), then no great changes in the exposure occurs in relation to the current exposure situation. Few women will in this case exceed EU's TDI. Similar exposure levels are reached if one meal a month of fatty fish with a low contamination level is exchanged with a meal of herring from the Baltic Sea proper (Scenario 5b). This is because herring caught in this area have relatively low levels of dioxin and dioxin-like PCB. If, however, herring from the Gulf of Bothnia is consumed once a month the exposure increase significantly and 80% of women will exceed TDI (Scenario 5c).

For men and older women a scenario calculation was done with the assumption that all consumers ate fish three times per week and that one meal per week consisted of herring.

Fish 3 times per week including one meal of herring: If men and older women in general follow the Swedish National Food Administration for fish consumption, that is to say, three times per week including one meal of fatty fish, and the fatty fish consists of contaminated herring, then the median intake of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs would increase from approximately 1 pg TEQ/kg body weight/day (Riksmaten 1997-98) to 3.6 pg TEQ/kg/day for older women and 2.7 pg TEQ/kg/day for men. In this case the men and women with the highest intake levels will have median intakes about four times higher than the median intake in the Riksmaten survey.

Body burdens among young women in Sweden and at LOAEL/NOAEL

Dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs

As mentioned previously, EU's TDI for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs is only 9.6-fold lower than the exposure levels where health effects have been observed in the offspring of exposed mothers in animal experiments. Table 26 illustrates margins between NOAEL and LOAEL body burdens of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in body lipids obtained from animal experiments and body burdens among women in childbearing ages in Sweden. The median level of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among nursing women for the period 1996-99 was 18 pg TEQ/g lipid, the highest level was 39 pg/g lipid, and the level at the 95th percentile was 33 pg/g lipid. The median level of total TEQ was 10-44 times lower than the estimated TCDD levels in experimental animals at NOAEL and LOAEL (Table 26). Total TEQ levels at the 95th percentile and the highest total TEQ level was 6-24 times lower and 5-21 times lower, respectively, than the TCDD levels in experimental animals.

Table 26. The ratio between estimated TCDD levels in body lipids at NOAEL/LOAEL for the most sensitive effects of 2,3,7,8-TCDD at *in utero* exposure in rats [280] and measured levels of total TEQ in lipids from mother's milk sampled among primiparous women from Uppsala County [67].

Effects/endpoint	TCDD levels in the mother animal ng/kg fat ¹	Ratio: TCDD levels in animal studies / levels in total TEQ in mother's milk		
		median	max	95th percentile
1996-1999				
Reduced sperm production, disruptions in sexual behaviour, male offspring	400 (LOAEL)	22	10	12
Reduced anogenital distance, male offspring	200 (NOAEL)	10	5	6
	800 (LOAEL)	44	21	24
2002-2004³				
Reduced sperm production, disrupted sexual behaviour, male offspring	400 (LOAEL)	31	19	21
Reduced anogenital distance, male offspring	200 (NOAEL)	15	10	11
	800 (LOAEL)	62	38	42

¹Assuming 10 % fat in the body

Levels of total TEQ in the body have decreased among primiparous women from Uppsala. If the measured body burdens among the women sampled in 2002-2004 are compared with NOAEL and LOAEL body burdens, the margins are almost doubled (Table 26). Women with the highest levels however have a margin of

only 10 times from the levels at NOAEL. The analyses of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs among pregnant women have been conducted on a limited number of individuals from one region in Sweden. It is likely that regional differences in body burden of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are small in Sweden [279]. It is nevertheless probable that some women in childbearing years in Sweden have body burdens that are less than 10 times lower than the body burdens at NOAEL in animal experiments.

New contaminants

Background

In this report the focus has been on risks caused by dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in food since these compounds currently have the highest potential among persistent organic food contaminants to cause health problems. The following chapter summarizes the knowledge about more or less persistent pollutants in food that may be emerging problems, but for which the current knowledge about exposure and health risks is almost completely lacking. Among these compounds there are substances that only recently have been identified as food contaminants, but also substances for which new toxicological effects and/or new distribution patterns have recently been discovered.

Perflourinated compounds

During recent years a group of perflourinated compounds (PFC), in particular perfluorooctanesulfonate (PFOS), has been identified as a new important group of environmental pollutants. The compound group has surface-active properties and has extensively been used for impregnation of textiles, for instance in Scotch-Guard™, among several other areas of use. The company 3M has ended the production of PFOS, but production still probably occurs among other smaller manufacturers. PFOS and certain other PFCs are very persistent in the environment. The half-life of the compounds in exposed animals and humans is long. PFOS can also be produced as a result of metabolism of other PFCs. Studies have shown that the levels of certain PFCs have increased in the environment during a long time period [281].

Only a few studies have reported levels of PFOS and other PFCs in human samples. Among primiparous women from the Uppsala area 5-8 PFCs have been identified both in blood serum and mother's milk, among them PFOS [282]. The concentrations of the compounds were generally higher in blood serum than in mother's milk; the blood serum levels were approximately 1 % of those in blood serum. This shows that PFCs have a different distribution pattern than lipid soluble persistent organic pollutants such as dioxins and PCBs. A strong correlation was however found between blood serum and mother's milk levels of PFOS and another PFC, called perfluorohexane sulfonate (PFHxS). Even though the levels of PFCs were much lower in mother's milk than in blood serum, the

transfer of the PFCs from the mother to the nursed infant is not negligible (approximately 200 ng/day). A risk assessment of this exposure is needed but not possible due to the lack of useful studies [282].

Among women with reported high fish consumption, it was indicated that fish could be a significant exposure source of PFOS [283]. The concentrations detected in this population were similar to levels detected among men and women from the general Swedish population [284].

The toxicity of PFOS is relatively high in animals. Toxicity has been reported after *in utero* exposure in both rats and mice, including increased neonatal death, increased liver weight, effects on body growth after birth and developmental effects [285, 286]. Similar effects have also been reported for perfluorooctane acid (PFOA) [287].

Musk compounds

These compounds are used mainly in perfumes and in scented soaps, shampoos, laundry detergents and cosmetics. Elevated levels of musk compounds have in recent years been detected in fish and mothers' milk in Sweden, Germany and the USA.

Musk compounds are currently mainly synthetically produced and they can be divided into three major groups: nitromusks, polycyclic musks, and macrocyclic musks. The most common nitromusks are muskxylene (MX) and muskettone (MK). Among the polycyclic musks it is HHCB (Galaxolide) and AHTN (Tonalide) that are most commonly used. The macrocyclic musks recently came into use and in the future this group of chemicals will probably substitute the nitromusks and the polycyclic musks. The world production of musks is about 6-8 000 metric tons/year and approximately 95 % of the production consists of MX, MK, HHCB and AHTN. In Sweden the yearly use of musk compounds is 4-5 metric tons [288]. The compounds have been detected in the environment in all Nordic countries [439].

The bioavailability of MX is low in humans and after absorption the half-life in the body is approximately 70 days. Fish may have elevated levels of musk compounds but direct exposure of humans through the use of perfume and perfumed products is regarded as the most important source of exposure. Musk compounds have been detected in mother's milk and may cause high intakes of the compounds among nursed infants [289]. Mother's milk from primiparous mothers living in the Uppsala area has been analyzed for musk compounds

between the years 1996 and 2003. The highest levels were found for HHCB (median: 62 µg/kg lipid). No significant trends of musk levels were observed during the study period but the lowest concentrations of AHTN and MX were detected towards the end of the study period [289].

Nitromusks and polycyclic musks have low acute toxicity and no signs of genotoxicity have been seen. MX and MK can, however, induce metabolic enzymes (cytochrome P-450) in the liver of mice and rats. The only available cancer study of MX in mice showed that the total tumor frequency was significantly increased among exposed mice (100 and 200 mg/kg body weight) than among control mice [288]. However, no dose-response was observed.

The cancer effects is regarded to be the critical effect in the risk assessment of musk compounds and a TDI of 50 µg/kg body weight has been proposed, after the use of an uncertainty factor of 2 000 [288]. Intake calculations suggest that fish consumption does not result in intakes exceeding the proposed TDI. Breast milk exposure of infants gives a higher intake than exposure from fish consumption among adults, but breast milk exposure is of relatively short duration. If the direct exposure to musks through the use of perfume and perfumed products is added a higher exposure than the TDI may be reached among adults for both nitromusks and polycyclic musks. This assessment must be regarded as preliminary due to lack of data [289].

Phenolic compounds

Chlorophenols

Pentachlorophenol (PCP) is the most widely used chlorophenol. The use of PCP started in the 1930's and a large proportion of the PCP produced (95-98 % i USA) has been used directly or indirectly for impregnation of wood. In Sweden large amounts of PCPs have been used in paper mills and in the paper industry. In Finland, 1 300 tons/year has been estimated to have been used in wood and paper industries during the 1980's. There has been no production of PCP within EU since 1992, but PCPs have been imported to Europe from Asia and possibly from the USA. All chlorophenols have been used as biocides. Dichlorophenols have been used as insecticides against gnats and mosquitoes and monochlorophenols have been used in antiseptic compounds in hospitals. The use of PCP and other chlorophenols have been prohibited in Sweden since 1977 and 1978, respectively [440].

Intake through food has been indicated to be the main path of exposure of chlorophenols for the general population. Some calculations suggest that more than 95 % of PCP intake occurs through food (Hattemeyer and Frey, 1989), and fruit, vegetables and cereals have been proposed to be the main sources. In other studies dairy products, grains and meats have particularly been identified as sources [290]. There are no studies that show fish to contain relatively high PCP levels. In a Slovakian study, the average intake of PCP through food was estimated to be 0.32 µg/kg body weight/day (Veningerova et al., 2000), but for the Swedish consumer there are no comparable data. In a study of Swedish primiparous women, a number of congeners of PCB-phenols and PCP in the blood during pregnancy were analyzed [291]. Of all the analyzed substances, it was PCP that had the highest levels in the blood: up to 3 ng/g serum (fresh weight). Certain proteins in the blood effectively bind PCP, which lead to relatively high levels in the blood.

PCP is the most acutely toxic compound of all chlorophenols tested. The most important acutely toxic mechanism is a free-coupling of oxidative phosphorylation. This leads to increased body temperature, heavy sweating, extreme exhaustion, and even higher PCP exposure leads to cardiac arrest and death. Occupational exposure to lower levels results in skin problems, irritated mucus membranes, and also to neurological problems. Immunological problems have also been observed. PCP has been classed as a possible carcinogen for humans (according to IARC). There are also indications that PCP and a number of other halogenated phenolic compounds can cause hormonal effects. *In vitro* studies have shown that PCP has a strong competitive effect on binding of thyroxine (T4) to trans-thyretin and albumin, transporters for T4 in the body (van den Berg, 1990). Other hormonal systems could also be affected [189].

The acceptable intake (ADI) for PCP is 3 µg/kg body weight/day [292]. Intake among the Swedish population is not known, but the above-mentioned Slovakian study reports an average intake that makes up about 10 % of ADI. If several different chlorophenols have a common mechanism for toxicity, which has been indicated in animal studies (effects on the thyroid hormone balance), then these substances should be summed up when comparing actual intake and acceptable intake, especially if the acceptable intake is based upon thyroid effects.

Alkylphenols

Alkylphenols are used in the form of alkylphenoloxylates, mainly in cleaning and polish products, and as emulsifying compounds. In water treatment plants ethoxylates are converted to alkylphenols which then can be found in the environment. The three most common alkylphenol groups are butyl- (BP), octyl- (OP) and nonylphenol (NP). The use of NP within EU is about 73 000 tons per year and about 20 000 tons of OP is used [293].

The general population is exposed to OP and NP through food, mainly fish and to some extent, through drinking water. Plastic film for food use may be an important source of exposure of NP. A realistic assessment of OP intake from fish is 0.01-0.1 ng/kg body weight/day, while the worst case intake of OP and NP from fish could be about 4 and 5 ng/kg body weight/day, respectively [293].

The alkylphenols have a low acute toxicity. OP and NP have been found to have estrogenic properties in several *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies. The most sensitive effect of OP is the change in sperm motility in rats (LOAEL 20 ng/kg body weight/day), and a longer gestational period in swine (LOAEL 0.01 mg/kg body weight/day) [293]. The safety margin for Swedish men is small if the intake of OP from fish is compared with intake levels where effects are found in male rats. The rat study on sperm quality is not uncontroversial and the study should be repeated. In the rat studies no effects on reproductive capacity were reported and the risk for harmful effects of OP on sperm quality among humans is still unknown. Women will not be at risk to exceed TDI according to the above criteria. The risk for health effects because of exposure to NP is very low for both sexes based on the current state of knowledge [293].

Brominated/chlorinated dibenzodioxins/furans

Brominated dibenzodioxins and furans (PBDD/F), as well as the mixed brominated/chlorinated dioxins and furans, have been identified in the Swedish environment. These compounds are formed during combustion processes where bromine and chlorine are present but also in chemical processes involving synthesis of brominated compounds, such as BFRs [441]. Little is known about the toxicity of these compounds. A review of the literature has shown that PBDD/Fs may have a similar toxicity to that of PCDD/Fs. Data for a risk assessment is, however, still lacking [294].

The concentrations of PBDD/Fs have recently been analyzed in several environmental matrices in Sweden, among them fish [295]. The levels of PBDD/Fs in fish were, in many cases, higher than the levels of corresponding PCDD/Fs. Levels of lower brominated congeners were however higher than those of higher brominated congeners. The bromine atom occupies more space than the chlorine atom, and the lower brominated dioxins and furans may therefore interact with the Ah-receptor in a different way than the corresponding PCDD/Fs.

”New” brominated compounds

Apart from the different compound groups described above there are many other brominated compounds that are used by the industry, in many cases as flame retardants:

- Brominated phenols (2,4-di-, 2,4,6-tri-). These compounds have shown some toxic effects *in vitro*.
- PBT (pentabromotoluene). Can be formed from bromostyrene.
- Decabromodiphenylethane.
- Brominated phthalateacid derivates.
- Bis (2,4,6-tribromophenoxy) ethane.

Almost no toxicity data are available for these types of compounds and nothing is known about human exposure. It is therefore not possible to assess the health risks associated to these compound groups.

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Appendix 1 – Epidemiology

Infants and children

Finland

In 1987 PCDD/F and PCB was analyzed in mother's milk among 167 randomly-selected mothers of ages 20-37 years [296]. The mother's milk was collected during the 4th week after delivery and the mothers lived in an urban area (Helsinki, Finland) or in a rural area (the Kuopio region). Simple correlation analysis showed a negative association between total concentrations of PCDD/F TEQ and birth weight (Table 1). The correlation was most evident among boys. No statistically-significant correlations were found if the analysis was based on primiparous mothers. No significant correlations were found between PCB concentrations in mother's milk and birth weight.

In the same cohort, the association between hypomineralization of teeth and exposure to PCDD/DF was studied when the children had reached age 6-7 years (N=102) [104]. Seventeen of the children showed hypomineralization of teeth that normally are mineralized during the first 2 years of life. The total PCDD/F exposure was estimated from the concentrations in mother's milk and the length of each child's nursing period. Hypomineralization was more common among children with the highest exposures than among children with the lowest exposure. No significant associations were found if the statistical analysis was based only on PCDD/F concentrations in mother's milk [104]. In a subsequent article dealing with PCB exposure, no significant associations were found between PCB exposure (sum of 33 PCB congeners) and hypomineralization [297].

During the period 1997-2000 all children (N=34 457), born at 4 hospitals in Finland, were examined for presence of natal and/or neonatal teeth [100]. A total of 29 newborns had natal teeth and 5 had neonatal teeth. Mother's milk was sampled from 14 of the mother's of these children; 11 came from the Helsinki area and 3 from the Turku area. The exposure of the children with natal/neonatal teeth did not differ between the two regions. Mother's milk from 12 mothers of children having no natal or neonatal teeth was also sampled in the Turku area. The mean PCDD/F/PCB exposure of the control children was lower than the mean exposure of the children with natal/neonatal teeth, but the difference was not statistically significant [100]. The study had low statistical power.

Table 1. Body burdens of PCB 153, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE among pregnant/nursing women in cohorts used in studies of associations between background exposure to the different compounds and birth weight and child growth. Concentrations in serum/plasma or mother's milk are presented as medians or means.

Study	Concentrations (ng/g lipid)	N	Effects
Birth weight and growth			
Sweden, fishermen's wives [101]	PCB 153 160/190 ¹ Body burden during pregnancy estimated from levels measured many years later	192	Birth weight (-PCB), weight increase after birth (-PCB)
Finland-Helsinki and Kuopio [296]	PCB 153 100 PCDD/DF 26	167	Birth weight both sexes (±PCB) Birth weight boys (-PCDD/F TEQ)
Netherlands – Rotterdam/Groningen [269, 298]	PCB 153 175 PCDD/DF 30	415	Birth weight, growth up to 3 months (-PCB), growth after 3 months (±PCB)
Netherlands – Amsterdam [299]	PCDD/F TEQ 28	38	Birth weight, growth (±PCDD/DF)
Germany-Hessen [300]	Only concentrations in blood of the children.	343	Height increase girls (-DDE, ±PCB), growth boys (±DDE, PCB)
USA–Michigan [269]	PCB 153 120 ²	192-236	Birth weight (-PCB), weight at 4 years girls (-PCB) boys (±PCB)
USA–Great Lakes, anglers [301]	PCB 153 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 314 Not analyzed during pregnancy	242	Birth weight (-DDE, ±PCB)
USA–North Carolina [75, 269]	PCB 153 80 ² <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 2190	872	Birth weight, growth up to 1 year (±PCB/DDE) Puberty: weight and length boys (+DDE boys), girls (±DDE)
USA–Oswego [302]	PCB 153 40 ²	559	Birth weight, head circumference (±PCB)
USA – 11 cities [269] [303]	PCB 153 140 ² <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 3077	2737 1712	Birth weight (±PCB, -DDE) Premature birth (±PCB, -DDE) Growth up to 7 years (±PCB, -DDE)
Canada – Inuites [304]	PCB 153 400 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 1200	94	Birth weight (±DDE, ±PCB) Birth length boys (-PCB/DD/DF) Birth length girls (+PCB/DD/DF)
USA-Wisconsin [305]	PCB 153 130 (0.7 % blood lipids) Concentrations partially estimated from fish consumption	1112	Birth weight (+PCB)
USA-Californien [306]	PCB 153 133 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 5880	1291	Birth weight boys (-PCB), girls (±PCB) Head circumference both sexes (-PCB) 5 yrs: growth boys (±PCB), girls (-PCB) DDE no associations
Japan-Tokyo [307]	PCB/DD/DF TEQ 24	240	Birth weight (±PCB/DD/DF TEQ)
Spanien – HCB-contaminated area [308]	PCB 153 25 (0.2 % blood lipids) <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 425 (0.2 % blood lipids)	98	Birth weight (±PCB/DDE) Length at birth (±PCB/DDE)
Michigan-anglers [309]	PCB 153 1900 (0.7 % blood lipids) <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 1040 (0.7 % blood lipids) Not measured during pregnancy	168	Birth weight (-PCB, ±DDE)
Michigan-PBB [380]	?	308	Body length of girls (±PCB), body weight (-PCB)

¹Controls/cases (normal birth weight/low birth weight).

²Estimated concentrations according to Longnecker et al. 2003 [269].

³Associations between exposure and effect within parenthesis (minus=negative association, plus=positive association, ±=no significant association).

Netherlands - Rotterdam/Groningen

A study of 418 pregnant women of European ancestry was performed in Rotterdam (industrial area) and Groningen (more rural area) between 1990 and 1992 [310]. Half of the women nursed their infants for at least 6 weeks, whereas the other half gave their children infant formula (from the same manufactured batch) for 7 months. Blood was sampled from the mothers in late pregnancy (week 36-40). Moreover, umbilical cord blood, mother's milk and children's blood were sampled. In most studies of associations between exposure and health out-comes sub-groups of the cohort were studied. Concentrations in blood from the mother in late pregnancy or cord blood were used as estimates of *in utero* exposure. Post-natal exposure was estimated from concentrations in mother's milk (in some cases together with length of nursing period) [70, 108, and 298].

Both birth weight and growth among the children up to an age of 42 months were studied, and a negative association was found between birth weight and in utero PCB exposure [311] (Table 1). Among formula-fed infants, a negative association was found between *in utero* PCB exposure and infant growth (weight, height and head circumference) between ages 0 and 3 months, but not between ages 3 and 42 months. No associations were observed between post-natal exposure and out-comes except for a negative association between PCB and dioxin exposure and height increase in among 3-7 months old infants (Table 1).

The neurological development of the children in the Dutch cohort has been followed up several times for 9 years after birth (Table 2). No associations between pre-natal PCB exposure and neurological development were observed at 10-21 days of age (N=418) [312]. A negative association was however found between PCB and dioxin concentrations in mother's milk and neurological development. At 3-18 months of age, negative associations between pre- and post-natal PCB and dioxin exposure and psycho-motor development and neurological status were observed (N=207-418) [313, 314]. A positive effect of nursing was indicated. At 42 months of age (N=394), no associations were found between pre-/post-natal exposure and neurological development [315, 316]. A negative association was however found between pre-natal PCB exposure and cognitive development [317]. Some positive effects of nursing was observed also in this study [315, 316].

At the age of 6-7 years, a negative association was observed between pre-natal PCB/dioxin exposure and cognitive and motor development among children growing up in sub-optimal home environments [318] (Table 2). These associations were not found among children growing up in more optimal environments. At a nine-year follow up on the Rotterdam children, negative associations were found between pre-natal PCB exposure and a few of the cognitive parameters among the tested children (N=83) [320]. Negative associations were also found between pre-natal PCB exposure and results of a

P300-latency test, but children that had been nursed for at least 16 weeks performed better than children that had been nursed 6-16 weeks [319]. The P300-latency test measures several cognitive skills, among them short-term memory and speed of stimulus classification.

Thyroid hormones were analyzed in blood plasma from infants two weeks and three months after birth (N=78). A positive association was found between PCB and dioxin concentrations in mother's milk and TSH levels in blood plasma, whereas a negative association between exposure and total T4 level was observed [321].

Possible effects of pre- and post-natal PCB and dioxin exposure on immune function were studied on the children from the Rotterdam area at ages 0-42 months and 7 years [322-324] (Table 4). Statistically-significant associations were found between pre-natal PCB and dioxin exposure and the numbers of monocytes, granulocytes, lymphocytes and certain T-lymphocytes, as well as levels of antibodies against mumps and measles, during the first 42 months of life (N=55-85) [322, 323]. No associations were found between pre- and post-natal PCB and dioxin exposure and incidence of infections (bronchitis, middle-ear infection, etc) (N=207) [322]. At the age of 42 months, however, a negative association was found between pre-natal PCB exposure and incidence of shortness of breath during the recent year, and a positive association between post-natal dioxin exposure and coughing for extended periods (N=175) [323] (Table 4). Moreover, the concentrations of PCB in blood plasma among the children at the age of 42 months (N=158) were positively associated with recurrent middle-ear infections and the incidence of chicken pox, and negatively associated with the incidence of allergic reactions [323]. Even though the body burdens of PCB at the age of 42 months among bottle-fed children were 3-4-fold lower than among nursed children, no difference in incidence of recurrent middle-ear infections, chicken pox and allergic reactions could be seen between the children [323]. When the children were seven years old (N=167), a negative association was found between pre-natal PCB exposure and the incidence of chicken pox during the most recent four years of life [324]. The post-natal PCB exposure was positively associated with recurrent middle-ear infections and children that had been nursed for less than four months had a higher incidence of recurrent middle-ear infections than children who had been nursed for four months or more [324] (Table 4).

The Netherlands–Amsterdam

During 1990-1991, 38 mother/infant pairs were recruited from the general population in Amsterdam. All participating women planned to nurse their infants for at least 12 weeks. Blood from the mother and umbilical cord blood were sampled immediately after delivery. Blood was sampled from the children 1 and

11 weeks after delivery and mother's milk was sampled three weeks after delivery. In several of the health studies, the children were divided into two groups: one low and one high exposure group according to the PCDD/F TEQ concentrations in mother's milk (low 8.7-28 pg/g lipid, high 29-63 pg/g lipid) [325, 326]. No differences in weight, length or head circumference were found between the infants with low and high exposures during the first 26 weeks of life [299] (Table 1). The neurological status of the infants was determined at birth, after six months and two years after birth [299, 327] (Table 2). No difference in neurological status was observed between the high and low exposure groups at birth and six months after birth [327]. When the children were two years old, significant differences were observed between the two groups regarding certain motor functions, but not regarding mental and psycho-motor development [299] (Table 2).

Some differences in thyroid-hormone status were observed between the low-level and high-level exposure groups at the ages 1 and 11 months (Table 3). Levels of total T4 and TSH in blood plasma were higher in the high-level exposure group than in the low-level exposure group [325, 328]. At two years of age, no significant difference in thyroid hormone status was found [299]. In a small number of the children (N=9) vitamin K status was determined 11 months after birth, but no significant associations with PCDD/F concentrations in mother's milk was observed [329]. Other hematological parameters, such as leukocytes, trombocytes, γ -glutamyltransferase (GGT), aspartataminotransferasé (AST), alaninaminotransferase (ALT), cholesterol and conjugated bilirubine, were analyzed at ages 1 and 11 months and 2 years [326]. A few significant associations were found between hematological parameters and PCDD/F TEQ concentrations in mother's milk at ages 1 and 11 months, but no differences were found between the high and low-level exposure groups at the age of two years [299] (Table 3).

In a follow-up study when the children were eight years old, associations between early-life dioxin exposure and immunological parameters in blood, allergies and infections were analyzed statistically [330] (Table 4). In this study PCDD/F concentrations in mother's milk were used to assess pre-natal exposure.

Post-natal exposure was estimated from the concentrations and the amount of mother's milk each child had consumed during the nursing period. A positive association was found between post-natal exposure and numbers of certain T-cell populations. A negative association was found between pre- and post-natal exposure and allergies. No associations were observed between dioxin exposure and middle-ear infections, pneumonia and chicken pox [330] (Table 4).

Table 2. Body burdens of PCB 153, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE (medians or means) among pregnant and nursing women in cohorts where neurotoxic effects have been studied.

Study	Concentration (ng/g lipid)		N	Health effects ²
The Netherlands, Rotterdam/Groningen [269] [298]	PCB 153	175	418	Neonatal: neurological development (-PCB, PCDD/F) Precht Neurological Examination
	PCDD/F TEQ	30	207	3 mo: psycho-motor development (-PCB, PCDD/F), mental development (\pm PCB, PCDD/F) Bayley Scales of Infant Development (BSID)
				7 mo: psycho-motor development (\pm PCB, PCDD/F), mental development (\pm PCB, PCDD/F) BSID
			418	18 mo: psycho-motor development (\pm PCB, PCDD/F), mental development (\pm PCB, PCDD/F) BSID, neurological development (-PCB)
			394	
			395	42 mo: neurological development (\pm PCB) Touwen/Hempel method, cognitive development (-PCB) Kaufman Assessment Battery for Children, language development (\pm PCB) Reynell Language Development Scales
Netherlands – Amsterdam [299]			193	6.5 yr: cognitive and motor development (-PCB) McCarthy Scales of Children's Ability, play behavior (-PCB, PCDD/F) Pre-School Activity Inventory
			372	9 yr: development of visual memory (\pm PCB) Rey Complex Figure Test, reaction time (-PCB) SRTT, hearing and language memory development (\pm PCB) Auditory-Verbal Learning Test, psycho-motor development (-PCB) Tower of London, auditory memory (-PCB)
	PCDD/F TEQ	28	38	6 mo: neurological development (\pm PCDD/F) Touwen Method/Precht Neurological Examination
			2.5 yr: motor development (+PCDD/F), mental and psycho-motor development (\pm PCDD/F) Hempel Test and Bayley Scales of Infant Development,	
Germany – Düsseldorf [269]	PCB 153	140	171	7 mo: mental development (-PCB), motor development (\pm PCB) BSID, Development of visual memory (\pm PCB) Fagan Test of Infant Intelligence
			110	18 mo: mental and motor development (\pm PCB) BSID
				30 mo: mental and motor development (-PCB) BSID
				42 mo: cognitive development (-PCB) Kaufman Achievement Battery for Children

¹Body burdens according to Longnecker et al. 2003 [269].

²Associations between exposure and effect in parenthesis (minus=negative association, plus=positive association, \pm =no significant association).

Table 2 continued. Body burdens of PCB 153, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE (medians or means) among pregnant and nursing women in cohorts where associations with neurotoxic effects have been studied.

Study	Concentration (ng/g lipid)	N	Health effects ²
USA – Michigan [269]	PCB 153 120 ¹	242	Neonatal: psycho-motor development (\pm PCB) Brazelton Neonatal Scale (BNS)
		123	7 mo: development of visual memory (-PCB) Fagan's Test of Visual Recognition
		236-265	4 yr: cognitive development (-PCB), motor development (\pm PCB) McCarthy Scales of Children's Ability, activity level (-PCB)
		167-212	11 yr: cognitive development (-PCB) 15 different neuro-psychological tests, IQ (-PCB) Wechsler Intelligence Scales for Children IQ test
USA – North Carolina [269] [75]	PCB 153 80 ¹ <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 2190	912	Neonatal: psycho-motor development (-PCB, -DDE) BNS
			12 mo: motor development (-PCB, \pm DDE) BNS, mental development (\pm DDE) BNS
			24 mo: motor development (-PCB, \pm DDE)
			3-5 yr: cognitive development (\pm PCB DDE)
USA – Oswego [269]	PCB 153 40 ¹	152	Neo-natal: psycho-motor development (-PCB, \pm DDE) BNS
		216-230	6-12 mo: development of visual memory (-PCB, \pm DDE) Fagan's Test of Infant Intelligence
			38 mo: cognitive development (-PCB) McCarthy Scales of Children's Ability
			54 mo: cognitive development (\pm PCB) McCarthy Scales of Children's Ability
USA – 11 cities [269] [303]	PCB 153 140 ¹ <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 3077	1207	8 mo: psycho-motor development (\pm PCB) BNS
		732	7 yr: IQ (\pm PCB) Wrechsler Intelligence Scale for Children
			8 yr: auditory development (\pm PCB) auditory test
Faeroe Islands 1986-87 [266]	PCB 153 223 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 713	1022	7 yr: motor and cognitive development, (\pm PCB) interaction with MeHg?
Faeroe Islands 1994.95 [269, 331]	PCB 153 450 ¹ <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 720	173	Neonatal: neurological development (\pm PCB) Prechtl Neurological Examination, interaction with MeHg?
Canada – Inuit [332] [333]	PCB 153 94 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 372	110	5 yr: neurological and motor development (\pm PCB) Amiel-Tison and Gosselin Examination, Huttenlocher Gross Motor Function Test, cognitive development (-PCB post-natal) Visual evoked potentials
Spain – HCB-contaminated area [308]	PCB 153 25 (0.2 % lipids) <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 425 (0.2 % lipids)	92	13 mon: mental and psycho-motor development (\pm PCB, -DDE) Bayley Scales of Infant Development, Griffith's Mental Development Scales
Spain - Menorca [334]	PCB 153 105 (0.2 % lipids) <i>p,p'</i> -DDE 500 (0.2 % lipids)	159	4 yr: Cognitive development (both Spanish cohorts) (\pm DDE, -DDT) McCarty Scales of Children's Ability

¹Body burdens according to Longnecker et al. 2003 [269].

²Associations between exposure and effect in parenthesis (minus=negative association, plus=positive association, \pm =no significant association).

Germany - Düsseldorf

In a German study, 171 healthy mother/child pairs were recruited between 1993 and 1995 at three hospitals in Düsseldorf directly after delivery [57, 335]. Women giving birth to their first or second child were included in the study. Cord blood, mother's milk and blood from the children were sampled. Pre-natal exposure was estimated from PCB concentrations in umbilical cord blood and mother's milk [57, 335].

Child development was studied at 7, 18, 30 and 42 months of age. At all ages significant associations were found between post-natal PCB exposure and mental and psycho-motor development [57, 335] (Table 2). At 42 months of age a negative association was found between post-natal PCB exposure and child intelligence. [57].

Germany - Hessen

Between 1994 and 1995, 671 children between the ages of seven and ten years were recruited from 18 different municipalities in Hessen [60, 300]. Parents and children answered questionnaires and the children's health were examined. Mercury was analyzed in urine samples and blood samples were analyzed for PCB and chlorinated pesticides. Follow-up studies were performed in 1996 and 1997 [60, 300].

The growth of the children from birth to 10 years of age (N=343) was studied and girls in the highest DDE exposure quartile ($>0.44 \mu\text{g/l}$ blood) were significantly shorter (mean: 1.8 cm) than girls in the lowest exposure quartile (Table 1) [300]. No association between DDE body burdens and growth effects was observed in the boys. PCB body burden was not associated with growth effects in the children (Table 1) [300].

A positive association was observed between serum concentrations of PCB 118 and TSH levels in blood. Moreover, a negative association between serum concentrations of several PCB congeners and levels of free T3 was found [60] (Table 3).

Questions about infections and asthma among the children were included in the questionnaires (N=343) and several markers of immune function were analyzed in blood (N=331) [336, 337] (Table 4). The DDE concentrations in blood serum were positively associated with asthma, and concentrations of PCB, DDE, HCB and gamma-HCH were related to alterations in some of the studied immune markers.

USA - Michigan

Primiparous women were recruited from four hospitals in western Michigan 1980-81 [105, 338, 339]. Women were initially interviewed and a group of women with moderate to high consumption of Lake Michigan fish (N=242, mean consumption 18 g/day for the last 16 years) were included in the cohort together with a group that did not consume this type of fish (N=71). Cord blood was sampled together with blood from the mothers in conjunction to the delivery. Mother's milk and blood from the children were collected at later stages of the study. All samples were analyzed for PCBs. Pre-natal exposure was determined from PCB levels in cord blood. PCB levels in mother's milk, sometimes together with the number of weeks of nursing (post-natal exposure), were also used in exposure assessment. The PCB concentrations in the blood and milk from the mothers were positively correlated with consumption of PCB-contaminated Lake Michigan fish [105, 338, 339].

The women that reported consumption of Lake Michigan fish gave birth to children with a shorter gestational age and a lower birth weight than mothers with no Lake Michigan fish consumption [338, 340] (Table 1). A negative association was found between these health-based endpoints and pre-natal PCB exposure [340]. When the children were four years old, a negative association was found between child weight and pre-natal PCB exposure, but the association was only statistically significant among girls [63].

Neurological status and development were studied among the children at birth and at ages seven months, four years and seven years (Table 2). Performance in tests of the neo-natal behavior was negatively associated with the Lake Michigan fish consumption of the mother (N=242) [338, 340]. At seven months of age the visual memory was negatively associated with fish consumption, as well as with pre-natal PCB exposure (N=123) [338, 341]. In tests of cognitive function among the children at the age of four years, negative associations was observed between pre- and post-natal PCB exposure and short term memory and activity level (N=236) [338, 341]. IQ and neuro-psychological functions were tested at the age of 11 years (N=148-212) [58, 343]. A negative association was found between pre-natal PCB exposure and performance in some of the IQ tests, as well as between exposure and total reading and word comprehension (Table 2) [58]. Post-natal PCB exposure was not significantly associated with these end-points [58]. Negative associations were observed between pre-natal PCB exposure among non-breast-fed children and neuro-psychological function [343]. It was concluded that children that were not breast-fed appeared to be more sensitive to pre-natal PCB exposure than breast-fed children [343]. It was, however, not possible to conclude if this protective effect of nursing depended on the nutritional quality of mother's milk or on a higher quality mental stimulation of the nursed infant.

Table 3. Body burdens of PCB 153, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE among pregnant and nursing women in cohorts where associations with thyroid status have been studied.

Concentrations are medians or means.

Study	Concentrations (ng/g lipid)		N	Health effects ³
The Netherlands – Rotterdam/Groningen [269, 298]	PCB 153	100 ²	78	2 weeks: TSH (+PCB, PCDD/F), T4 (-PCB, PCDD/F) 3 months: TSH (+PCB, PCDD/F)
The Netherlands – Amsterdam [299]	PCDD/F TEQ	28	38	Newborn: No associations with hormones (PCDD/F) 1 week: TSH (±PCDD/F), total T4 (+PCDD/F), TBG (±PCDD/F) 11 weeks: TSH (+PCDD/F), total T4 (+PCDD/F), total T3 (±PCDD/F), TBG (±PCDD/F) 2 years: No associations (PCDD/F)
Germany-Hessen [300]	Post-natal exposure		320	7-10 years: TSH (+PCB), free T4 (±PCB), free T3 (-PCB)
USA–North Carolina [75, 269]	PCB 153	80 ²	160	Newborn: TSH, free T4, total T4, total T3 (±PCB)
	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE	2000		
Canada – Inuit [304]	PCB 153	?	94	Newborn: TSH (±PCB, PCDD/F, DDE)
	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE	962		
Japan [368]	PCB/DD/DF TEQ	27	36	1 year: T3, T4 (-PCB/PCDD/F), TSH, TBG (±PCB/PCDD/F)
Japan [370]	PCB/DD/DF TEQ	26	71	1 year: T4 (-PCB/PCDD/F), TSH (+PCB/PCDD/F), T3, TBG (±PCB/PCDD/F)
Japan [372]	PCB/DD/DF TEQ	13-30	337	1 year: TSH (±PCB/PCDD/F)
	pg/g lipid			
Spain – HCB-contaminated area [308]	PCB 153	70 (0.7	80	Newborn: TSH (±PCB, DDE)
	% lipid)			
	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE	800 (0.7		
	% lipids)			

¹Body burdens according to Longnecker et al. 2003 [269].

²Associations between exposure and effect in parenthesis (minus=negative association, plus=positive association, ±=no significant association).

USA – Great Lakes anglers

Between 1993 and 1995 licensed charter-boat captains were recruited in the area around the Great Lakes (Wisconsin, Illinois, Indiana, Ohio, and Michigan) [301]. It was assumed that these individuals consumed contaminated fish from the Great Lakes on a regular basis. The wives/partners and children of the charter captains also participated in the study. A control group with individuals from the general population not consuming Great Lakes fish was randomly matched to the exposed group. The women in the highest quartile of Great Lakes fish consumption and all the participating women in the control group were asked to give a blood sample. A total of 262 women gave blood, and 242 of these women had children. The blood samples were analyzed for PCB and DDE.

Ambiguous results were obtained in the study (Table 1) [301]. Children born 1970-1977, 1978-1984 and 1985-93 by women with high consumption of Great Lakes fish had a birth weight that was 164 g less, 42 g more and 134 g more, respectively, than children born by mothers who did not consume Great Lakes fish. After adjustment for possible confounding factors birth weight was

negatively associated with the serum concentrations of DDE of the mother, but not with the PCB concentrations [301].

USA - North Carolina

During 1978 to 1982, about 800 pregnant women were recruited from the general population in North Carolina [108, 344]. Cord blood and mother's milk (colostrum) were sampled for PCB and DDE analyses. Additional mother's milk samples were collected for up to 12 months after delivery. The PCB and DDE concentrations in mother's milk directly after delivery were used in assessment of pre-natal exposure. Concentrations in mother's milk combined with the length of the nursing period were used to estimate the post-natal exposure.

No associations were found between pre-natal exposure and birth weight, head circumference and neo-natal jaundice (Table 1) [344]. Moreover, no association was found between pre-natal PCB exposure and weight increase among the children up to the age of one year [70]. The growth of the children (N=594) were followed up at puberty and the height and weight (adjusted for height) of the boys increased with increased pre-natal DDE-exposure [345].

The neurological status and development of the children were determined several times up to the age of five years (Table 2). Higher pre-natal PCB and DDE exposures were associated with some alterations in neonatal behaviour during the first month after birth (N=912) [344]. A negative association between pre-natal exposure, but not post-natal exposure, and psychomotor development among the children at 6-24 months of age was found (N=670-802) [70, 346, 347]. At three, four and five years of age no association was found between pre- and post-natal exposure and neurodevelopment (N=712) [348]. The research team concluded that the negative effects that were observed during the first two years of life were not detectable at ages three to five years (Table 2).

No association between pre-natal PCB exposure and levels of thyroid hormones in umbilical cord blood were observed (N=160) (Table 3) [349]. The thyroid hormones were, however, not analyzed in cord blood until 1998, and the research team concluded that it could not be excluded that degradation of hormones may have occurred due to the long storage period [349].

Table 4. Body burdens of PCB 153, PCDD/F and *p,p'*-DDE among pregnant and nursing women in cohorts where associations with immune system function, infectious diseases and asthma/allergies have been studied. Concentrations are medians or means. **JAPAN SAKNAS**

Study	Concentrations (ng/g lipid)		N	Health effects ³
The Netherlands – Rotterdam/Groningen [269, 298]	PCB 153 PCDD/F TEQ	100 ² 30	206	0-42 months: Markers of immune function associated with pre-natal PCB and PCDD/F exposure 18 months: Infections, (±PCB, PCDD/F) 42 months: Shortness of breath (-PCB pre-natal), middle ear infection, chicken pox (+PCB post-natal), allergic reactions (-PCB post-natal) 7 yrs: Chicken pox, shortness of breath (-PCB pre-natal), middle ear infection (+PCB post-natal), allergic reactions (±PCB)
The Netherlands – Amsterdam [299]	PCDD/F TEQ	28	38	8 yrs: Markers of immune function associated with PCDD/F postnatal exposure 8 yrs: Allergy (-PCDD/F pre- and post-natal), asthma, middle ear infection, chicken pox (±PCDD/F pre- and post-natal)
Germany - Hessen [300]	Only analyses of children's blood		343	7-8 yrs: Markers of immune function associated with PCB and DDE post-natal exposure 7-8 yrs: Asthma (+DDE, ±PCB post-natal)
Canada – Inuit (1989-90) [304]	PCB 153 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE	? 962	171	3-12 months: No associations between markers of immune function and pre-natal PCB/DDE exposure 3 months: Respiratory infections (±PCB, DDE pre-natal), middle ear infection (±PCB, +DDE pre-natal) 7 months: Respiratory infections (±PCB, DDE), middle ear infections (±PCB, +DDE) 12 months: Respiratory infections (±PCB, DDE), middle ear infections (±PCB, DDE)
Canada - Inuit (1993-96) [333]	PCB 153	94	343	5 yrs: Middle-ear infection (+PCB), upper respiratory infections (±PCB), lower respiratory infections (+PCB)
Canada - Inuit (1995-2001) [53]	PCB 153 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE	102 294	199	6 months: Middle-ear infection (±PCB, DDE), upper respiratory infections (±PCB, DDE), lower respiratory infections (+PCB, ±DDE), total infections (+PCB, ±DDE)
Canada – fishing villages [364, 365]	PCB 153 <i>p,p'</i> -DDE	18-58 105-167	112	Neo-natal: Markers of immune function associated with PCB pre-natal exposure
Japan [369]	PCB/DD/DF TEQ	27	37	1 year: Markers of immune function associated with post-natal PCB/PCDD/F TEQ exposure
Japan [371]	PCB/DD/DF TEQ	26	71	1 year: Markers of immune function associated with post-natal PCB/PCDD/F TEQ exposure
Spain - Menorca [334]	PCB 153 % lipid <i>p,p'</i> -DDE % lipid	105 (0.2) 500 (0.2)	405	4 yrs: Shortness of breath (+DDE pre-natal) 6 yrs: Shortness of breath (±DDE pre-natal, ±DDE post-natal), asthma (+DDE in utero, ±post-natal)

¹Body burdens according to Longnecker et al. 2003 [269].

²Associations between exposure and effect in parenthesis (minus=negative association, plus=positive association, ±=no significant association).

USA - Oswego

Between 1991 and 1994, 559 pregnant women in Oswego on the shore of Lake Ontario were recruited [108, 268, 302]. The cohort consisted of women reporting consumption of Lake Ontario fish before and during pregnancy (N=395), as well

as randomly-selected women reporting no consumption of fish from the area (N=164). The women's self-reported fish consumption was divided into three groups of PCB exposure from fish: high exposure, low exposure, and controls. Apart from this exposure assessment, PCB concentrations were analyzed in umbilical-cord blood (pre-natal exposure) and in mother's milk (post-natal exposure). The health of all the children was examined at birth and thereafter a sub-group was followed up from 6 months to 4.5 years of age.

No differences regarding birth weight and head circumference were observed between the groups with different PCB exposure from fish [302] (Table 1).

The behavior and development of the children were studied at birth and at ages 6, 12, 36 and 54 months (Table 2). Newborns in the group with the highest PCB exposure from fish performed poorer in the test of neo-natal behavior than newborns in the control group [302]. Moreover, a negative association between pre-natal PCB exposure and some of the behavioral parameters were observed [350]. At ages 6 and 12 months a negative association was found between pre-natal, but not post-natal, PCB exposure and development of visual memory [268]. A negative association between pre-natal PCB exposure and cognitive development was found when the children were 3 years old [351]. At 4.5 years of age, no difference in cognitive development could be detected among the children with different PCB exposures.

USA – 11 Cities 1959-65

Pregnant women (N=42 000) from 11 US cities were recruited between 1959 and 1965 in a prospective study of reasons behind neurological diseases among children (N=55 000). Blood was sampled from the women on several occasions during pregnancy and PCB and DDE were analyzed in approximately 1700 samples from the final trimester. The measured PCB and DDE concentrations in blood serum were used to estimate pre-natal exposure to the compounds.

No association was found between pre-natal PCB exposure and birth weight, length of gestation, incidence of premature birth, and low birth weight in relation to length of gestation (N=1034 (Table 1) [352]. The risk of exposure and premature birth increased with increasing pre-natal DDE exposure. The same pattern was observed for low birth weight in relation to length of gestation (N=2380) [354]. When the children were one, four and seven-years old, the body height was negatively associated with pre-natal DDE exposure (N=1289-1540) [303].

The neurological status of the children was followed up several times during child-hood up to the age of seven years (Table 2). No associations were found

between pre-natal PCB exposure and mental and motor development when the children were seven years old (N=1207) [355]. At the same age no associations between pre-natal PCB exposure and IQ were observed (N=894). Positive associations were found between pre-natal PCB exposure and IQ when the children were four years old (N=894) [353].

In a sub-group of the cohort (N=810) the children's hearing was tested at the age of eight years, but no association with pre-natal PCB exposure was observed [356].

A study of associations between pre-natal DDE exposure and cryptorchidism, hypospadias and polythelia among boys in the study did not reveal significant associations between exposure and health effects (N=1137) [357].

Faroe Island 1986-87 and 1994-95

Two mother/child cohorts from the Faroe Islands were recruited with the main intention to study associations between methyl mercury exposure and neurological development of children. The Faroe Island inhabitants traditionally consume whale meat and blubber that contains high concentrations of both methyl mercury (meat) and PCB (blubber).

The first cohort was recruited during 1986 and 1987 and included approximately 1000 mother/child pairs [266, 267]. Umbilical-cord blood and tissue, as well as hair, were sampled from the study participants. PCB was analyzed in the umbilical-cord blood. The other cohort was recruited between 1994 and 1995 and included 182 mother/child pairs [108, 331]. Umbilical-cord blood was sampled as well as blood and hair from the mother and mother's milk. PCB was analyzed in blood serum from the mothers, mother's milk and umbilical-cord blood.

In the cohort from 1986-87, the study participants were divided into groups according to the amount of fish and whale the mothers had consumed during the pregnancy. The birth weight and length increased with the number fish meals the mother reported per week, but only up to a consumption level of 3 meals per week [358].

In both cohorts the neurological development of the children was studied (Table 2). At two weeks of age, the pre-natal methyl mercury exposure was negatively associated with results of the neurological testing of the infants born 1994-95 [331]. No associations were found between PCB/DDE exposure and neurological development. At the age of seven years extensive neurological testing was performed on the children born 1986-87. A few associations were found between pre-natal PCB and methyl mercury exposure and results from the neurological testing [266, 267, 359]. It was difficult to discriminate between possible PCB and

methyl mercury effects, since PCB and methyl mercury concentrations were significantly associated with each other in the umbilical-cord blood [266]. It was concluded that the influence of methyl mercury on neurological development appeared to be stronger than the effect of PCB [266].

Canada - Inuits

Fish and marine mammals are important parts of the diet among Inuits living in Arctic Québec. This is the main reason behind the high body burdens of heavy metals and polychlorinated organic compounds found in this population. Three epidemiological studies of infant and child health have been performed on this population.

During 1989-1990 213 Inuit women were recruited in the Nunavik area [304, 360, 361]. Mother's milk was sampled within three days after delivery. Pre-natal PCB exposure was estimated from the PCB concentrations in the milk from 109 mothers. Concentrations of chlorinated pesticides, dioxin-like PCBs and dioxins were also analyzed. The health of the children was followed for 12 months. Another study was performed in Nunavik between 1993 and 1996 including 490 pregnant women [333, 362]. Cord blood was sampled and PCB, DDE, HCB, lead and mercury were analyzed. When the children were five to six years of age hair and blood were sampled. A third study was performed 1995-2001 including 248 pregnant women from Nunavik [53, 362, 363]. At delivery, umbilical-cord blood and blood from the mothers were sampled and mother's milk was sampled one month after delivery. PCB and chlorinated pesticides were analyzed in the samples. Blood was sampled from the children when they were seven months old.

In a smaller study performed in 1995-1997, 47 mother/child pairs, living in fishing villages along the shore of the St. Lawrence River in Québec, Canada, were recruited together with 65 mother/child pairs from urban areas in the same region [364, 365]. PCB, DDE and mercury were analyzed in umbilical-cord blood. The birth weight, body length and head circumference were measured in the 1989-90 cohort (Table 1). Negative associations between mother's milk concentrations of PCB, HCB and PCDD/F TEQ and body length at birth were found among boys [361]. A positive association was observed between concentrations of PCB, HCB and PCDD/F TEQ in mother's milk and body length at birth in girls [361].

The neurological development of the children was tested in the 1993-96 cohort (Table 2). At ages five and six years, 110 children in the cohort were tested regarding neuro-motor function and the brain's ability to process visual information [333, 366]. No associations were found between neuro-motor function and concentrations of PCBs and chlorinated pesticides in umbilical-cord blood and in blood from the children at the time of testing [333]. Significant

associations were, however, found between PCB 153 concentrations in blood at the time of testing and brain's ability to process visual information [366].

Among children in the 1989-90 cohort, TSH levels in blood were analyzed at birth, but no significant association was found with mother's milk concentrations of PCB, chlorinated pesticides or dioxins [361] (Table 3).

In all studies of Inuit children associations between PCB and DDE exposures and infectious diseases were studied (Table 4). In the study of the 1989-90 cohort information about infections during the first year after birth was collected (N=171). Markers of immune function were also analyzed in the blood of the children [304]. The risk of middle ear infection was highest among children whose mothers had the highest mother's milk concentrations HCB and DDE. No associations were found between contaminant concentrations in mother's milk and markers of immune function. Among the children in the 1993-96 cohort information about incidence of upper and lower respiratory infections and middle-ear infections during the first five years after birth were collected from the medical journals of the children [332]. Cord blood concentrations of PCB 153 were positively associated with the risk of lower respiratory infections and middle-ear infections [332].

In the study of the 1995-2001 cohort, upper and lower respiratory infections, gastro-intestinal infections and middle ear infections among the children were studied during the first year of life (N=199) [53]. Significant positive associations between pre-natal exposure to PCB 153 and DDE (concentrations in blood from the mother) and infections were observed during the first 6 and 12 months of the children's life. For instance, the risk of lower respiratory infections and infections in general increased with increased PCB exposure [53]. (Table 4).

The PCB and mercury concentrations in umbilical-cord blood were two- to three-fold higher in the population living in fishing communities along the north shore of the St Lawrence River than in the population living in urban areas in the same region [364]. Many statistical comparisons were performed regarding markers of immune function between the two populations, and a lower percent of immature T-helper cells, lower levels of IgM in blood plasma, lower T-cell proliferation after mitotic stimulation *in vitro*, as well as higher levels of IgG in blood plasma, were found among the newly-born children from the fishing communities (Table 4) [364]. A negative correlation between PCB and mercury concentrations in cord blood and percentage of immature T-helper cells and T-cell proliferation was found. Moreover, mercury concentrations and IgM levels were negatively correlated with each other [364]. In a more detailed study of T-cell proliferation, a lower secretion of cytokines among the new-borns from the fishing societies was found [365]. Furthermore, a negative association between secretion of tumour necrosis factor-alpha and PCB concentrations in cord blood was observed [365].

Wisconsin

Between 1987 and 1989, 1112 pregnant women (age 18-35 years) from the Green Bay area were recruited. In this area, PCB-exposure may occur due to consumption of Lake Michigan fish [305]. Blood was sampled from the mothers at their first visit to the maternity clinic. Among the women who were asked to participate 82 % accepted to be included in the study.

A positive association between PCB concentration in blood during pregnancy and birth weight was observed, after adjustment of the results with 12 potential confounders (Table 1) [305]. The research team concluded that the PCB-exposure among the study participants probably was lower than among fish-consuming mothers from Michigan participating in a study showing a negative association between pre-natal PCB exposure and birth weight [340].

California, USA 1964-67

In the mid 1960's 20,500 pregnant women were recruited at maternity clinics in California [306]. PCB was analyzed in blood from 399 of the pregnant women during the second and third trimester. The majority of the women were of Caucasian or Afro-American heritage.

No associations between PCB body burden during pregnancy and birth weight, body length at birth, and gestational age were found if both sexes were included in the statistical analysis (Table 1) [306]. The results were adjusted for 13 potential confounders. The head circumference was negatively associated with PCB body burden of the mothers. A separate statistical analysis of the results based on sex showed a negative association between pre-natal PCB exposure and birth weight among boys after adjustment for gestational age. No such association was observed among the girls. Instead, the pre-natal PCB exposure was negatively associated with the gestational age. A follow-up of the growth of the children up to the age of five years did not show any associations with pre-natal PCB exposure, except for a negative association between PCB exposure and height of the girls [306].

In a similar study associations between pre-natal DDT compound exposure (*p,p'*-DDE, *p,p'*-DDT and *o,p'*-DDT) and the above mentioned health out-comes were reported [367] (Table 1). No significant associations were found, except for a small increase in gestational age with increased pre-natal exposure to *p,p'*-DDT and *o,p'*-DDT.

Japan 1998-2000

In a small study of 36 mother/child pairs from Japan, PCDD/F and dioxin-like PCBs were analyzed in mother's milk sampled during the third month after delivery [368, 369]. In a similar study, 71 mother's milk samples were analyzed for PCDD/F/PCB and analyses of chlorinated pesticides, among them *p,p'*-DDT and *p,p'*-DDE, were done in 75 samples [370, 371]. During 1999-2000 the study was enlarged to include 415 mother/child pairs from different parts of Japan [372]. In the enlarged study a group of bottle-fed children (N=53) was included. Blood was sampled from the children and thyroid hormones were analyzed along with white blood cells one year after birth. Exposure to the organochlorines was estimated from the levels in mother's milk and the length of breastfeeding.

The associations between pre-natal dioxin exposure and birth weight were studied (N=240) [307] in a sub-group of the enlarged cohort from 1999-2000 (Table 1). A negative correlation was observed, but this association disappeared after adjustment for potential confounders [307].

In the smallest cohort of 36 mother/child pairs, simple correlation analysis showed that the ratio between CD4⁺ lymphocytes (T-helper cells) and CD8⁺ (cytotoxic T-cells) increased with increasing total TEQ exposure from mother's milk (Table 4). Levels of thyroid hormones T3 and T4 decreased with increasing TEQ exposure (Table 3) [368, 369]. No association was found for TSH and TBG levels. In the somewhat enlarged cohort of about 70 participants a similarly negative association was observed for T4, but the TSH levels were positively associated with total TEQ exposure [370]. No significant association was found for T3 and TBG. DDT-exposure from mother's milk was negatively associated with the percentage of B-cells and T-helper cells (Table 4) [371]. In the largest cohort, no significant differences in thyroid hormone levels were found between nursed children and children fed with infant's formula [372]. In contrast to the smaller studies, no significant associations between PCDD/DF/PCB exposure and thyroid hormone levels were found (Table 3) [372].

Spain

Between 1997 and 1999, two mother/child cohorts were recruited in Ribera d'Ebre (N=70 pairs) and Menorca (N=405 pairs), Spain [373, 374]. PCB and chlorinated pesticides were analyzed in umbilical cord blood and mother's milk. The Ribera d'Ebre area is heavily polluted with HCB and some of the women had been occupationally exposed to HCB [373].

In the HCB-polluted area, a negative association between umbilical-cord blood HCB concentrations and body length at birth was observed, even after adjustment for potential confounders [308] (Table 1). No significant associations were

observed for birth weight and head circumference. Moreover, no associations were found between pre-natal PCB and DDE exposure and birth outcomes [308].

The neurological development of the children was studied during the first year after birth (Table 2) [375]. The children were tested with the Bayley Scales of Infant Development, which consists of tests for mental and for psychomotor development. DDE concentrations in umbilical-cord blood were negatively associated with the mental as well as the psychomotor development, also after adjustment for potential confounders [375]. No associations were found for PCB and HCB exposure. In another test, the Griffith Mental Development Scales, negative associations were observed between DDE exposure and psychomotor and social development, as well with a performance test. No associations were found for PCB and HCB exposure.

A study of cognitive development was performed on both Spanish cohorts (Table 2) [334]. The McCarthy Scales of Children's Abilities was used and this test can be divided into 18 parts consisting of 6 different developmental scales (general cognitive, verbal, perceptivo-performance, quantitative, memory and motor scales). In the Spanish study, new scales were constructed based on different combinations of the 18 parts of the test (verbal memory, working memory, short-term memory, and performance function) [334]. The concentrations of *p,p'*-DDT and *p,p'*-DDE, and the DDT/DDE ratio, were slightly higher in the Menorca cohort. When the results for the two cohorts were analyzed separately, several of the test results were negatively associated with *p,p'*-DDT concentrations in cord blood even after adjustment for potential confounders, whereas the associations with *p,p'*-DDE in most cases were not significant [334].

No associations between pre-natal exposure to DDE, PCB and HCB and thyroid hormone levels in umbilical-cord blood were found in the cohort from HCB-contaminated area [376] (Table 3).

In the Menorca cohort, associations between pre-natal DDE, PCB and HCB exposure and asthma were studied when the children had reached the ages of four and six years (Table 4) [377, 378]. Asthma was defined as wheezing when breathing at the age of four years, wheezing for an extended time period, and an asthma diagnosis by a physician. The risk of wheezing at the age of four years increased with increasing DDE exposure. No association was found between asthma diagnosis by a physician and pre-natal exposure to DDE. The different asthma end-points were not significantly associated with pre-natal exposure to PCB and HCB [378]. At the age of six years no associations between the studied out-comes and pre-natal exposure were found.

Fish consumers-Michigan

Between 1973 and 1991, blood was sampled from anglers (both men and women) living in Michigan, USA, and PCB and DDE concentrations were analyzed [309]. Information about life style and medical factors was collected during telephone interviews.

The associations between birth weight among the 168 children born 1968 by study participants and the concentrations of PCB and DDE in blood of the mothers on the sampling occasion closest to birth were studied [309] (Table 1). Children born by mothers with the highest PCB body burdens had a significantly lowered birth weight, also after adjustment for potential confounders. Only seven children were born to mothers with the highest PCB body burdens. No associations with DDE were observed [309].

In another study the association between sex ratio among the children and body burden of PCB and DDE among the fathers was studied [379]. The researchers identified 208 children born after 1963 to fathers with body burdens of PCB and DDE determined. The fathers were divided into a low and a high body burden group with approximately the same number of children in each group. More boys than girls were born to fathers in the high PCB body burden group, after adjustment for potential confounders. No significant differences were found for DDE, and the body burdens of the mothers were not significantly associated with sex ratio [379].

Michigan, PBB-cohort

Polybrominated biphenyls (PBB) have been used as flame retardants, and in 1973 PBB was accidentally mixed into animal feed in Michigan, USA [380]. A cohort of exposed individuals was established and blood samples were taken on several occasions between 1976 and 1981. PBB and PCB were measured in the blood. Among girls born between 1973 and 1992 (N=308) body height and weight were studied, using measurements taken at home by the parents 1997 and 1998. The families also answered a questionnaire about life style and medical factors. Girls over 18 years of age were also interviewed by telephone. The PBB concentrations in the blood of the mothers during pregnancy were determined from the PBB concentrations measured 1976-81 and from the half-life of PBB. The PCB concentration in the first blood sample taken from the mother was used as a measure of PCB body burden during pregnancy. No temporal trend in PCB concentrations were observed among the study participants.

No associations between pre-natal PBB-exposure and body height and length were found among the girls. Girls born to mothers with body burdens of PCB above the median level had a lower body weight than girls born to mothers with lower PCB body burdens [380].

Epidemiology - adults

Cancer

Endometrial cancer

In a population-based retrospective case-control study from Sweden, 10 chlorinated pesticides, including DDT and its metabolite DDE, and 10 PCB congeners, were analyzed in blood from 154 cases of endometrial cancer and 205 controls [381]. The women lived in the regions along the Swedish east coast and around Lake Vänern and Lake Vättern. Certain PCB compounds and chlorinated pesticides are suspected to have estrogenic activity. Estrogen is a strong risk factor for endometrial cancer making this cancer form interesting to study in relation to exposure to PCB and other similar compounds [381]. The participating women had never been treated with estrogen. The cancer cases had higher concentrations of DDT, DDE, β -HCH, oxychlordan and the PCB congener CB 28 in blood serum than the controls. After adjustment of the results for age and BMI, no significant associations were found between body burdens of PCB and chlorinated pesticides and cancer risk [381]. The concentrations of PCB 153 among the controls varied between 60 to 600 ng/g serum lipid whereas the concentrations of DDE varied between 110 to 2310 ng/g lipid (Table 20) [381].

Blood from the cases was sampled after cancer was diagnosed, but before treatment. The researchers draw the conclusion that if the disease had influenced the distribution and turnover of the compounds in the body, it would most likely have resulted in higher serum concentrations among the cases than among the controls [381].

In a smaller retrospective case-control study from Sweden, samples of adipose tissue from 76 cases of endometrial cancer and 39 controls were analyzed for 37 different PCB congeners, 8 chlorinated pesticides and 10 congeners of PBDE [88]. The samples were taken during surgery of the cases and the controls (benign disease). No significant associations between body burdens of contaminants and cancer were found. It was concluded that the study was based on few cancer cases and controls, and that the inclusion of controls with benign disease sensitive to hormones (hyperplasia in the endometrium) was a problem [88].

Among 90 endometrial cancer cases and 90 controls from the USA, 27 PCB congeners, 4 DDT compounds and 13 other chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were analyzed [382]. No statistically significant associations between body burdens of contaminants and risk of endometrial cancer were observed.

Breast cancer

This cancer form has been extensively studied with regard to PCB and DDE as risk factors, and several studies have been performed in the Nordic countries. Blood samples that were collected 1976-1978 in a Danish cohort of 7 712 women were used in a study of PCB and chlorinated pesticides as risk factors for breast cancer [383]. During 17 years of follow-up, 268 women were diagnosed with invasive breast cancer. Each cancer case was matched against 2 controls from the same cohort, and blood was analyzed for concentrations of total PCB, DDT, DDE, β -HCH and dieldrin. No associations between body burdens of the contaminants and risk of breast cancer were found, except for dieldrin. In this case the risk of cancer increased with increasing body burden of dieldrin, and it was concluded that the results gave support to the hypothesis that certain halogenated organic pollutants, such as dieldrin, may be a risk factors for breast cancer. No support was found for the hypothesis of PCBs and DDT-compounds as risk factors for breast cancer. An analysis of synergistic effects of the contaminants did not reveal significant associations with cancer [383].

In a follow-up of the Danish cohort, PCB and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were analyzed a second time in blood samples collected 1981-1983 [385]. The finding of increased risks of breast cancer among women with elevated dieldrin body burdens could not be confirmed, since the concentrations in blood serum were below the quantification limit. A significant positive association was however found between the mean concentration of DDT from the first and second blood samples and breast cancer risk after adjustment for potential confounders. Women with the highest body burdens of the single PCB congener CB 138 also had an increased risk of breast cancer. The association was, however, not significant after age-adjustment of the results [385].

The same Danish cohort was used in a study of PCBs and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites as risk factors for breast-cancer mortality [386]. The results of the analyses of the two blood samples from the earlier studies were used again. The researchers tested the hypothesis that some of the contaminants could affect malignant cancer cells that were not removed by the treatment of the disease. A high blood level of dieldrin was associated with an increased risk of breast-cancer mortality, even after adjustment for potential confounders. No other significant associations were found [386].

The Danish cohort was also used to study if PCB and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites are involved in the development of estrogen positive (ERp) breast cancer [387]. An increased cancer risk was observed with increased dieldrin body burdens among women with estrogen receptor negative (ERn) breast cancer. Otherwise no significant associations were found, except for an increased risk for ERp breast cancer among women with the highest body burden of PCB. It was concluded that the study did not support the hypothesis that

potentially estrogenic environmental pollutants increase the risk of ERp breast cancer. The positive association between body burdens of dieldrin and risk of ERn cancer was regarded as uncertain due to few cancer cases [387].

In another study of the Danish cohort it was found that mutations in the tumor-suppressor gene p53 did not appear to influence the associations between body burden of PCB and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites and the risk of breast cancer/breast cancer mortality [388]. The results were, however, regarded as uncertain since it was based on only a few cases with a mutation of p53 [388].

A separate Danish cohort of 29 000 women was recruited in 1993-1997 when biopsies of adipose tissue were taken [389]. The mean follow-up time was 4.8 years and during this period 434 menopausal women had attained breast cancer. The same number of controls was matched to the cases and 18 PCBs and 14 chlorinated pesticides/metabolites, among them DDT compounds, HCB, dieldrin and β -HCH, were analyzed in adipose tissue from the cases and controls. No significant associations between body burdens of single PCB congeners and breast cancer risk were found [389]. Among women with ERn breast cancer, a negative association with PCB body burden was found, i.e. the risk of breast cancer decreased with increased body burdens of PCBs. The risk of ERp breast cancer was not associated with PCB body burdens. A decreased risk of breast cancer with increased body burdens of β -HCH, oxychlorane and HCB was also found, even after adjustment for potential confounders. Moreover, a negative association was found between ERn breast cancer and body burdens of DDE, β -HCH, oxychlorane, *trans*-nonachlor and HCB. The study could not confirm the positive association between breast cancer and body burdens of dieldrin observed in the other Danish cohort [383, 389].

In a study from Norway a cohort of 25 000 women from the general population was used [384]. Blood was sampled from the women during 1973-1991. In an effort to include as many highly-exposed women as possible, women that had been working or living on a farm were over-represented in the cohort. In a prospective study, 150 controls were matched to 150 cases of breast cancer diagnosed 1993 or earlier. PCBs, dieldrin and DDE were analyzed in blood, among other contaminants. The results did not show any significant associations between body burdens of contaminants and risk of breast cancer, even after adjustment for potential confounders [384]. The finding of the Danish study of an increased risk of cancer among women with elevated body burdens of dieldrin could not be confirmed. It was concluded that it was not possible to study associations between body burdens of more easily metabolized PCB congeners and cancer, and that there still is a lack of studies of potentially susceptible sub-populations, such as women with a more PCB-inducible CYP1A1 enzyme. Moreover, studies of women with body burdens above background are lacking [384].

A small Swedish retrospective study (22 cases and 19 controls with benign disease) of associations between body burdens of PCDD/Fs, PCBs and chlorinated pesticides and risk of breast cancer was published in 1996 [390]. The researchers concluded that the cases had higher body burdens of octachlorinated dioxins, but the differences in body burdens were not significant after adjustment for potential confounders [390].

Several review articles have summarized the extensive literature on associations between body burdens of PCB/chlorinated pesticides and breast cancer risks [120, 121, 391-394]. These reviews have all concluded that the hypothesis that human exposure to PCB and DDT compounds is a cause of breast cancer is not supported by the scientific literature [120, 121, 391-394]. A few studies indicate that women with a certain CYP1A1 genotype are sensitive to high PCB exposures [395-399]. The studies published so far however, have been too small to make it possible to draw firm conclusions in this matter.

Soft tissue sarcoma (STS)

A few Swedish studies published during the period 1970 to 1980 have suggested that dioxins are risk factors for STS [400-403]. The strength of conclusions of these studies are uncertain, however, since the exposure assessment was performed using questionnaires and telephone interviews. Associations between dioxin exposure and STS have also been studied in occupationally-exposed cohorts. In some of these studies the number of STS cases was too small to allow for statistical analysis [139, 217, 404]. Other studies included a few more cases but the conclusions about associations between exposure and disease remain uncertain [140, 405, 406].

A recent study from Finland investigated the associations between STS and PCDD/F concentrations in adipose tissue including 110 cases and 227 controls that had been surgically treated for appendicitis [407]. The mean concentration of PCDD/F among the study participants was 33 pg TEQ/g lipid (range: 1-146 pg/g lipid). The statistical analysis did not reveal increased risks of STS with increased body burdens of PCDD/F. Instead, it was suggested that the reference category with the lowest body burdens of PCDD/Fs had the highest risk of STS (OR=1) [407]. A similar trend was observed when dioxin-like PCBs were included in the exposure assessment [408].

Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (NHL)

A small Swedish study of NHL analyzed 36 PCB congeners, DDE, HCB, four different chlordane compounds/metabolites and PBDE 47 in either adipose tissue

or blood [87]. NHL cases (N=50) and controls (N=47) were recruited in 1994-1997 and were living in an area around the cities of Uppsala and Örebro. Blood samples were also collected from 32 cases and 36 controls in 1997-1999 recruited at the Örebro Hospital and the University Hospital of Lund, Sweden. The statistical analysis showed an increased risk of NHL among study participants with a body burden of immunotoxic PCBs, HCB, some of the chlordanes compounds and PBDE that was higher than the median body burden among all the study participants, after adjustment for age, sex, BMI and type of biological sample (adipose tissue or blood). It was not possible from the publication to identify the PCB congeners claimed to be immunotoxic. The body burden of total PCBs and DDE were not significantly associated with an increased NHL risk. In a multivariate analysis of the results only the association with PBDE 47 was statistically significant. Among study participants with a high titre of Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) an increased risk of NHL was indicated for individuals with high exposure to the studied pollutants [87].

In another small Swedish case-control study of PCB, DDE, HCB and chlordanes compounds as risk factors for a type of NHL, called hairy cell leukemia, 54 cases and 54 age-, sex- and residence-matched controls were recruited [409]. No significant associations between blood levels of the studied compounds and cancer risk were found. Among individuals with a high titre of anti-bodies for EBV those with a high body burden of the studied compounds had an increased cancer risk [409]. Blood was sampled years after diagnosis of the cases, and it cannot be excluded that the blood concentrations of the pollutants were affected by the disease and the medical treatment.

A case-control study of PCB and DDT compounds as risk factors for NHL was performed in the USA [410]. Among over 25 000 participants in a study of cancer and stroke, 87 participants were diagnosed with NHL between 1975 and 1989. Blood was sampled for the entire cohort (N=1 074) and the total concentration of PCB and DDT was analyzed in 74 cases and in 147 controls with no cancer diagnosis at the time when the matched case was diagnosed with disease. A significant increased risk of NHL (adjusted odds ratio (OR):4.1 (confidence interval (CI): 1.4-11.9) was found among participants with the highest body burdens of PCB. A dose-response relationship was also observed. No significant association was found for DDT. The researchers were careful in their conclusions, since the results had not been adjusted for potential confounders such as food habits and body weight [410].

In a following study of the same cohort, associations between body burdens of chlorinated pesticides and NHL were studied [411]. No significant associations were found. It was concluded that the results did not support the hypothesis that the studied compounds are important risk factors for NHL. However, the study

design made it impossible to draw conclusions about the possibility of minor influences of the compounds on NHL risk [411].

A large number of PCB-congeners, including dioxin-like PCBs, PCDD/Fs, and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were analyzed in blood from 100 cases and 100 controls in a population-based study from the USA [412]. The study participants were randomly selected from a larger case-control cohort, based on the requirement of enough blood sample volume for PCDD/F analysis. A significant positive association between body burdens of PCDD/F/PCB TEQ and NHL was found. A statistical analysis of the results for PCB TEQ, PCDD TEQ and PCDF TEQ showed that only the trend for PCDF TEQ was statistically significant [412]. The risk of NHL, however, did not differ between the reference exposure quartile and the other quartiles with higher exposure. A positive trend of NHL risk was also observed for some of the studied PCB congeners, but the associations between NHL and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were not statistically significant [412]. Information about potential confounders, such as smoking, and body height and weight, was lacking for many of the study participants. The cases also had lower levels of blood lipids than the controls. It was proposed that this difference was disease related or that there was a difference in food consumption the day before blood sampling between cases and controls. It was not possible to draw conclusions about how the blood lipid differences between controls and cases influenced the results [412].

In another study from the USA, a national bio-bank of adipose tissue from surgical patients or deceased patients, sampled between 1969 and 1983, was used [413]. PCB and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were analyzed in adipose tissue from 175 cases and 481 controls, matched for age, sex, area of residence and ethnicity. Adipose tissue concentrations of heptachlorepoxide, oxychlorane, dieldrine, *p,p'*-DDE and β -HCH were positively associated with NHL risk. The strongest associations were found for dieldrine and heptachlorepoxide. Problems with the PCB analyses made it impossible to draw conclusions about associations with NHL risk. The researchers highlighted several problems with the study, such as lack of information about potential confounders and the fact that many samples of adipose tissue had been taken after the patient had deceased [413].

Pancreatic cancer

PCB (11 congeners) and DDE and other chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were analyzed in blood lipids from 113 cases and 82 age- and sex-matched controls in a study that was a part of a larger case-control study of risk factors for pancreatic cancer [414]. The cases had higher PCB and DDE levels than the controls. After adjustment for potential confounders (age, sex and ethnicity) the positive association between PCB levels and cancer remained significant. However, the large weight loss among the cases before blood sampling made it difficult to

interpret the results. Moreover, the cases had lower blood lipid levels than the controls [414].

A small case-control study performed in Spain showed that pancreatic cancer cases with a so called *K-ras* mutation in codon 12 (N=34) had significantly higher body burdens of DDE, DDT and the three PCB congeners PCB 138, PCB 153 and PCB 180 than cases without the mutation (N=17) [415]. A comparison with 26 controls, that had been through surgery of benign diseases (not of gastro-intestinal origin), showed that the body burdens of contaminants among cases without the mutation did not differ with those of the controls. Cases with the mutation had significantly higher body burdens of DDT and DDE than the controls [415].

Colon and liver cancer

A follow-up of cancer mortality among more than 14 000 workers from the USA, with potential PCB-exposure (more than 90 days) did not show an increased risk for liver cancer (21 cases) in comparison with the general population [416].

In China DDT is still used in the control of malaria mosquitoes, which makes China a good setting for studies of associations between DDT and DDE body burdens and liver cancer. Blood was sampled in 1984-1985 from over 29 000 subjects from the general population in a study of oesophagus and stomach cancer and nutritional intervention [417]. In May 2001 186 study participants had become sick in liver cancer and blood samples were available from 168 of these cancer cases. The DDT compounds were analyzed in these blood samples and in blood from matched controls (N=385). High body burdens of *p,p'*-DDT was associated with an increased cancer risk after adjustment for important risk factors for liver cancer. No associations were found between body burdens of DDE and cancer. The results indicated that the risk of cancer was largest among study participants with high ongoing DDT exposure [417].

A case-control study of colorectal cancer from Spain (132 cases and 76 controls) indicated a positive association between blood concentrations of PCB congeners PCB 28 and PCB 118 and cancer risk [418]. For other studied PCB congeners and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites no significant associations were found.

Testis cancer

DDE concentrations in mother's milk from the different Nordic countries during a time period of 20 years were compared, in an ecological study of DDE as a risk factor for testis cancer, [419]. No marked differences in mother's milk concentrations of the DDT metabolite was observed, and the researchers concluded that there were no marked differences in pre- and post-natal DDE exposure between the Nordic countries. These findings were compared with the

large difference in incidence of testis cancer that is evident between the countries. It was concluded that DDE is probably not an important risk factor for testis cancer [419].

A few publications have reported results from a Swedish case-control study of testis cancer [420, 421]. Concentrations of 38 PCB congeners, DDE, HCB and 6 chlordanes compounds were analyzed in blood from cases (N=61) and age-matched controls from the general population. Blood was also sampled from mothers of 44 cases and 45 controls. No associations between body burdens of the contaminants among the men and cancer risk were found, except for an increased risk among men with high body burdens of one of the chlordanes compounds after adjustment of the results for age of the men and BMI. An increased risk of testis cancer was however found among men with mothers that had body burdens of PCB, HCB and two of the chlordanes compounds that were above the median body burdens of the control mothers. The researchers speculated that the body burdens of the mothers mirrored the body burdens that the mothers had during pregnancy many years earlier [420].

In another publication about this cohort, the PCB compounds had been grouped according to biological activity [421]. No significant associations between body burdens of the different PCB compound groups among the men and testis cancer were observed. An increased cancer risk was found among study participants whose mothers had body burdens of enzyme-inducing PCBs and PCB TEQ that were higher than the median body burdens of the control mothers. Similar associations were found for PBDE.

Prostate cancer

A Swedish study of PCB, HCB, DDE and 6 different chlordanes compounds as risk factors for prostate cancer included 58 cancer cases and 20 controls that had been through surgery of benign disease [422]. The environmental pollutants were analyzed in adipose tissue. An increased cancer risk was observed among study participants with body burdens of PCB 153 and a chlordanes compound above the median body burden of the control group. Otherwise no significant associations were found. In the group of participants with higher levels of prostate-specific antigen (PSA) stronger associations between cancer and body burdens were observed [422].

In case-control study from the USA (58 cases and 99 controls) a positive association was found between prostate cancer and blood concentrations of the PCB congener PCB 180 and the chlorinated metabolite oxychlordanes after adjustment for age, BMI and prostatitis [423]. No significant associations were found for the other 29 PCB congeners studied as well as for 17 chlorinated pesticides/metabolites. In another publication including the same cohort

associations between groups of PCB compounds and prostate cancer risk were reported [424]. A positive association between blood concentrations (fresh weight-based) of three different groups of PCB compounds and cancer was found after adjustment for age, BMI and prostatitis. After adjustment of the results for levels of blood lipids, no significant associations were observed [424].

Diabetes

Among 205 elderly women from Sweden, participating as controls in a study of risk factors for endometrial cancer (see above), associations between life-style and medical factors and body burdens of PCBs and chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were studied [51]. Only seven women reported that they had diabetes (type unknown) and after adjustment of the results for other determining factors women with diabetes had significantly higher concentrations of HCB in blood lipids (30 % higher) than women reporting that they did not have diabetes. For the other studied compounds no significant differences in blood lipid concentrations were observed between diabetic and non-diabetic study participants, even if the mean concentrations were higher among the diabetic women. The researchers concluded that the disease probably was the cause of the higher blood concentrations of the compounds [51].

Between 1999 and 2002, PCB 153, 1,2,3,4,6,7,8-heptachlorodibenzo-*p*-dioxin, 1,2,3,4,6,7,8,9-octachlorodibenzo-*p*-dioxin, oxychlorodane, *p,p'*-DDE and *trans*-nonachlor were analyzed in blood from over 2000 men and women (age ≥ 20 years) in a national health survey in the USA [425]. Among these participants 217 had diabetes (type not specified). The risk of diabetes was strongly associated (positive) with the body burdens of all six compounds, after adjustment for age, sex, ethnicity, social group, BMI and waist circumference. Additional adjustment for blood triglycerides, cholesterol, dietary fat intake and smoking did not affect the results. The cross-sectional study had the same problem as the studies summarized above, i.e. the blood samples were taken when the diabetic subjects already had the disease.

In a study of pregnant women from the USA, women with type 2 diabetes (44 women) had a 30 % higher mean blood concentration of PCB than non-diabetic women (N=2201), after adjustment for potential confounders [426]. As with the other studies, the researchers could not conclude if the higher concentrations were causing the disease or were caused by the disease.

Nine study participants with diabetes had significantly higher concentrations of PCDD/F, dioxin-like PCBs and non-dioxin-like PCBs in blood than the other non-diabetic study participants, in a study of 257 men and women from the general Belgian population [204].

Osteoporosis

Ten PCB congeners, 5 DDT-compounds and 6 other chlorinated pesticides/metabolites were analyzed in blood serum lipids from taken from 115 men between the ages of 40 to 75 years from Uppsala County, Sweden [162]. No clear associations between blood levels of the compounds and bone density were found when three different measurements were performed on three skeletal sites. However, a weak negative association between body burden of DDE and bone density was observed.

A negative association between bone density and DDE body burden was found in a smaller study of associations between bone density and body burdens of DDE among 68 sedentary elderly women [163]. The association did not change markedly after adjustment for age and estrogen treatment. Another study of 103 women from the USA has been published, where no significant associations between bone density and body burdens of DDE were found [164].

Reproduktion

Age at puberty

Associations between development of puberty and pre-natal PCB exposure were studied among 156 fourteen year old boys from the Faero Islands [213]. No significant associations were found between PCB exposure and development of sex organs and pubic hair.

Body height and weight were measured at the time of puberty in a follow up of development of 316 girls and 278 boys from the North Carolina cohort in the USA [345]. No significant associations between pre- and post-natal PCB and DDE exposure and age at puberty and the body size measurements. The boys with the highest DDE exposures had a higher body weight at puberty than the boys with the lowest exposures.

No associations between pre-natal DDT exposure and body height, weight, BMI and skeletal development at puberty were observed among 304 boys in another study from the USA [427].

In a Belgian study of girls treated for premature puberty, researchers found that a large proportion of the girls were not born in Belgium, in comparison with the expected proportion [428]. Higher blood concentrations of DDE were found among these girls than among Belgian-born girls treated for the same condition [428].

Among 200 Belgian adolescents with a mean age of 17 years, three di-ortho PCBs and total dioxin-like activity were analyzed in blood and the puberty development

was estimated [429]. A negative association between dioxin-like activity in blood and breast development was found among the girls after adjustment for age, BMI, use of contraceptives and the parents' social group. No associations were observed between development of pubic hair and dioxin-like activity and PCB concentrations in blood among the girls, or between breast development and concentrations of PCB. A negative association between development of sex organs and concentrations of PCB 138 was found among the boys, as well as between development of pubic hair and concentrations of PCB 153 and PCB 180. No associations with dioxin-like activity in blood were found among the boys [429].

Among 151 women, that were children to mothers participating in a cohort of high consumers of fish from the Great Lakes, USA, a lowered age of puberty with increased pre-natal DDE exposure was observed [430]. After adjustment of the results for body size at puberty, the association was not statistically significant. No significant association was found for PCB exposure [430].

A decreased age at puberty with increased total concentrations of DDT compounds in blood was found among non-smoking Chinese female textile workers (N=466) [431]. The results remained significant after adjustment for potential confounders. Blood was sampled several years after puberty.

The blood concentrations of DDE were not associated with age at puberty among 138 girls between the ages of 10 to 17 years from the Akwesasne Mohawk Nation in USA and Canada [432]. For the PCB compounds classified as potentially estrogenic, a negative association between age at puberty and blood concentrations of the PCB compounds was found, even after adjustment for potential confounders.

Menstrual cycle

In a study from the USA, 2314 women were asked about their menstrual cycles at the time of blood sampling in the 1960's [433]. An increased menstrual cycle length with increased blood concentrations of total PCB was observed. No associations between PCB concentrations and irregular cycles, length of bleeding, amount of bleeding and menstrual pain were found. The blood concentrations of DDE were not associated with the studied menstrual parameters, except for a positive association with irregular menstruation among primiparous women and among women that had given birth to their last child more than 2 years before blood sampling [433].

Among 50 women, living in the USA but who had been born in Southeast Asia, no association between blood concentrations of PCBs and total menstrual cycle length or between blood concentrations and length of follicular and luteal phase

was found, [170]. The study covered a time span of three menstrual cycles. For DDT and DDE no significant associations were found, except for a positive association between DDE and length of the luteal phase, when a woman with very long menstrual cycles were excluded from the reference group with the lowest DDE exposure [170].

The total concentration of DDT compounds in blood was positively associated with the risk of having at least one short menstrual cycle (<21 days) during the previous year among 466 Chinese textile workers, after adjustment for potential confounders [431]. The association was strengthened if 54 women were excluded because of alcohol use, miscarriage, abortion, or use of oral or inter-uterin contraceptives devices. No association between DDT exposure and the risk of having at least one long menstrual cycle was observed.

Sex hormones

Associations between blood levels of sex hormones and environmental pollutants among women are normally difficult to study since the hormone levels fluctuate during the menstrual cycle. During the third trimester of pregnancy hormone levels are more stable. In a small study of associations between body burdens of PCDD/F/PCBs and estrogen metabolism among 50 women from Taiwan, significantly negative associations between the ratio of two estrogen metabolites (4-OH-E₂/2-OH-E₂) and blood concentrations of TCDD, 1,2,3,7,8-pentaCDD, total PCDD, total PCDF and total TEQ in late pregnancy were observed [169]. The associations with TCDD and 1,2,3,7,8-pentaCDD remained significant after adjustment for age, other dioxin compounds and PCBs.

In a study of menstrual cycles among 50 women, living in the USA but who were born in Southeast Asia, no association was found between blood concentrations of PCB and hormone levels (estrogen and progesterone) during menstruation [170]. The study covered three menstrual cycles. For DDE a negative association with levels of progesterone during luteal phase was observed [170].

Among 305 Swedish men of ages 18-21 years the blood concentrations of PCB 153 were positively associated with the blood levels of steroid hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) and negatively associated with the ratio between levels of testosterone and SHBG after adjustment of the results for BMI [212]. No associations were observed for inhibin B, total level of testosterone, estradiol, FSH and LH. The significant associations were weak and the researchers concluded that the lack of similar associations among older men with higher body burdens of PCB indicates that the associations observed among the younger men may be due to chance [212].

On the Faeroe Islands associations between pre-natal PCB exposure and hormone levels were studied among 156 fourteen year-old boys [213]. No significant associations were observed between PCB exposure and levels of inhibin B, SHBG, FSH, LH and testosterone.

Levels of sex hormones, PCB (89 congeners) and DDE were analyzed in blood from 178 men with different levels of consumption of fish from the Great Lakes in the USA [222]. Levels of SHBG-bound testosterone were negatively associated with the body burdens of total PCB after adjustment for potential confounders and exclusion of three individuals with liver disease. No significant associations were found between body burdens of PCB and levels of free testosterone, FSH, LH, DHEAS and SHBG [222].

Among 107 men, that 50 years ago (1946-1950) were exposed to DDT during a campaign against the malaria mosquito, hormone levels (LH, FSH, estradiol, testosterone, SHBG) were analyzed in blood [434]. Correlation analyses showed no significant associations between DDE concentrations in the sampled blood and hormone levels. Estimated exposure levels during the malaria campaign were also not correlated with the hormone levels [434].

No associations between pre-natal DDT exposure and blood levels of testosterone and a testosterone metabolite were found among 304 male teenagers from the USA [427].

In Thailand the levels of sex hormones were analyzed among 97 men together with the concentrations of DDT [435]. The estradiol levels were negatively associated with body burdens of *p,p'*-DDE and positively associated with *o,p'*-DDE, after adjustment for age and BMI. The associations were, however, weak.

Among 137 African-American farmers from North Carolina, USA, the associations between blood levels of androgen hormones and *p,p'*-DDE were studied [436]. No significant associations between DDE-body burden and hormone levels were found.

Time to pregnancy (TTP)

In a study from the USA, PCB and *p,p'*-DDE were analyzed in blood from 390 women between 1959 to 1965 [180]. The women lived in different parts of the country and women that reported that they had been planning to get pregnant before blood sampling were asked about TTP. No significant associations between PCB and DDE body burdens and TTP were found [180].

Among 289 women from the USA which answered questions about their most recently-planned pregnancy, a shorter TTP with increased pre-natal *p,p'*-DDE

exposure was found [181]. For *p,p'*-DDT an opposite association was observed. Adjustment for potential confounders did not change the observed associations [181].

Miscarriage

Among 388 newly-wed female Chinese textile workers associations between blood concentrations of DDT compounds and miscarriage were studied [192]. The women donated urine samples daily after cessation of contraceptive use, which made it possible to detect early miscarriages that otherwise, would be hard to diagnose. Among the women, 128 early miscarriages were detected, as well as 36 miscarriages later in pregnancy. A significant positive association between body burden of DDT compounds and early miscarriage was found. No associations were found for miscarriage later during pregnancy [192].

In a large study of 1717 women from the USA, blood was sampled during pregnancy and the women were concurrently asked about the outcome of earlier pregnancies [191]. A significant positive association between miscarriage and blood concentrations of *p,p'*-DDE was observed. The researchers were cautious in their conclusions since women that had a full-term pregnancy may have eliminated more DDE from the body than women with miscarriages [191].

Concentrations of *p,p'*-DDT and -DDE were analyzed in mother's milk from Australian 815 women that had given birth to their first child [188]. No statistically significant associations between concentrations of the DDT compounds and the risk of an earlier stillbirth or miscarriage were found. In a smaller study of 200 mothers, no associations between PCB concentrations in mother's milk and stillbirth or miscarriage were observed [437].

In Germany 1989-1993 the blood concentrations of PCB, DDT compounds and other chlorinated pesticides were analyzed among 89 women with repeated miscarriages and the results were compared with concentrations found among women with no miscarriages [189]. No differences in blood concentrations between women with early miscarriages and women with late miscarriages, or between women with two and three miscarriages. Women with four miscarriages had higher PCB concentrations than the other women.

In a small case-control study from Japan, including 45 cases with at least 3 miscarriages and 30 controls with no miscarriage or that had not yet been pregnant, no significant associations between blood concentrations of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE and risk of miscarriage were found [190]. The age and BMI of the cases did not differ from the controls.

Endometriosis

PCB and PCDD/F were analyzed in blood from 139 infertile women from Japan [202]. After diagnosis with laparoscopy the women were divided into two groups; one group with endometriosis of stages II-IV and a control group with endometriosis of stages 0-I. After adjustment for potential confounders no significant increased risk for endometriosis in stages II-IV with increased body burden of PCB and PCDD/F was found [202].

In a small study of 40 Italian women with endometriosis and 40 women with other gynaecological problems, an increased risk for endometriosis was observed even at low blood concentrations of PCBs [200]. The results did not change after adjustment for age and smoking.

In a small study from Belgium, the associations between risks for peritoneal (N=25) and adenomyotic endometriosis (N=25) and blood concentrations of PCDD/F and dioxin-like PCBs were studied [201]. The concentrations of the contaminants were significantly higher among women with adenomyotic endometriosis than among control women without gynaecological problems (N=21). After adjustment for potential confounders a significant positive association was found between blood concentrations of total TEQ and risk of having one of the two endometriosis types [201].

Another small study from Belgium, including 10 cases of endometriosis and 132 controls, found no differences in blood PCB and PCDD/F concentrations between cases and controls [204].

PCBs were analyzed in the blood of 32 women from the USA with diagnosed endometriosis and 52 women with no disease [203]. An increased risk of endometriosis was found among women with the highest body burdens of PCBs that had been classified as anti-estrogenic. No increased risk was observed after adjustment for potential confounders.

Menopause

In a study of 874 women from the USA, of ages 24 years and older that had been exposed to polybrominated biphenyls (PBB) and PCB (1976-78), associations between blood concentrations of these compounds and time to menopause were investigated [205]. In 1997 the women were asked if they had menstruated during the last year. Women that had reached menopause before exposure were excluded from the study. No associations between blood concentrations of the compounds and age at menopause were found [205].

Between 1993 and 1996, 1407 women from North Carolina, USA, were recruited in a case-control study of PCB and DDT compounds as risk factors for breast cancer [206]. Both cases and controls were asked if they had stopped having menstruation. If the answer was yes the women were asked why the menstruation had stopped and at what age. A statistical analysis of association between body burdens of PCBs and age at menopause did not show any statistically significant associations [206]. For *p,p'*-DDE a positive association was indicated after adjustment for potential confounders, i.e. women with the highest body burden of DDE were on average 1 year older at menopause than women with the lowest body burden. The researchers were cautious in their conclusions since the blood concentrations of DDE were analyzed many years after the women had reached menopause [206].

In a study from 1982-1984 of associations between exposure to DDT-compounds and age at menopause among 219 women from the USA, that had already reached menopause, the women with the highest body burden of *p,p'*-DDT were younger at menopause than women from the lowest exposure group [207]. No statistically significant associations were found for *p,p'*-DDE. As in the other study summarized above, the researchers were cautious in their conclusions since the blood concentrations of the contaminants were measured many years after the women had reached menopause. It may be possible that the body burdens of DDT compounds are lower among women with a late menopause due to a higher elimination of the compounds due to menstrual bleeding. Information about certain potential confounders, such as nursing, was lacking.

Function of sex glands and sperm quality

Among 305 male conscripts between the ages of 18 to 21 years a weak but statistically significant association was found between blood concentrations of PCB 153 and percentage of motile sperms [212]. No significant correlations were found between PCB 153 and volume of the testis, semen volume, sperm concentration, and sperm count. The associations were not markedly changed by adjustment for potential confounders such as smoking and BMI.

No significant associations were found between pre-natal PCB exposure and testis volume among 156 fourteen year-old boys living on the Faeroe Islands [213]. Moreover, no associations were found between PCB and non-descendant testies (N=19) and spermaturia (sperms in the urine) (N=58).

The sperm quality was investigated among 29 hospital patients with background body burdens of PCB and *p,p'*-DDE [438]. Eleven patients had problems with sperm quality and 18 patients had a normal sperm quality. The study was too small to enable the researchers to draw conclusions about associations between sperm quality and body burdens of the contaminants. In a following study of 303

men, recruited from pairs with fertility problems, synergistic negative interactions were observed between body burdens of PCBs and certain phthalates and sperm motility [214]. No associations were observed for several other sperm quality indicators.

Up to year 2000, DDT was used in the control of malaria in certain areas of Mexico. Among men (N=116) involved in the malaria control campaign the associations between DDT exposure and sperm quality were studied [215]. Several statistically significant negative associations between *p,p'*-DDE concentrations in blood and sperm quality indicators, such as percentage of motile sperms, percentage of sperm with damaged tails and condensation of chromatin were observed.

1. Mikroprofil Gris – Kartläggning av mikroorganismer på slaktkroppar av M Lindblad.
2. Nyckelhålet för spannmålsprodukter av A Laser Reuterswärd.
3. Interkalibrering av laboratorier. Mikrobiologi – Livsmedel, januari 2006 av C Normark och K Mykkänen.
4. Studie av förstföderskor – Organiska miljögifter hos gravida och ammande. Del 1 Serumnivåer av A Glynn, M Aune, P O Darnerud, S Atuma, S Cnattingius, R Bjerselius, W Becker och Y Lind.
5. Kontroll av rests substanser i levande djur och animaliska livsmedel – Resultat 2005 av I Nordlander, H Green och I Nilsson.
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7. Proficiency Testing – Food Chemistry, Trace Elements in Food, Round T-12 by C Åstrand and L Jorhem.
8. Krav på livsmedelsföretagarna – Utbildning i livsmedelshygien.
9. Interkalibrering av laboratorier. Mikrobiologi – Livsmedel, april 2006 av C Normark och K Mykkänen.
10. Interkalibrering av laboratorier. Mikrobiologi – Dricksvatten 2006:1, mars av T Šlapokas och C Gunnarsson.
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12. Rapportering av dricksvattentillsyn 2005 – Tillsynsmyndigheternas rapportering om dricksvattentillsyn av D Rosling.
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14. Kontroll av svenska musselodlingar av I Nordlander.
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17. Proficiency Testing – Food Chemistry, Vitamins in Foods, Round V-4 by H S Strandler and A Staffas.
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19. Riksprojekt 2005: Centralt producerad mat till särskilt och enskilt boende – mikrobiologi och tillämpning av M Lindblad och A Westöö.
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21. Interkalibrering av laboratorier. Mikrobiologi – Dricksvatten 2006:2, september av T Šlapokas, C Gunnarsson och M Foucard.
22. Proficiency Testing – Food Chemistry, Trace Elements in Food, Round T-13 by C Åstrand and L Jorhem.
23. Interkalibrering av laboratorier. Mikrobiologi – Livsmedel, oktober 2006 av C Normark, K Mykkänen, I Tillander och C Gunnarsson.

1. Algtoxiner i avsaltat dricksvatten.
2. Nationellt tillsynsprojekt 2006 om livsmedelsmärkning.
3. Indikatorer för bra matvanor av W Becker.
4. Interkalibrering av laboratorier: Mikrobiologi – Livsmedel, januari 2007 av C Normark och K Mykkänen.
5. Proficiency Testing – Food Chemistry, Nutritional Components of Food, Round N-39 by L Merino and M Åström.
6. Nutrient Analysis of Dairy Foods and Vegetarian Dishes by M Arnemo, M Arnemo, S Johansson, L Jorhem, I Mattisson, S Wretling and C Åstrand.
7. Proficiency Testing: Food Chemistry, Trace Elements in Food, Round T:14 by C Åstrand and L Jorhem.
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